

ARTICULATING THE SIGNIFICANCE OF ARCHAEOLOGICAL SITES

Prepared by the 'Articulating the Significance of Archaeological Sites' Working Group

Published by:

Europae Archaeologiae Consilium (European Archaeological Council)
p/a Urban.brussels
Mont des Arts 10-13
1000 Bruxelles, BELGIUM
www.europae-archaeologiae-consilium.org

EAC Guidelines 11: Free publication distributed by the EAC

DOI: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14975018

Belgian Library issue number: D/2026/15813/01

Layout: Design Penguin

Cover: Aerial view of Newgrange, part of the Brú na Bóinne - Archaeological Ensemble of the Bend of the Boyne - World Heritage Property © Photographic Archive, National Monuments Service, Government of Ireland.

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INTRODUCTION

Thor Ingólfsson Hjaltalín

The European Archaeological Council (EAC) Working Group on Articulating the Significance of Archaeological Sites was formed in response to the [2017 “Making Choices” survey](#) (EAC, 2018), which identified key areas where guidance was needed in archaeological heritage management. One of the most pressing challenges was how to evaluate the significance of archaeological sites – a concept that is inherently philosophical, shaped by cultural narratives, and constantly evolving.

The group’s primary aim was to explore and provide an overview of the diverse methods and systems used across Europe to assess archaeological significance. Initially, the Working Group aimed to define “best practice” in evaluating significance. However, it became clear that a universal standard was impractical due to the diversity of national systems and cultural contexts. Those who are charged with the assessment of archaeological significance are first and foremost heritage managers who prepare and use state inventories of heritage. The secondary users are practitioners who must articulate the significance of archaeological heritage to a range of public audiences, especially those involved in land use and development planning and development control. Diverse approaches and different systems exist in different countries. The material collected by the Working Group reveals the wide range of methodological diversity in different European countries.

The process led to the idea of a publication that could serve as a bank of ideas or provide examples of best practice. Neither were considered ambitious enough in themselves. But with further thought, a combination of both was considered a practical alternative. The Working Group can indeed present an inspiring bank of ideas – presenting how the evaluation of archaeological sites and assessment of their significance is conducted in different parts of Europe, and instead of talking of “best practice”, we talk about “good practice”. In all the diversity of methods, there are common syntax principles and objectives.

Significance is not a fixed value; it is dynamic and context-dependent. It raises fundamental questions: significant to whom, and under what circumstances? Can it be measured objectively, or does it shift with time, place, and societal change? These questions form the philosophical backbone of the guidance, which begins with reflections on the nature of significance in heritage management. It then traces the historical development of how societies have valued heritage – from national regulations and protections to international conventions and declarations. Over time, there has been a clear shift from regulation to participation, from exclusion to inclusion, reflecting broader changes in societal attitudes and governance.

The guidance also draws on two surveys conducted by the EAC in 2017 and 2019. These surveys revealed a wide range of practices and legal frameworks across member states. For example, in some countries, sites are automatically protected based on age – either before an absolute calendar date, or using a rolling boundary (‘more than 100 years old’). Such rules are in a way based on the idea that everything is equally valuable, but in practice, it is not. In most countries there are criteria for putting sites on an inventory or a national protection list, but when using the automatic 100 years rule it in a way becomes the other way around. The heritage managers often need, because of different reasons, to evaluate what should be taken of the list, rather than what should be put on it. But in many countries, there is no time limit on the definition of archaeological heritage. Then, it often comes to evaluation or ratings on values such as: historical, scientific, aesthetic, traditional/intangible, social, folkloric, religious, rarity, uniqueness, just to mention a few. It is also interesting to see how sites are listed in different countries, and it sometimes seems that the mechanisms or criteria are not transparent or consistent enough, even based on quite subjective evaluations.

Time plays a crucial role in shaping significance. The 2019 survey asked whether changes in social circumstances, beliefs, and fashions affect how significance is evaluated. All respondents agreed that significance is not constant – it changes over time. This fluidity can be sensitive, especially when heritage is used politically – for good or bad. Shifts in public interest, such as increased attention to 20th-century remains and the growing importance of landscapes and intangible heritage, all influence how sites are valued. As one survey response put it, “Significance is significance to people: people change.”

Context also matters. In times of war or natural disaster, the significance of archaeological sites may be deprioritized. With the increased danger of armed conflict spreading in Europe, the question of how different contexts can affect the evaluation of significance and the protection of sites becomes more pressing. In wartime, and preparation for war, significance of archaeological sites is not dealt with in the same manner as in time of peace. The same can also be said about natural hazards. For example, during a volcanic eruption in Iceland, legal protections were suspended to allow for emergency construction, illustrating how urgent needs can override heritage considerations. In the end, it often comes down to competition of interests.

The guidance includes comparative studies of five European countries, showcasing both commonalities and differences in how significance is assessed in the heritage management system of each country. It also presents a diverse array of case studies – from Stone Age sites to contemporary landscapes, from single monuments to expansive regions – spanning locations all across Europe. These cases demonstrate varied reasons for evaluating significance. It plays an important role in development-led archaeology and land-use management, planning and development, and also for research, public benefit, and national listing of sites and monuments.

Ultimately, articulating the significance of archaeological sites is a vital task for heritage managers. It must be done transparently, consistently, and with clear reasoning. Decisions about protection, excavation, and research must be grounded in sound methodology, not opinion. Heritage managers must be able to explain cultural heritage matters – whether for scientific, economic, or social reasons – and must be prepared to defend those values in the face of competing interests. This guidance, along with its strategic companion (see below) aims to support those responsible for safeguarding Europe’s archaeological heritage by offering adaptable tools, thoughtful reflections, and practical examples to inform decision-making in a complex and ever-changing field.

This document forms one of several interlinked resources developed to provide European Archaeological Council (EAC) members with tools to help them manage their archaeological heritage. A short document ‘Assessing Archaeological Significance: Key Concepts’ has already been published ([EAC Guidelines 9](#), 2025). It provides a strategic overview of the issues explored in more depth here, providing a practical toolkit for heritage managers that highlights both the diversity and the common baselines found in European approaches to significance assessment.

Other EAC tools and resources can be found via the [EAC website](#), or on the [EAC community on Zenodo](#).

SECTION 3

The Concept of Significance in Heritage Management

3.1 De Significantia Disputatio

Bernhard Hebert, Claudia Volgger, Yael Alef¹

A European discussion on Significance in the Socratic tradition.

The so-to-say Socratic dialogue presented below is intended to illustrate some of the issues and philosophical uncertainties that arise whenever one thinks about ideas of significance. If there is anything philosophical in the following text, it might be the European method of asking questions in the Socratic tradition to examine the meaning of words we use in everyday speech.

Let us start.

PROLOGUS

Being archaeological heritage managers, we do not ask why we are managing heritage. By making laws, establishing authorities and granting resources, society commissioned us to manage heritage. Therefore, we perceive heritage management as a responsibility of states and of peoples, of experts and of public or private owners that has been accepted by society.

However, we have to ask how we are managing heritage. How do we make decisions within a legal framework, within legal frameworks differing from state to state? Although each concept that people try to apply to the visible and invisible world must stay fluid, there should be a certain consistency in dealing with certain qualities of heritage or monuments.

One of these central qualities of heritage or monuments is something called significance. Therefore, we will ask what significance means for everyday people and which significance we mean as heritage managers.

There will be a difference because to become heritage managers we had to learn, theoretically and practically, to understand the way significance has historically

and scientifically been ascribed to cultural relics. Our choices have to reflect that other heritage of how to build knowledge and recognize significance as well as our present cultural, legal and social realities.

ACTUS PRIMUS

Question 1: What does significance mean?

Significance is a noun derived from Latin *significare*, that is *signum facere*, to make a sign, to give a sign. In a very concrete sense. It could be said that *collegii membra inter se significaverunt*, if the members of our working group should agree with the definitions given by raising their hands or nodding their heads.

Significare is also used to announce something that will happen. *Non vobis futura significo*, I do not predict the future – of our guidance on significance.

Significare also expresses correspondence: *Consilium Latine significat* working group. “Consilium” means “working group” in Latin.

The Latin noun *significantia* was more frequently used in post-classical Latin. It stands for both vividness or clarity and importance. That combination of being both clear and also of relevance will make sure that an object to which you ascribe *significantia* will be highly rated. It might not be on top of the scale, but we may assume it will rate above the average. In a quite similar way, significant or Italian *significativo* will stress the relevance of a phenomenon: a significant deterioration, *deterioramente significativo*. Significance therefore does not tell us if a thing is good or bad, but marks a relevant peak or a certain level at a scale going up or down.

In European languages like English, French or Italian the Latin word is used most frequently to indicate importance, although the aspects of meaning and announcing are also conserved. German speakers have another word: *Bedeutung*, which may translate as importance or as meaning. *Er ist ein bedeutender Mann*.

¹Yael Alef, architectural conservator working in archaeological heritage management, and Bernhard Hebert, archaeologist by education and profession, were commissioned to write an introduction on the philosophy of ascribing significance in heritage management. Claudia Volgger, who has been working in archaeological heritage management for many years and has a deep interest in philosophy, finished their text.

He is an important man. *Das bedeutet gar nichts*. This does not matter at all. If you say: *Was ist die Bedeutung von Denkmalschutz?* you may understand: What does (the word) heritage protection mean? as well as What is the importance of heritage protection?

As always, translations are a very difficult case and we will not extend our arguing over the meaning of significance. We might agree that the word significant is commonly used to express a certain quality of things or events, which makes them exemplary for a group of things or a certain level of development, thus clarifying their essential points. Obviously whenever we assign significance to a thing or an event we do it before a background of other things or processes which will add perspective.

Significance therefore is no quality per se, of its own, but a quality of relation and reference. A quality to be discussed. Moreover, this discussion will include the questions: who will be willing to join it and who will determine the outcome. Anyway, we are all aware that there cannot be a definitive result: background, time, participants will change, and so will our results. *Hoc enim nobis significare audio*. This I dare to predict.

ACTUS SECUNDUS

Question 2: What kind of significance are we talking about?

Perhaps you will think: let us now finally concentrate on the significance of heritage or more specifically of archaeological heritage. Why not. But let us be aware that one object may be significant on a number of quite different scales trying to measure very different qualities. For example:

The untouched ruins of a medieval castle are significant as a suitable place – and frequently endangered habitat – of plants and animals.

The hidden ruins of a medieval castle are significant as a suitable place for adventurous children or a romantic refuge for lovers.

The accessible ruins of a medieval castle are significant as a suitable place for touristic use.

The reduced ruins of a medieval castle are significant as a suitable place for an architect planning a daring building project.

And so it goes on, even omitting multiple attempts of heritage managers to ascribe significance to those same ruins.

Let me repeat the question: What kind of significance are we talking about? Whose notion of significance do we have to consider?

ACTUS TERTIUS VEL PERIPETIA

Do we agree that significance is never absolute? Do we also realize that the perception of significance, in general and in particular, has changed over time and will continue changing? Let's think about that a little without wasting many words.

ACTUS QUARTUS

First statement, given by a heritage manager: The same object may have several kinds of significance all at once and several kinds of value if regarded as a heritage resource.

The question of what constitutes heritage, that is, what is significant is context dependent.

Significance and values are dynamic concepts that change over time and in different places and among different people with different perspectives. Valuation is by its very nature assessment and interpretation and thus subjective. To balance it a reflective and critical process needs to allow more voices to be heard.

Significance is a primary consideration in heritage management and informs decisions about what will be considered an archaeological heritage resource worthy of protection, conservation, and management and why. By summing up specific values and putting the result on a scale, significance gives a statement about why a site or a monument should be the subject of preservation and conservation and/or further management action.

Significance of archaeological heritage derives from a process based on archaeological science and experience in heritage management as well as on public discussion. A guidance for this process should grant structure, quality and transparency. At the end of it heritage authorities will decide which sites or monuments become objects of interest in the context of conservation and management.

ACTUS QUINTUS ET ULTIMUS

Second statement, given by an interested layperson: assessment of significance often seems to be an intuitive rather than a critical process.

Many academics and heritage managers used to ascribe significance within a black box. They would rather not explain how they define the specific values of an archaeological resource and how they decide where on the scale to put them, neither do they declare precisely why they do so. In recent times, courts have been prone to doubt the conclusiveness of such elitist knowledge. They demand: Let us see the process, let us see how careful, how honest and how farsighted the process is.

Perhaps responsibility for ascribing significance or value should shift at least partially away from state authorities to allow community participation.

Nobody understands what significance really means. Some heritage managers refer only to their own understanding of significance and ignore what other people might think. Significance of archaeological heritage is a versatile thing.

EPILOGUS

Significance assessment is relative, not absolute, depends on context, influx. Therefore, there is no “simple model” or formula for how to assess significance. Who dares to ascribe significance to a certain element of archaeological heritage? Heritage managers are obliged to do this one way or another.

The goal of significance assessment is to provide a sound foundation for decision-making in heritage management. It is a foundation, not the whole building. Decision-making will not end until you put the last tile on the roof.

This brings us back to the central theme of heritage: who is asking the question?

3.2 Commentary notes on the Philosophical Introduction

Yael Alef

This Socratic dialogue reflects the ambiguous nature of the philosophical discussion about significance in the context of archaeological heritage management (AHM), i.e., why and what do we preserve? Significance in AHM refers both to the meaning of the resource that is related to its context, and to its importance in comparison to other resources.

The ambiguous nature of significance: Significance of archaeological heritage in the context of AHM is a dynamic concept that is based on new research, assessments and interpretations. Thus, it is not a given but the outcome of societal processes. What we value may change in time and in place, so it cannot be absolute. In the last decades, the perceived value and significance of archaeological heritage has shifted from traditional historic, artistic, aesthetic, scientific heritage value judgement, to embrace broader societal values.

Perception of significance may vary among different people, so it is always subjective and understood in relation to the context, knowledge and cultural (in its broadest sense) frameworks of the people who ascribe it. Furthermore, archaeological heritage is related to very long processes in place and time. Hence its significance depends on the multiple contexts from which it is perceived and used; it may therefore embody different and even conflicting values.

Significance in AHM and its assessment therefore, cannot be a technical procedure linked to a definitive formulation or model calculation to grade different archaeological sites, rather it is a critical approach that is context-dependent and part of an ongoing reflective process of negotiating values in society and education.

WHY do we preserve the archaeological heritage?

The significance of archaeological heritage is related to the philosophical question: why do we preserve? The value of archaeological heritage is the subject of a long theoretical and practical discourse (Avrami et al, 2019; Lipe, 1974; Mason and Avrami, 2002; Sullivan and Mackay, 2012). Today it is widely accepted that all cultural heritage including archaeological heritage benefits society. Archaeological heritage can assist in society's understanding of the past and can strengthen the sense of continuity, connection, and the identity of people with places. It is "an important reminder of where we come from, who we are, and who we want

to be..." (Mason and Avrami, 2002 p.13). [The Charter for the Protection and Management of the Archaeological Heritage](#) recognizes that "understanding of the origins and development of human societies is of fundamental importance to humanity in identifying its cultural and social roots." (ICAHM, 1990). And the [Valletta Convention](#) recalls "that the archaeological heritage is essential to a knowledge of the history of mankind... as a source of the European collective memory and as an instrument for historical and scientific study" (CoE, 1992). These are the answers to the question why do we preserve? to the rationale for AHM and the motivation of heritage professionals.

The purpose of significance assessment: It is accepted that "managing heritage is about managing values" (Clark, 2014 p.70). It implies that the purpose of significance assessment is to inform decision-making in AHM practice about what will be considered an archaeological heritage resource worthy of protection, and address why and how we conserve and manage it (Avrami and Mason, 2019). The assessment of significance describes the meanings of a place and a statement about why a place is socio-culturally important, while identifying the need for protection and support further conservation action where necessary. Despite its ambiguous nature, significance assessment is a critical element in the activities of AHM. It includes the identification of archaeological heritage resources for listing and protection under national legal systems and provides for their integration into value-based planning and participatory processes.

The question is, what do we preserve? Which archaeological resources should be chosen to become objects of conservation interest and how do we ascribe significance to them? How do we assess the level of significance and its relative importance in comparison to other resources? Although listing criteria have been developed in several countries, they are not easy to implement and assessment of significance remains a largely expert-driven, state evaluation process (Mathers et al, 2005a). There is no universal and accepted definition of criteria for assessing archaeological heritage significance. Therefore, assessing significance is still one of the most difficult professional chores facing the heritage manager or archaeologist (ibid.).

Changing approaches to significance assessment:

In the last decades there has been shift in AHM responsibilities in state heritage and land-use planning authorities to facilitate the involvement of community participation. It is changing the approach to significance assessment. Firstly, it raises the question of who is responsible for ascribing significance and value? Secondly, it forces a broadening of professional archaeological perspectives to accommodate and balance different values and to reflect other views of heritage. The change in approach has emphasized the importance of inclusion and taking a holistic approach to the assessment of significance that includes public participation as well as academic assessment. It is a process of mediation of interests and values that requires an open and plural approach. In that way, the assessment process can be used to inform rather than justify professional judgement, providing balanced and transparent decisions that involve all the stakeholders and actors.

SECTION 4

Historical Background

4.1 Historical Summary

Adrian Olivier

In most countries the social values of heritage have always existed alongside the more instrumental values of identification, regulation, and protection. Likewise, social objectives have been explicit features of international instruments (conventions, recommendations, declarations) since 1931. However, these have been difficult to operationalize in practice, and attention has generally focussed on the more technical aspects of heritage management. Only in recent years have serious and realistic steps been taken to translate these aspirations into a meaningful reality, and this has seen a significant shift from regulation to participation, and from exclusion to inclusion. Recognizing and understanding the full range of values that comprise all the different aspects of significance lies at the very heart of this process.

Widespread interest in heritage protection throughout Europe developed in the 19th century, at a time of increasing scientific curiosity and enlightenment. At this time thinking about heritage and conservation often included an aesthetic appreciation of buildings, monuments, and landscapes and their associated intangible values (Jones and Leech, 2015 p.8). In Britain this approach was exemplified by campaigning conservation organisations². However, nascent national heritage laws in Britain³ and elsewhere were invariably directed at protecting selected elements of the cultural heritage and the main focus of these legal and regulatory measures was on those intrinsic and material values of the physical remains of the past that could be readily identified, classified, assessed, and selected. During the late 19th and 20th centuries approaches to heritage protection, preservation, and conservation gradually diverged: on the one hand the broader and more socially inclusive objectives of campaigning organisations often fixed on a sense of place and other intangible values; in contrast, the

development of legal and administrative mechanisms to identify, inventorise, regulate, and protect historic buildings and monuments relied on understanding a range of more intrinsic and material values.

In an international context, the [Athens Charter for the Restoration of Ancient Monuments](#) (ICOMOS, 1931) was an early attempt to define agreed approaches and standards to the restoration and preservation of historic monuments. It recognised the importance of understanding and maintaining the non-intrinsic values inherent in a monument (aesthetics, character, and context) and also tried to reconcile potential tensions between state and private/community responsibilities in monument restoration. The general approach of the charter, however, encouraged an emphasis on the predominant role of intrinsic and 'scientific' values.

After World War Two, the creation of UNESCO in 1945 signalled a collective desire for international collaboration as a means of underpinning universal respect for justice, the rule of law, and for human rights and fundamental freedoms as a means of avoiding further conflict (Hall, 2011a). Culture (and heritage) was seen as a way to realise universal principles to cement and safeguard greater international unity. This humanist approach was emphasised in 1949 by the founding principles of the Council of Europe which identified the need to safeguard and ensure access to a common (European) cultural heritage (Pickard, 2002 p.11).

Since then, there has been a proliferation of international instruments (conventions, charters, recommendations, declarations) the provisions of which have been translated to a greater or lesser extent into national legislations. Generally, these all incorporate (in principle) the concept of a common (universal) heritage and, alongside the need for heritage protection and regulation, a consideration of the social values of heritage. Characteristically each instrument articulates the value of heritage as a common good to be safeguarded on behalf of society at large from

²E.g. The Commons Preservation Society (1865); William Morris' Society for the Protection of Ancient Buildings (1877); and the National Trust (1896)

³The Ancient Monuments Protection Act (1882) and the Ancient Monuments Act (1900)

destruction and/or dispersal. Each sets out – in their different spheres – the actions needed to safeguard those elements of heritage that are identified and selected as having particular significance.

Despite the high level philosophical and social aspirations, implementation of most international heritage instruments during the second half of the 20th century was generally directed at the practical measures necessary to identify, protect, regulate, and manage heritage. Professional attention was invariably focussed on technical, scientific, legal, and administrative aspects of heritage related to specific elements (e.g. archaeology, architecture, landscape) and/or specific policy areas (e.g. spatial planning, regional development etc.). This is exemplified by the [Venice Charter](#) (ICOMOS, 1964) which provided an international framework for the conservation and restoration of buildings. This stressed, in particular, the primacy of the material and historic values embodied in the fabric of buildings and monuments and set out the agreed technical parameters for their restoration and reconstruction (Pace, 2012). In 1969, stimulated by economic growth and the development of towns and cities during the post-war period the [London Convention](#) (CoE, 1969) similarly placed particular emphasis on the importance of material culture recorded as a result of archaeological work.

The [Convention for the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage](#) (UNESCO, 1972) deployed the concept of ‘outstanding universal value’ (OUV) as a means of identifying and selecting the most significant natural and cultural heritage sites at a global level. Although OUV is based largely on very explicit tangible material values related mainly to integrity and authenticity, the Convention does actively encourage democratisation of cultural heritage at a global level and, as heritage management practice evolves, social (and political) values are being increasingly incorporated in its implementation (Labadi, 2010).

In 1979 the Australia ICOMOS Burra Charter (further developed and [revised in 2013](#)) adopted a much more directly values-led approach to conservation and heritage management (ICOMOS, 1979). This arose from the need to adapt European cultural heritage instruments to a country where the understanding of significance – and therefore heritage management practice – often used different perspectives and assumptions to those current in Europe (Clark, 2005). The original Burra Charter focussed on ‘place’ rather

than individual buildings and sites. It put cultural significance at the heart of decision-making and set out the practical steps necessary to use significance to underpin policy and management frameworks. Later revisions have broadened the definition of significance to include social values and multiple values, and the key principles and approaches of the Burra Charter have now gained widespread currency, and indeed have been adopted and incorporated into many subsequent cultural heritage conventions and instruments worldwide.

Three of the Council of Europe family of heritage conventions / charters – [The European Charter of the Architectural Heritage](#) (CoE, 1975), [The Granada Convention](#) (CoE, 1985), and [The Valletta Convention](#) (CoE, 1992) all reflected this approach. Each echoed Article 5 of the Venice Charter (ICOMOS, 1964) by contextualizing their objectives in the context of economic and social life; each identified some associated social values and each promoted the development of public awareness. The Valletta Convention in particular highlighted the need to promote public access to the past as a fundamental human right, but one that ‘can only be met by specialists – archaeologists – who can interpret the data and assist the public in gaining access to its heritage’ (CoE, 1992 explanatory notes) which unfortunately consigned public (and community) interest and engagement to an entirely passive activity subject to expert/specialist mediation. Despite some acknowledgement of social values, the focus of all three conventions remained firmly grounded in an appreciation of ‘historic’ and ‘evidential’ values and each adopted a fundamentally criteria-led, rather than a values-led approach in developing standards for heritage management. It is also true of course that each convention very naturally reflected the ‘scientific’ and ‘technical’ issues that were matters of professional concern at the time of drafting.

The success of these conventions lies in the strong framework they created for the curation of heritage and the development of robust approaches to mitigate, document, protect, and preserve threatened archaeological sites and historical monuments (Pace, 2012). Today, most states have developed – to a greater or lesser extent – a functioning legal system grounded on the provisions of these conventions for the protection, conservation, and management of the cultural heritage- albeit one that measures significance in terms of intrinsic values.

Since 1992, heritage management practice has continued to evolve, building on the Burra Charter to create a more flexible, inclusive, dynamic, and integrative approach which addresses the whole of the historic environment (archaeology, buildings, and landscapes) as a single entity (Clark, 2001). The associated conservation management plan process recognizes the role of local stakeholders in defining significance, and (in theory) incorporates the need to engage stakeholders in management decisions (Clark, 2005). These changes are reflected in a number of documents: the [Nara Document on Authenticity](#) (ICOMOS, 1994) sets out the principle that the authenticity of a site is rooted in specific social-cultural contexts and values and that these can be drawn from a variety of information sources including, in addition to intrinsic historical and architectural sources, a whole range of other values (e.g. local traditions, location, setting, spirit, and feeling). Authenticity is therefore regarded as relative, not absolute; its criteria change from one culture to another, so that conservation practice also needs to change to reflect the cultural values of different societies. In 1996 The Helsinki Declaration (CoE, 2002) marked a significant shift away from a conservation-oriented scientific and technological approach to one that explored ways in which culture and heritage could support social progress and the fundamental values of European unification (Thérond, 2009). The declaration's cross-disciplinary approach reinforced cultural diversity by asserting every person's right of access to the cultural heritage of his or her choice (while respecting the rights and freedoms of others), and promoted the concept of a common European heritage.

The Council of Europe's [Declaration on Cultural Diversity](#) (CoE, 2000) stimulated consideration of the relationship between citizenship, cultural identity, human rights, and core values (Stradling and Rowe, 2009). In particular, how intercultural dialogue could support the heritage 'values' inherent in the founding principles of the Council of Europe and help to reconcile potential tensions between 'private' interests in heritage and the need to protect and provide access to heritage and culture to everyone. This led to an interest in how heritage could support social cohesion by developing ways to share responsibility for heritage between all the different elements of civil society including those with little or no interest in traditional and technical aspects of heritage (Weber, 2001). The Council of Europe actively began to promote not just

the principles of integrated heritage conservation and management, but the social and cultural aspects of heritage (Pickard, 2002). These approaches are reflected to some extent in the [Florence Convention](#) (CoE, 2000) but are more particularly embodied in the [Faro Convention](#) (CoE, 2005).

The Florence Convention marks a significant shift from regulation to participation and emphasises the concept that landscape management requires collaboration between individuals and organisations, and that official landscape activities (including policy development and decision-making) should include the participation of civil society (Article 5). A key aspiration is to help people identify with the areas and towns where they live and work by giving them a more active role in decision-making. The Convention also attempts to address how (landscape) heritage can help underpin social identity. The Faro Convention reiterates the social ambitions of earlier instruments and in a wider cultural context extends the aspirations of the Florence Convention by putting people and human values at the centre of an enlarged and cross-disciplinary concept of cultural heritage (Article 1b). It presents heritage as a resource for human development, the enhancement of cultural diversity, and the promotion of intercultural dialogue. The principle of access to cultural heritage as a fundamental human right then provides a link between heritage practice and social cohesion (as a form of public benefit). This has far reaching implications for heritage management in the wider global context of human rights and democracy. The Faro Convention also specifically supports public participation in cultural heritage activities and decision-making (Article 5) and provides for the development of legal, financial, and professional frameworks for joint actions by public authorities, experts, owners, investors, businesses, non-governmental organisations and civil society and for voluntary initiatives which complement the role of public authorities (Article 12).

The Florence and Faro Conventions include a much more inclusive, self-defining concept of cultural heritage that embraces a perception of values in a social context (e. g. contribution to quality of life). This wider approach recasts heritage to incorporate the 'human rights' dimension into the Council of Europe's heritage work and is very much a product of 21st-century sensitivities. It shifts practice away from traditional concerns of designation and protection centred on the intrinsic and scientific-led values of

the Granada and Valletta conventions but at the same time potentially creates new tensions when the values of different heritage communities do not coincide (Stanley, 2006 p.32). Such a people-oriented approach is difficult to instrumentalise through international frameworks or to operationalise through national legislation and will require flexible, open approaches based on deep and respectful understanding of different social and cultural values (Stradling and Rowe, 2009).

In recent years, the [Namur Declaration](#) (CoE, 2015), emphasised the different social values of the cultural heritage and its contribution to quality of life and prosperity and promoted public participation in heritage governance. This was reinforced by the [European Cultural Heritage Strategy for the 21st Century](#) (CoE, 2018) which included social aspects of cultural heritage as one of its three themes and repositioned cultural heritage policies at the heart of an integrated approach that focuses on the conservation, protection, and promotion of heritage as a shared responsibility 'by society as a whole' – an attempt to bridge the gap between the often unfulfilled societal objectives of earlier international instruments and day-to-day practice.

The [European Framework for Action on Cultural Heritage](#) (European Commission, 2019) complements the [European Union Work Plan for Culture 2019–2022](#) (European Union, 2018) and both initiatives include important strands related to the contribution of culture and heritage to social cohesion, intercultural dialogue, dialogue with stakeholders, and the need to mobilise stakeholders from civil society to engage with cultural heritage. This focus on social values is also exemplified by the [Berlin Call to Action](#) (Europa Nostra, 2018) which underscores the need for the full involvement and engagement of all relevant public and private stakeholders, including civil society, in the development of cultural agenda and policies.

Despite the early recognition of the importance of the non-intrinsic social values of cultural heritage in the late 19th century, and despite repeatedly acknowledging the social function of cultural heritage, for much of the 20th century heritage instruments and regulations for protection generally focussed on selection procedures that are reliant on intrinsic and material, evidential, historic, and scientific values. From the late 20th century onwards, the evolution of international heritage instruments displays a significant

shift from regulation to participation, moving away from preservation and mitigation as the primary driver to a more proactive approach based on a better articulation of a wider range of the different values at play to inform decision-making. However, many of the top-down approaches embodied in international instruments and other heritage management frameworks of the second half of the 20th century, are still current today, but no longer reflect the heritage management needs of a modern multi-cultural Europe (Olivier, 2016). There is a growing acceptance that in addition to reliance on traditional scientific and evidential heritage values derived from specialist and expert knowledge, heritage management now requires a much greater focus on, and understanding of broader and more inclusive concepts of social and public value, and an appreciation of how those different values may also be vulnerable to harm and loss in different ways.

At the same time there is a growing (but by no means universal) acceptance that not all elements of heritage have the same value and significance (even in strictly academic terms); that not everything can (or should) be protected or conserved (there's simply too much); and that not everything can (or should) be recorded/ excavated (there are insufficient resources). The need for selection to underscore heritage management processes and decision-making remains as vital and relevant today as it was at the end of the 19th century but today we must deploy a wider and more socially inclusive range of values to inform that selection. In this way the heritage that we manage and conserve will better articulate the dynamic relationship between desired professional heritage outcomes and public expectations expressed by the social and cultural values of different communities (Lowenthal, 2000; Clark and Drury, 2001).

Despite the articulation of the importance of social and societal values of heritage in recent instruments and policy documents (e.g. modern principles of conservation: Drury and McPherson, 2008; ICOMOS, 2013; Avrami et al, 2019), existing protection systems still often ignore the non-intrinsic, societal, and personal values that people assign to the heritage and there is evidence that public awareness and (meaningful) interest in protecting the heritage remains consistently at a fairly low level (Schadla-Hall, 1999; McDonald, 2011). There is a clear discrepancy between the high-level principles expressed in international instruments and their practical application in real-world situations. To comprehend the wider

implications of significance heritage managers need to move away from technical aspects of heritage management and conservation and draw out 'local skills, knowledge, and experience of place rather than dictating what is of cultural significance' (Lammy, 2006). Heritage managers must integrate into their work a direct, meaningful, two-way engagement between heritage professionals and public communities at all levels so that public value and public benefit are firmly grounded in a realistic understanding of public attitudes and needs (Lowenthal, 2000).

The challenge today is to explore how heritage management can be combined with effective community and public engagement, in a new matrix that will deliver increased public benefit at the same time as supporting integrated value-led conservation. A more rounded understanding of all aspects of significance will lie at the heart of this process.

4.2 The Concept of Outstanding Universal Value in World Heritage

Margaret Gowen

Introduction

Outstanding Universal Value (OUV) in UNESCO World Heritage is the theoretical and conceptual standard that is used to determine the global heritage significance of the properties that are inscribed on the World Heritage List. The UNESCO [Convention Concerning the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage](#) is a global treaty instrument that was devised around the notion “that parts of the cultural or natural heritage are of outstanding interest and therefore need to be preserved as part of the world heritage of mankind as a whole” (UNESCO 1972a, p.1). This can be understood to mean that Outstanding Universal Value (OUV) is internationally recognised as a transcendent standard, that can be inclusive of all other heritage values globally. The Convention text does not define OUV, that task was left to the World Heritage Committee as the elected representative body of the Convention’s States Parties. However, the Convention does state that the definition of OUV will be determined by criteria (ibid. Article 11, 5)⁴. The current definition of OUV is described in the convention’s [Operational Guidelines](#) as follows:

“Outstanding universal value means cultural and/or natural significance which is so exceptional as to transcend national boundaries and to be of common importance for present and future generations of all humanity. As such, the permanent protection of this heritage is of the highest importance to the international community as a whole. The Committee defines the criteria for the inscription of properties on the World Heritage List.” (UNESCO 2025, Op. G., Para 49).

The World Heritage Convention was a mould-breaking heritage management instrument that brought the designation, of natural and cultural heritage for the purposes of protection and conservation, into the legal realm of inter-governmental/ supra-governmental global governance (Lixinski 2013, 137). In the hierarchy of heritage management systems, World Heritage is an international and transnational system of heritage designation, accreditation, monitoring, and management that is related to the international recognition of the need to protect the exceptional and universal heritage value of the properties that have been inscribed on the World Heritage List. In adopting and ratifying the Convention, States Parties recognise “that the duty of ensuring the identification, protection, conservation, presentation, and transmission to future generations of the cultural and natural heritage ... situated on its territory, belongs primarily to that State...”, albeit providing scope of international assistance in that task (UNESCO 1972a, Article 4). It is understood therefore (Article 5), that by ratifying the Convention each State Party undertakes to endeavour to take “effective and active measures” nationally for the protection, conservation and management required⁵.

The historical context

The World Heritage Convention is very much a heritage document of its time and historical context. It was the first international legal instrument that sought to raise awareness of iconic heritage places globally and to define a globally applicable standard of value for them. It was created to raise awareness and to engage international cooperation. The Preamble to the Convention notes that the cultural and natural heritage “are increasingly threatened with destruction not only by the traditional causes of decay, but also by changing social and economic conditions which

⁴ Article 11.5 The Committee shall define the criteria on the basis of which a property belonging to the cultural or natural heritage may be included...

⁵ Art. 5 (a) to adopt a general policy which aims to give the cultural and natural heritage a function in the life of the community and to integrate the protection of that heritage into comprehensive planning programmes; (b) to set up within its territories... services for the protection, conservation and presentation of the cultural and natural heritage ... (c) to develop scientific and technical studies, and research...(to help counteract) the dangers that threaten its cultural or natural heritage; (d) to take the appropriate legal, scientific, technical, administrative and financial measures necessary for the identification, protection, conservation, presentation and rehabilitation of this heritage; and (e) to foster the establishment or development of national or regional centres for training in the protection, conservation and presentation of the cultural and natural heritage and to encourage scientific research in this field.

aggravate the situation with even more formidable phenomena of damage or destruction". It also expresses a sense of urgency, driven by fear of loss, "that deterioration or disappearance of any item of the cultural or natural heritage constitutes a harmful impoverishment of the heritage of all the nations of the world" (UNESCO 1972a, p.1). By creating a World Heritage List, the Convention sought to attract international collaboration and support (political and financial) for the preservation and conservation of the selected 'outstanding' sites on the List, especially in situations where these were threatened and/or nation states had insufficient resources to protect them. The mission of UNESCO World Heritage had its foundations and genesis in the international efforts of nations to recover from the destruction of World War Two. Its ideological foundations stemmed from the League of Nations (1920-1946) and the International Committee on Intellectual Cooperation (1922-1939) and the international politico-cultural and diplomatic traditions of the global North that led to the establishment of the United Nations (Titchen, 1995, p.3; Meskell, 2018, p.1-27).

UNESCO was established just one month after the United Nations in November 1945 with a mandate to promote education, science and culture. Both organisations were focused on building intergovernmental political collaboration and cultural understanding as a key to lasting peace, based "upon the intellectual and moral solidarity of mankind" (UNESCO 1945, Preamble). This mission to maintain, increase and diffuse knowledge was to be achieved by "assuring the conservation and protection of the world's inheritance of books, works of art and monuments of history and science and recommending to the nations concerned the necessary conventions" (UNESCO 1945, Art 1, 2c). UNESCO's mission led to the first meetings that started to conceive "a system for the protection of heritage sites of exceptional value" in the 1950s and 60s (Titchen, 1995, p.36-74; Labadi, 2015, p.2607; Meskell, 2018, p.19-24)⁶. This was a period when international cooperation under the mandate of UNESCO raised very significant funds for several international cultural heritage safeguarding missions, notably the first huge project to dismantle and reconstruct the temples of Abu Simbel and Philae above the floodwater level of the River Nile following the construction of the Aswan Dam (Meskell, *ibid*).

Labadi (*ibid.*) notes that the term "outstanding universal value" was only crafted at the end of the convention's lengthy drafting process having been preceded by the terms "world-wide importance" and "universal interest". Promoting the principle of the universality of heritage value generally and fostering intercultural dialogue and especially co-operative endeavour, the Convention sought to further UNESCO's mission of promoting peace through international collaborative programmes. In the year of adoption of the World Heritage Convention, the General Conference of UNESCO also adopted an important, if lesser-known, complementary [Recommendation Concerning the Protection, at National Level, of the Cultural and Natural Heritage](#) (UNESCO 1972b), that was aimed at ensuring the broader, individual state-based application of the principle of protection of heritage. The recommendation supported the view that the protection of "more modest items that have, with the passage of time, acquired cultural or natural value" should be considered equally important (UNESCO 2007, p.32). Cultural heritage was, and still is, regarded by UNESCO as a legacy in an intergenerational cultural rights frame of reference, that "in its broadest sense, (is) both a product and a process, which provides societies with a wealth of resources that are inherited from the past, created in the present and bestowed for the benefit of future generations" (UNESCO n.d.,a). In World Heritage, this legacy is seen as globally and universally relevant, and a responsibility for all humankind.

Much has been written about the history of the Convention, the recognition of its Euro-American intellectual and conceptual foundations, and the Eurocentric traditions of conservation philosophy and practice that influenced its creation and its early years (e.g. Titchen, 1995; Jokilehto, 1999; Cameron and Rössler, 2013; Labadi, 2013; Meskell, 2018). Archaeology played a particular role in the early development of UNESCO's early international collaborative focus on saving cultural heritage sites (Abu Simbel, Egypt; Moenjodaro, Pakistan; Venice, Italy; and Borobudur, Indonesia) as did a number of key people notably Julian Huxley (Meskell, 2018, p.1-27). Meskell makes an interesting observation that archaeological safeguarding missions, as multidisciplinary, internationally funded scientific endeavours were later "bypassed" by UNESCO in favour

⁶The Hague Convention (UNESCO 1954) was the first comprehensive multilateral UNESCO treaty dedicated exclusively to the protection of cultural property, albeit focused on such protection in the event of armed conflict. Two previous Hague Conventions on the Laws and Customs of War, 1899 & 1907 also included clauses related to the treatment of cultural property.

of the creation of the World Heritage List and a focus on the protection of monumental heritage. That focus on monuments (including natural parks also referred to as 'monuments' in American heritage management) necessarily broadened over time as the number of states parties grew and the Convention became a recognised brand and standard-bearer for heritage places. Inscription brought a much sought-after degree of national prestige and, in many cases, significant tourism income. The Convention is the most highly ratified of all the United Nations intergovernmental conventions with 196 [States Parties](#). As such, it is regarded as UNESCO's flagship international treaty instrument. As of January 2026, there are [1,248 properties in 170 countries](#)⁷ on the World Heritage List, 972 of which are cultural, 235 natural and 41 mixed cultural and natural.

In common with other international treaty instruments, the Convention is governed by the General Assembly of its States Parties and, as such, it is a sovereign body. The General Assembly elects the 21-member World Heritage Committee, and the Committee in consultation with its States Parties takes all the decisions in relation to the implementation of the Convention on their behalf, including inscription, monitoring, management, funding, policy development and thematic studies. This includes decisions on the inscription of World Heritage properties on the List of World Heritage in Danger and in extreme cases where OUV is deemed to be lost, decisions to delete properties from the List. The work of the Committee in the administration of the Convention is assisted by its Advisory Bodies (ICCRUM, IUCN, ICOMOS), the World Heritage Centre (since 1992) and its own elected bureau. States Parties are individually assigned with the responsibility for the identification and nomination of candidate sites. If successful, they have responsibility for the protection, monitoring and management of the OUV of their inscribed World Heritage properties in accordance with the Operational Guidelines, with an undertaking that they will also do this for heritage generally within their territory (UNESCO 1972a, Art. 3, 4 and 5)⁸. The Convention has therefore fostered the notion that the identification of heritage is a state-based responsibility, allowing that the identification

and preservation of places of outstanding universal value may require assistance with training, capacity-building, and funding contribution from its States Parties. The Advisory Bodies (albeit with European-American scientific and cultural roots) have assisted the Committee and the growing number of States Parties to the Convention to fulfil this mandate and, in so doing, have sought to encourage and cater for greater cultural diversity and representative balance on the World Heritage List.

Outstanding Universal Value as a standard

The attribution of OUV is central to the system used to select sites for inscription on the World Heritage List, and it is the key consideration used in the decision-making of the three main stakeholders involved in the identification of World Heritage: i) the States Parties who make nominations to the List, ii) the Advisory Bodies who undertake the evaluation of nominations and assist in the monitoring of the State of Conservation of the properties inscribed on the List; and iii) the World Heritage Committee which takes decisions on all aspects of the implementation of the Convention⁹. OUV is regarded as an essentialist, recognisable and timeless truth that is closely linked to the notion of inherent value (Aoki, 2021, p.308). OUV, however, has proved to be a vague and ambiguous concept that has been a challenge to operationalise from inception. It remains so even after 50 years of theoretical examination, technical development and operational adjustment. In seeking to provide opportunities for its increasing number and diversity of States Parties, these developments have sought to cater for and reflect more plural understandings of OUV that reflect the multiplicity of heritage values globally. The development can be seen in the growth of the knowledge base within the World Heritage system. It can also be seen in a notable move away from the original notion of the List as an elite list of places (reflecting Euro-American thinking in the 1970s). Nonetheless, because of its ambiguity, the use of OUV as a standard continues to present challenges for adjudication. In the past 20+ years, the popularity of the List has made way for increasing political dynamics

⁷The number of World Heritage properties in each country varies widely.

⁸Nomination to the WH list is a two-stage process, the first being the identification of candidate properties by the States Parties on their World Heritage Tentative Lists which are submitted to the WH Centre and reviewed every 10 years. <https://whc.unesco.org/en/tentativelists/>

⁹Once inscribed, a nominated site is described as a World Heritage property.

at World Heritage Committee meetings (also the annual General Assembly of the Convention's States Parties). Political lobbying and pacting has affected the conduct of the meetings and the decision-making of the Committee (e.g. Meskell, 2015). The impact of increasing politicisation has raised questions about the credibility of World Heritage processes, in particular the probity of the Committee's procedures and decision-making (Cameron and Rössler, 2016, p.236–238; Brumann, 2021).

The Convention's Operational Guidelines, resource manuals, and a significant body of thematically developed literature (UNESCO, n.d.,b; Fulton et al, 2020) have all sought to make the task of nomination and identification and justification of OUV easier for States Parties, and the assessment of OUV and justification of OUV more transparent for the evaluation panels of the Advisory Bodies and the members of the Committee. This literature is supplemented by publications prepared by each of the Committee's three formal Advisory Bodies, ICOMOS, IUCN and ICCROM (below). The Operational Guidelines (UNESCO 2025) set out the principles, rules, procedures and regulations for the administration of World Heritage. By seeking to provide appropriate technical guidance and procedural clarity to the operationalisation of OUV, the Guidelines have always been regarded as necessarily dynamic with the capacity to adapt to development in thinking and procedure. As a result, they have grown significantly in length and detail, from 28 paragraphs (13 pages) in 1977 to 290 paragraphs (188 pages) in 2021, remaining approximately the same length since then. This mirrors the increasingly technocratic and bureaucratic environment within which World Heritage operates. The development reflects the challenge of developing a transparent, standardised and relevant set of criteria for the diversity of internationally exceptional cultural and natural sites of universal value, and providing clear guidance and conditions that can be applied to the nomination, evaluation, inscription and subsequent protection and management of the OUV of all inscribed World Heritage properties.

Defining Outstanding Universal Value – historical beginnings

In 1972, the notion of OUV reflected the primary ambition of the Convention to create "a selective list of the world's most outstanding examples of heritage" of universal importance to humanity as a

whole (Jokilehto 2020, p. 16). From inception, it was not immediately clear how the OUV of this elite list should be defined and verified as a global standard of significance (Schmutz and Elliot, 2017) or what criteria would be necessary to achieve that purpose. That task was assigned, by the Convention to the World Heritage Committee who, in turn, sought the input of their [Advisory Bodies](#). Criteria were developed for cultural heritage by ICOMOS with significant input from ICCROM and were devised separately for natural heritage by IUCN. They were published as part of the second draft set of Operational Guidelines adopted in 1977 by the World Heritage Committee (UNESCO 1977b).

Prior to publication, at a meeting organised by UNESCO in Morges in 1976, the three advisory bodies cautioned that that it was "not possible that to draw up a set of objective criteria" but they nonetheless came to the meeting with pre-prepared draft criteria that were formulated along very similar lines. Of note, it was felt that it would be "necessary to rely on the judgement of informed specialists who could assist the World Heritage Committee in the evaluation of properties" (Parent 1976, II, Para 4). In an attempt to articulate what OUV meant, the meeting settled on the idea that "universal" should represent or symbolise a set of ideas or values which are universally recognized as important, or as having influenced the evolution of mankind as a whole at one time or another" (ibid. II, Para 6). From the outset it was suggested that the criteria used to justify OUV for both cultural and natural properties should be supported by a requirement to demonstrate integrity/unity. For this 1976 meeting, both ICOMOS and IUCN created separate draft criteria: ICOMOS for cultural heritage and IUCN for natural heritage. The evaluation of nominations, and the selection of criteria used to justify their OUV, remains the responsibility of these two organisations who frequently advise changes to the criteria selected by nominating States Parties. ICCROM's contribution to that meeting (attached as an annex to the report, see Jokilehto et al, 2008, p.57) offered definitions of outstanding universal value for cultural properties in line with Article 1 of the Convention, including "artistic value, historic value and typological value" making the statement that OUV "cannot be justified except when referred to specialized scientific literature on the subject, which is considered the most up-to-date expression of the universal consciousness on the issue". The ICOMOS text prepared for the meeting was more

detailed, justifying its choice of criteria and explaining them (ibid, 60). The adjectives used were “unique artistic achievement”, “outstanding importance”, “most significant examples”, “exceptional”, “unique or extremely rare”, “of great antiquity”, “the best”... (UNESCO 1976, Annex IV 2; Jokilehto et al, 2008, Annex 1c).

Defining cultural World Heritage from 1977

For the purposes of selection to the World Heritage List, the Convention (Article 1) defines cultural heritage as:

“monuments: architectural works, works of monumental sculpture and painting, elements or structures of an archaeological nature, inscriptions, cave dwellings and combinations of features, which are of outstanding universal value from the point of view of history, art or science;

groups of buildings (ensembles): groups of separate or connected buildings which, because of their architecture, their homogeneity or their place in the landscape, are of outstanding universal value from the point of view of history, art or science;

sites: works of man or the combined works of nature and man, and areas including archaeological sites which are of outstanding universal value from the historical, aesthetic, ethnological or anthropological point of view.”

The connection with the ICOMOS Venice Charter’s broad concept of what constitutes a ‘monument’ (1964) is evident in this text (Petzet, 2008, p.7-8). In addition, to qualify for the World Heritage List, monuments, groups of buildings and sites/places have to be demonstrably outstanding or exceptional (outstanding is translated as “exceptionnelle” in French and similarly in Spanish, Portuguese, and Italian). OUV therefore embodies the notion of exceptionality and also perhaps the ability to inspire wonder. At the inception of the Convention the notion of OUV was such that it should reflect the globally superlative in culture and nature. It is also important to add that the Convention’s mission was underpinned by the principle that international cooperation was needed to protect and conserve the exceptional properties of universal value on its list.

The first draft text of Operational Guidelines (UNESCO 1977a) did not include the criteria which were still being worked on by the Advisory Bodies at the time; the text was quickly superseded by a more developed document later that year (UNESCO 1977b), see Fig.2. Of note however, the text includes in para 14 (v) a statement that justification for inclusion in the World Heritage List for cultural property should include: “Unique artistic or aesthetic achievement; Outstanding importance in terms of influence on subsequent developments; Rarity; Significant example of a type of structure; Vulnerability of traditional forms; (and) Exceptional historic significance”.

Figure 1: Scelig Mhichíl, Ireland, inscribed on the World Heritage List in 1996. <https://whc.unesco.org/en/list/757/>

© Photographic Archive, National Monuments Service, Government of Ireland.

This first draft text also includes a note (Para 7) stating that the definition of “universal” in the phrase Outstanding Universal Value required comment, explaining that “Some properties may not be recognized by all people, everywhere, to be of great importance and significance. Opinions may vary from one culture or period to another and the term “universal” must therefore be interpreted as referring to a property which is highly representative of the culture of which it forms part”. It added that OUV ... “should be interpreted as an outstanding response to issues of a universal nature common to, or addressed by, all human cultures. Re. natural heritage - bio-geographical diversity; Re. culture - human creativity and resulting cultural diversity.” It also noted (ibid., Para 22) that “Properties included in the World Heritage List shall be considered as being of equal value. For this reason, the criteria proposed above make no reference to the relative value of properties”.

In this earliest draft text there was no mention of the additional conditions of Authenticity and Integrity discussed at the Morges 1976 meeting, but the revised text of the guidelines (UNESCO 1977b) added the following paragraphs in relation to cultural properties:

“8. In every case, consideration must be given to the state of preservation of the property (which should be evaluated relatively, in comparison to the state of preservation of other property dating from the same period and of the same type and category).

9. In addition, the property should meet the test of authenticity in design, materials, workmanship and setting; authenticity does not limit consideration to original form and structure but includes all subsequent modifications and additions over the course of time, which in themselves possess artistic or historical values”.

Of note the need to demonstrate integrity was not included for cultural properties. This was reintroduced much later in 1997. In 1978, this definition included a sentence that mirrored the theory expounded in the Venice Charter that “authenticity does not limit consideration to original form and structure but includes all subsequent modifications and additions... which in themselves possess artistic or historical values”. The qualification was quickly removed, however, and did not appear in revised Operational Guidelines adopted by the World Heritage Committee in 1978 (UNESCO 1978).

i)	Represent a unique artistic or aesthetic achievement, a masterpiece of human creative genius
ii)	Have exerted considerable influence, over a span of time or within a cultural area of the world, on subsequent developments in architecture, monumental sculpture, garden and landscape design, related arts, or human settlements
iii)	Be unique, extremely rare, or of great antiquity
iv)	Be among the most characteristic examples of a type of structure, the type representing an important cultural, social, artistic, scientific, technological or industrial development
v)	Be a characteristic example of a significant, traditional style of architecture, method of construction, or human settlement, that is fragile by nature or has become vulnerable under the impact of irreversible socio-cultural or economic change
vi)	Be most importantly associated with ideas or beliefs, with events or with persons, of outstanding historical importance or significance

Figure 2: The 1977 cultural criteria for inscription on the World Heritage List (UNESCO 1977b)

The requirements for evaluating nominations were further clarified by adding that, in every case, consideration must be given to the state of preservation of the property. Each “should be evaluated relatively, in comparison to the state of preservation of other property dating from the same period and of the same type and category”. This requirement thereby established the requirement in all nominations for definitive comparative analysis as part of the justification of OUV.

In efforts to provide clarity and operational reliability, the criteria were adjusted and developed three times before they were again formally adopted in 1980. Further development was required however, as the advisory bodies (especially ICOMOS) sought to accommodate the unanticipated scope and variety of the earliest cultural nominations to the List. The original notion of the World Heritage List an elite list of the world’s outstanding heritage, “the best of the best”, was also forced over the next 20 years to develop conceptually and practically. Global study from 1983 sought to provide a suitable framework for the growth of the List (Cameron and Rössler, 2016, p.76) as the appetite of European countries for World Heritage illustrated by the numbers of European nominations to the List created a significantly unbalanced group of global properties that did not reflect the composition of the Convention’s States Parties. Nonetheless this phenomenon continued unabated with the Committee reticent to ‘cap’ the numbers of nominations presented by individual States Parties each year. By 1992, the 20th anniversary of the Convention, there was an obvious need to address lack of balance in the List which, by then, had become a very significant issue. In that year the 16th Session of the WH Committee was presented with an “Evaluation Report on the Implementation of the Convention” (UNESCO 1992a) which pointed out that lack of global representative balance and an over-reliance on the nomination of monuments could no longer be ignored. The issue was related, in part, to the cultural criteria the narrow scope of which endured despite seven modifications up to 1992 (Jokilehto et al., 2008, Annex 2A). At that point it was clear that the criteria did not adequately address or recognise the global range of social and anthropological aspects of cultural heritage. This had led to repeated inscription of “privileged” and elite sites of architectural, religious and/or artistic value, reflecting Eurocentric notions of

heritage¹⁰. The 1992 report led to an important decision that the cultural criteria needed to be significantly broadened to include non-monumental cultural heritage. Cultural Landscapes were added as a new cultural category of World Heritage property (UNESCO 1992b) and from 1992 onwards discussion focused more on the potential need to ‘cap’ the List while the very size of the List was deemed by others, including Herb Stovel who was the ICOMOS General Secretary at the time, to be a measure of its success (Cameron and Rössler, 2016, p.57). Accordingly, the Committee focused on supporting the Global Strategy to create a more balanced World Heritage List (UNESCO 1998; Ishizawa and Westrik, 2021) including supporting concerted efforts on the part of the Advisory Bodies to produce targeted thematic studies on under-represented heritage.

1998-2005 continuing efforts to define OUV

Reflecting the influence of the [Nara document on Authenticity 1994](#), OUV was probably best defined in 1998 as “...an outstanding response to issues of universal nature common to or addressed by all human cultures. In relation to natural heritage, such issues are seen in bio-geographical diversity; in relation to culture in human creativity and resulting cultural diversity” (UNESCO 1998). The Nara Document changed perceptions of authenticity and sought greater acceptance of cultural and heritage diversity in conservation practice, stressing the cultural integrity of replacement/renewal of material elements of monuments and buildings and the importance of continuity, a topic that is still subject to debate (e.g. Khalaf, 2020). It also introduced the term “attribution” in the assessment of value (Young, 2021). By defining the attributes of sites as the essential carriers or vessels of value (Araoz, 2008, p.169-171), the justification of OUV was made somewhat clearer. Of importance, it was also accepted that the attributes could also include intangible and associative values. That notion became integrated into World Heritage thereafter and had an important bearing on the assessment of the integrity of cultural sites which was briefly alluded to in 2002 (OP. G. 2002, Para 24b) and eventually adopted for cultural sites in the Operational Guidelines in 2005 (UNESCO 2025, Para 87-89).

¹⁰In spite of recognition of the problem far greater numbers of nominations from Europe and the developed world continued during the following 15 years leaving other parts of the globe underrepresented (UNESCO 2007,39).

The Nara Document and the subsequent UNESCO cultural conventions reflect an evolution in global definitions of what culture and cultural heritage means and all it represents in all its global diversity. The 2001 UNESCO Universal Declaration on Cultural Diversity and Convention on the protection of the Underwater Cultural Heritage, the 2003 Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage¹¹ and the 2005 Convention on the Protection and Promotion of the Diversity of Cultural Expressions all sought not just to advocate for the protection of cultural expressions and cultural heritage as part of social identity, but to reinforce UNESCO's mission to promote tolerance for the diversity of culture globally. These conventions, like the World Heritage Convention, were promoted as mechanisms for the promotion of tolerance for the multiplicity of socio-cultural identities and well-being worldwide, while fostering intergovernmental cultural tolerance in international diplomatic and economic relations. Even though each of the cultural conventions are in some way related, there is no overarching governance mechanism within which they can work together.

Concerted expert consideration of OUV continued within ICOMOS after 1998, influenced by the revision of the Burra Charter (ICOMOS 1999) and it led to the so-called Gap Report prepared by ICOMOS (2004). The report was prepared in response to the invitation by the World Heritage Committee at its 24th Session in Cairns (2000) to: "proceed with an analysis of sites inscribed on the World Heritage List and the Tentative List on a regional, chronological, geographical and thematic basis" and to "provide States Parties with a clear overview of the present situation, and likely trends in the short to medium term with a view to identifying under-represented categories". The report pointed out that the imbalance in the List was due to two factors: i) structural issues relating to the World Heritage nomination processes and to managing and protecting cultural properties and ii) qualitative issues relating to the way properties are identified, assessed and evaluated, and the way that properties were assessed (by States Parties) for Outstanding Universal Value when

they were submitted as candidate nominations to the World Heritage List. (ICOMOS 2004, p.2). Acting on this information, the World Heritage Centre with the Advisory Bodies embarked on a major revision of the [Operational Guidelines](#) between 2002 and 2005.

Following up on the ICOMOS 2004 report, an important statement on OUV was presented to the World Heritage Committee meeting in Kazan, Russia in 2005 (Cameron, 2005). It was followed soon afterwards by the seminal ICOMOS study on OUV (Jokilehto et al, 2008) that integrated concerns about lack of representativity on the World Heritage List. In spite of the detail in this publication, it still failed to pin down a precise operational meaning for OUV. The report states that OUV could be seen not so much as the "best of the best" globally but rather as "representative of the best" in a thematic and geo-cultural regional context (Jokilehto et al, 2008, p.9). The World Heritage Convention thereby evolved from a treaty that sought to engage shared responsibility for humanity's most prized sites to sharing the World Heritage List as an exercise in global representation (Brumann, 2014, p.2076). Cameron's 2005 report stressed some important central notions related to OUV that still resonate in the determination of heritage values generally. A selection of these includes:

- values are attributed by people and through human appreciation
- the concept of value must be widely drawn and allow for evolution over time
- evaluation criteria must continue to evolve to accommodate changing perceptions and interpretations of heritage
- the concept of OUV implies a shared concern for the conservation of that value/significance
- OUV is poorly articulated in general and requires major communication efforts, both generally and at site level
- identification of value/significance needs wide participation by stakeholders including local communities and indigenous people

¹¹The intangible cultural heritage is sometimes called living cultural heritage and includes activities, expressions, knowledge, practices, and the cultural spaces in which these living heritage are expressed (UNESCO, 2003; ICOMOS Xi'an, 2005)

The report stressed the centrality of the criteria which became 'fixed' following the revision of the Operational Guidelines undertaken between 2002 and 2005. The current iteration of the criteria dates from 2005. The revision was formalised by a Committee decision in 2003 (Decision 6EXT.COM 5.1) and the textual revisions were adopted in 2005 (see 'World Heritage Criteria' below). Of importance, the 2005 version of the guidelines merged the cultural and natural criteria into a single list with cultural criteria (i) – (vi) and natural criteria (vii) – (x). The merger was a response to the growing acceptance that culture and nature could not be regarded as uninfluenced by each

other. Nonetheless, the merger of the criteria did not result in full integration, even though the need for the integration of natural and cultural values in both cultural and natural heritage was widely accepted at the time. This was and remains due to the division of evaluation responsibility between ICOMOS and IUCN and it continues as before for practical reasons, albeit with a far greater level of communication between these Advisory Bodies especially on relevant mixed cultural and natural nominations that use a combination of the cultural and natural criteria. Cameron's 2005 report also stressed the importance of the conditions of authenticity and integrity (ibid).

World Heritage Criteria

World Heritage criteria quoted from the Operational Guidelines for the Implementation of the World Heritage Convention Section II.D, Para. 77-78). (UNESCO 2025)

77. The Committee considers a property as having Outstanding Universal Value (see paragraphs 49-53) if the property meets one or more of the following criteria. Nominated properties shall therefore:

- represent a masterpiece of human creative genius;
- exhibit an important interchange of human values, over a span of time or within a cultural area of the world, on developments in architecture or technology, monumental arts, town-planning or landscape design;
- bear a unique or at least exceptional testimony to a cultural tradition or to a civilization which is living or which has disappeared;
- be an outstanding example of a type of building, architectural or technological ensemble or landscape which illustrates (a) significant stage(s) in human history;
- be an outstanding example of a traditional human settlement, land-use, or sea-use which is representative of a culture (or cultures), or human interaction with the environment especially when it has become vulnerable under the impact of irreversible change;
- be directly or tangibly associated with events or living traditions, with ideas, or with beliefs, with artistic and literary works of outstanding universal significance. (The Committee considers that this criterion should preferably be used in conjunction with other criteria);
- contain superlative natural phenomena or areas of exceptional natural beauty and aesthetic importance;
- be outstanding examples representing major stages of earth's history, including the record of life, significant on-going geological processes in the development of landforms, or significant geomorphic or physiographic features;
- be outstanding examples representing significant on-going ecological and biological processes in the evolution and development of terrestrial, fresh water, coastal and marine ecosystems and communities of plants and animals;
- contain the most important and significant natural habitats for in-situ conservation of biological diversity, including those containing threatened species of Outstanding Universal Value from the point of view of science or conservation.

78. To be deemed of Outstanding Universal Value, a property must also meet the conditions of integrity and/or authenticity and must have an adequate protection and management system to ensure its safeguarding.

Post 2005 Criteria, Integrity and Authenticity

Since the major review of the Operational Guidelines in 2005, the criteria for nomination, the conditions of integrity and authenticity and the definition of OUV have remained largely unchanged with the exception of Para 80 on authenticity which added (re. value) 'as accumulated over time' in 2015. For nominating States Parties, the choice criteria are the first step in the identification and evaluation of OUV; it is critical to achieve the correct 'fit' and ensure that criteria chosen are suitable. However, the identification of the attributes of the nominated site is equally critical.

Since 2005, all nominations are required to include a formal Statement of Outstanding Universal Value and to present a justification for that claim. After 2008, all States Parties with existing properties on the List were obliged to submit Retrospective Statements of OUV for their inscribed sites.

Authenticity

In its articulation of the concept of authenticity the text of the Operational Guidelines (UNESCO 2025, Para 80) states that "The ability to understand the value attributed to the heritage depends on the degree to which information sources about this value may be understood as credible or truthful. Knowledge and understanding of these sources of information, in relation to original and subsequent characteristics of the cultural heritage, and their meaning as accumulated over time, are the requisite bases for assessing all aspects of authenticity." This can be taken to mean that, in line with the Nara document mentioned above, multiple sources of information are required. Authenticity is technically demonstrated and assessed in World Heritage in relation to eight categories of consideration. Depending on the type of cultural heritage, and its cultural context, properties may be understood to meet the conditions of authenticity if their cultural values (as recognized in the criteria proposed) are truthfully and credibly expressed through a variety of attributes including:

- form and design;
- materials and substance;
- use and function;
- traditions, techniques and management systems;

- location and setting;
- language, and other forms of intangible heritage;
- spirit and feeling; and
- other internal and external factors.

(Ibid., Para 82).

Integrity

Integrity on the other hand has always been regarded as an elusive concept and UNESCO provides no definitional protocol in relation to cultural heritage (Gullino and Larcher, 2013), nor has it been very clearly defined in the Operational Guidelines (Paras 87-90), although there is a short explanation in the 2011 resource manual on Nominating World Heritage Properties (UNESCO 2011). Integrity is more easily demonstrated in natural heritage than in some forms of cultural heritage, being "a measure of the wholeness and intactness of the natural and/or cultural heritage and its attributes. Examining the conditions of integrity, therefore requires assessing the extent to which the property: a) includes all elements necessary to express its Outstanding Universal Value; b) is of adequate size to ensure the complete representation of the features and processes which convey the property's significance; c) or suffers from adverse effects of development and/or neglect. This should be presented in a [statement of integrity](#)" (ibid.). The text of the guidelines attempts to explain, albeit briefly in Paras 89-90, how this might be applied under the ten criteria. In relation to the cultural criteria, it states that 89. "For properties nominated under criteria (i) to (vi), the physical fabric of the property and/or its significant features should be in good condition, and the impact of deterioration processes controlled. A significant proportion of the elements necessary to convey the totality of the value conveyed by the property should be included. Relationships and dynamic functions present in cultural landscapes, historic towns or other living properties essential to their distinctive character should also be maintained". The guidelines fail to address those aspects of cultural integrity that must be measured in a more nuanced way. A side comment, dated 2005, states "Examples of the application of the conditions of integrity to properties nominated under criteria (i) - (vi) are under development". This development has never taken place in spite of several expert meetings, including an important meeting at [Al Ain in 2012](#) on the matter which suggested a number of

revisions to the Operational Guidelines that were never followed up. While the promised guidance on integrity is still awaited, confusion can arise between the notion of integrity and the State of Conservation of a property. The two are, of course, linked but the integrity of the property is linked to its value and, in the process of nomination, ensuring that the property is of sufficient size and is sufficiently well preserved to convey its value. The State of Conservation is a technical assessment of physical/material condition including deterioration processes and their impacts, and it is linked to the focus on the management of the property.

Adapting Outstanding Universal Value to cater for diversity

The World Heritage Convention explicitly aims to establish a common collaborative system for the protection of world-class heritage across distinctive places, times and cultures by formally identifying those places with demonstrable OUV (Schmutz and Elliot, 2017, p.155). In a reflection on OUV in relation to cultural World Heritage, Jokilehto (2006, p.1) pointed out that in order to meet the requirements of inscription (i.e. one or more of the criteria and satisfying the conditions of authenticity and integrity) one should approach the question as a process, identifying the relevant themes of universal nature (such as spirituality, defence, utilisation of resources etc.), and to verify the representativity in the pertinent cultural-historical context. In addition, nominations had to provide a guarantee of an appropriate management system and a plan for the protection of the nominated resource into the future. Jokilehto also pointed out that UNESCO's emphasis on the recognition of "cultural diversity as a fundamental aspect of heritage" would bring a certain difficulty in the assessment of cultural values, aiming to address that by stating also that the attribution of value occurs in the "social association of qualities to things" (ibid., 2). However, he neglects in this text to identify non-religious spiritual values that are associated with places – a value that centrally important to Indigenous Peoples and local communities. This point was soon afterwards formally recognised by ICOMOS at its [general assembly in Quebec 2008](#). The debate has continued to move forward since that time but the need to accommodate the plurality of cultural values globally has remained challenging within World Heritage as an essentially State-centred, inter-governmental system.

Evaluating World Heritage

Evaluation of nominations to the World Heritage List is a protracted and complex business that takes place over almost 2 years involving up to 35-40+ people in each advisory body and several stages of review for each nomination. Both ICOMOS and IUCN are charged with this task as advisors to the World Heritage Committee and each make a selection of scientifically appropriate practitioners from their global membership to undertake the work annually. Individually chosen people with appropriate academic, professional and heritage management backgrounds undertake the desk reviews of the nominations, while many nominations require additional and technically focused reviews on matters such as tourism or aspects of culture and/or regional ecologies. Both ICOMOS and IUCN select members to create a globally representative World Heritage Panel annually. The Panels collectively review the nominations, desk studies and field evaluation mission reports with time to engage in discussion with States Parties as necessary. Following the technical field evaluation missions the Panels of each organisation meet twice over many days to collectively review the documents and finalise the evaluations. These reports include the Advisory Bodies' recommendations to the Committee and provide a draft decision text on each nomination.

Each evaluation starts by assessing the OUV (significance) of the property and the criteria chosen to demonstrate it. Acceptance of the state party's justification of OUV is always predicated on the recognition that the property meets one or more of the criteria and the conditions of authenticity and integrity. The justification of OUV must be supported by a detailed comparative analysis that demonstrates why the nominated site is unique/outstanding as a particular type of site in the geo-cultural region in which it is located. Many other factors are considered that relate to the State Party's ability to protect the OUV of the property if it is inscribed. The factors considered include: the choice of boundaries and buffer zone, the legal protection mechanisms, the identified threats, the state of conservation of the site, and the presentation of an appropriate management framework/management plan. Other factors can be included, including local community consultation and participation and issues relating to tourism and its impacts. All are focused on the ability of the State Party to protect the OUV of the place once it is inscribed.¹³

From inception, World Heritage evaluation has been an expert-led and expert-assisted endeavour which, in the past, was significantly influenced by 'western/global north concepts of culture, heritage and conservation philosophy and management within its Advisory Bodies (ICOMOS, ICCROM and IUCN). However, the approaches now used have been significantly broadened in line with developments in academic and professional heritage management thinking internationally. Some of the considerations raised by individual nominations have also created gradual changes in approach and have precipitated the preparation of dedicated thematic studies designed to advise both States Parties and the World Heritage Committee. The three Advisory Bodies have therefore absorbed emerging critical scientific and academic thought and developed far more comprehensive and plural understandings of heritage significance and cultural value in their professional activities globally and, by association, in their evaluation of World Heritage. They have done this in recognition of principles set out in all six of UNESCO's cultural conventions integrating broader perspectives of cultural values and cultural diversity, including non-monumental cultural heritage, intangible cultural heritage and the link between culture and the natural world.

As noted above, the integration of cultural values into nature conservation and vice versa in World Heritage has occurred gradually, accepting that for many cultures the two are indivisible. The [Connecting Practice initiative of IUCN and ICOMOS](#) was established in 2013 and it continues its development in the [IUCN ICOMOS ICCROM Nature-Culture Journey](#) platform. In addition, people-centred approaches to the attribution of cultural value and the management of cultural heritage have been an important element of training within ICCROM from 2013, following on from its [Living Heritage Programme](#) (2003-2008) and also taken up by other organisations e.g. [Europa Nostra](#). The UNESCO Recommendation on [Historic Urban Landscape](#) (2011) and an increasing focus on heritage-led regeneration in cities (e.g. the theme for ICOMOS GA 2012) has continued to develop through the [Organisation of World Heritage Cities](#).

Policy emphasis in World Heritage changed in 2007 from a concern about representativity and capacity-

building during its 30th anniversary year (the four 'C's', or strategic objectives of Convention in 2002: Credibility, Conservation, Capacity building and Communication) with the addition of "the fifth 5 C", Communities in a policy that seeks "To enhance the role of communities in the implementation of the Convention" (UNESCO 2025, Para 26, 5). This strategic objective in 2007 was the result of an acknowledgement that community awareness, understanding, engagement and participation was essential for the successful management of World Heritage properties. This community aspect of World Heritage policy was quickly linked to the notion of heritage as a driver of sustainable development but dedicated policy on the integration of sustainable development was slow to emerge in World Heritage and its policy was only finally adopted in 2015 (UNESCO 2015; Cave and Negussie, 2017) in line with the Convention's text (Art 5) which notes that States Parties should "adopt general policies to give the heritage a function in the life of the community". Since the revisions of the Operational Guidelines in 2015 and especially in 2019 there has been an increasing emphasis on local communities, community engagement, rights and participation.

Despite the policy emphasis on communities as key stakeholders World Heritage, as an international treaty of States Parties, is of necessity a largely a state-driven and state managed endeavour, or a cooperative multi-state endeavour in the case of transnational serial nominations. Community-led nominations are rare, the East Rennell Islands (WH 854), Budj Bim, Australia (WH 1577), Writing-on-Stone / Áísínai'pi, Canada (WH 1597) and Pimachoiwin Aki, Canada (WH 1415rev) being notable examples.

Pimachoiwin Aki is of particular interest as a mixed cultural and natural nomination because the first ICOMOS evaluation of the property in 2013 questioned the property's cultural significance which the evaluation found not to be outstanding. The evaluation report also makes a notable statement that "To satisfy cultural criteria, the value of the interaction between people and their environment over time needs to be shown to be exceptional in cultural terms"(UNESCO 2013), finding the comparative analysis of this nomination to be inadequate at the time. It added "What has not been demonstrated is how

¹³The evaluations of nominations to the World Heritage List annually are published on the UNESCO World Heritage website together with other World Heritage Committee Meeting Agenda items as Item 8: (e.g.) INF8B1 (ICOMOS) and INF8B2 (IUCN). The reference number remains the same each year.

this strong association between the Anishinaabeg people and the land in the area nominated can be seen to be exceptional – in other words of wider importance than to the Anishinaabeg themselves. However, in the supplementary information provided by the State Party it was made clear these First Nations peoples did not wish present their property as being ‘exceptional’ as they did not want to make judgements about the relationships of other First Nations with their lands and thus make comparisons. When finally inscribed in 2018, following referral of a revised nomination in 2016 when the nomination did make a claim to exceptionality, ICOMOS found that “In making the case for why it is considered that there is room on the World Heritage List for Pimachiowin Aki, it is suggested that it has the most complete representation of the attributes and is thus an exceptional example and has the strongest claim to Outstanding Universal Value, over and above others presented in the comparative analysis” (UNESCO, 2013 *ibid.*).

World Heritage at 50

There is an abiding tension within the World Heritage system between OUV as its central standard (based on exceptionality and universally recognisable and/or acknowledged transcendent value) and its policy emphasis on representativity, with an implicit acknowledgement of cultural diversity and the importance of local communities, community engagement, participation and a growing acknowledgement of the place of minority rights in the management of World Heritage. The growing emphasis on heritage as driver of sustainable development has brought additional societal, environmental and economic values to bear on World Heritage. The World Heritage policy on sustainable development (UNESCO, 2015) seeks a focus on community inclusion, benefit-share and resilience, all of which require a sensitivity towards minority inclusiveness, human rights and cultural diversity in the participatory management of World Heritage. The perspectives of Indigenous Peoples and minority cultural rights are also being heard more at WH Committee meetings (influenced by the UNESCO

2003 and 2005 conventions and the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (United Nations, 2007; Meskell, 2013). However, these issues can be ignored by States Parties as the revisions to the Operational Guidelines in 2015 and 2019 simply urge States Parties to “consider” them¹⁴.

Notwithstanding significant plural policy development the World Heritage system, the imbalance in the List remains, reflecting global political and economic power dynamics. World Heritage primarily serves national interests, politically, culturally, and economically and this can be recognised in the forum (the annual World Heritage Committee Meeting) of the General Assembly of States Parties to the Convention. The economic value and awareness of World Heritage have grown as the List has grown, largely through its use as a resource for tourism development which has flourished especially in recent decades. The World Heritage brand is highly sought-after, not just for this reason but also as part of promoting national identity (Labadi, 2015). However, it has led to a situation where culture and natural heritage can be vulnerable to commercial capture and overuse, thereby giving rise to socio-economic processes of exclusion (Larsen, 2018, p.22).

Because of its legal and governance structure as an international treaty body of States Parties, with an elected representative committee, diplomacy and politics have always played a role in the conduct of the General Assembly, in World Heritage Committee meetings. Politics and diplomacy influence the conduct of Committee meetings and their decisions, with occasional outright conflict between the Committee and the expert technical/scientific opinions of its advisory bodies (Meskell 2014, Brumann 2021). The result has been the approval of nominations for inscription that have been inadequately or inappropriately formulated. Some have not met the requirements for demonstrating OUV. Others lack adequate protective provision and/or suffer from development and other pressures and lack of management capacity. In some cases, the Committee will decide to inscribe and simply request the State Party to improve the protective provision and/or develop its management framework.

¹⁴Op.G 2015 Para 40 (+text box on UNDRIP); Para 123; Annex 6B (IUCN evaluation procedure); WHC Decision 39COM11. Op.G 2019 Paras. 12,14,64,111,117 (Decision 43 COM 11A).

To avoid this situation and ensure that future nominations are correctly formulated at an early stage, the Committee after much deliberation and formally introduced a process of nomination reform in 2021. This adds a new and additional phase of Preliminary Assessment for the benefit of nominating States Parties and was introduced on a voluntary basis from Sept. 2023 and will become a mandatory phase of the nomination cycle in 2027 (UNESCO 2025, Para 122, Annexes 3 & 6).

Once World Heritage status is awarded to a heritage property the State Party has a duty to conserve its OUV. This requirement is all too frequently not met.¹⁵ But the World Heritage 'brand' still remains highly sought-after, and the List continues to grow. In this regard the Convention can be seen to have successfully raised awareness of the immense range and value of World Heritage and, while conservation and management may be inadequate in many places, it is excellent in many others. Targetted violent destruction is a rarity but it has occurred in conflict situations and it often gives rise to reactive international collaboration on reconstruction of the kind dreamt of by the founders of the Convention. The orientation and the quality of the professional activity and development within World Heritage can be seen in the published output and policy development work of the World Heritage Centre and the Advisory Bodies. On one level it relates to capacity-building, training and advisory output on World Heritage, through the UNESCO Category 2 Centres and in site-specific cases at the request of States Parties. At another level, each these agencies in their own way address the growing global issues for natural and cultural heritage conservation in the face of global cross-cutting issues. Developments can be seen in policy and guidance on climate action, risk preparedness, human rights, community resilience and sustainable development while maintaining efforts to uphold the original mission of the Convention which sought global collaborative action and support for the protection and conservation of the Outstanding Universal Value of World Heritage properties.

Conclusions

In the hierarchy of heritage management systems, World Heritage regards properties with OUV as a global legacy in a framework of intergenerational equity, and its mission is to promote cooperative and collaborative international agency in the protection of the places on its List that possess this universal significance for the benefit of the future generations of all mankind (UNESCO 1972a, Art. 7)¹⁶. Responsibility for the choice of properties on the WH List is made by the elected State Party representatives on the World Heritage Committee, advised by experts and in line with the requirements of the Operational Guidelines.

At a national level, heritage inventories and the choice of what heritage should be protected also remains a State-sponsored endeavour and this includes those candidate World Heritage properties that are chosen for the World Heritage Tentative List. The process of selection is most frequently undertaken in the domain of heritage professionals employed by government, but since 2010 States Parties can be assisted in this task by the Advisory Bodies under the Upstream Process (Terrill, 2014). While the 'voice' of community is increasingly sought, and some nominations are community-led, state agencies generally choose what is to be selected, protected, and conserved as outstanding on the global stage.

Developments within the World Heritage system and the attempts to define and use OUV as a standard for selection and management of World Heritage, reflects the development in thinking and the copious academic literature that has examined the heritage values and uses of heritage (e.g. Avrami, 2010; Poulis, 2010; De la Torre, 2013; Clark, 2014; Fredheim and Khalaf, 2016; Silberman, 2014; Jones, 2017; Smith, 2012; Smith and Waterton, 2012; Diaz Andreu, 2017; Avrami et al, 2019). In both World Heritage and state systems, it has been state agencies that decide on selection of sites for state protection while a vast number of NGOs, academic science and heritage management practitioners and civil society groups have pressed for the development of heritage, conservation and application of appropriate management frameworks. There are increasing numbers of successful cases, at individual

¹⁵In 2025 there are 1248 properties on the WH List, of which 96 properties are on the List of World Heritage in Danger, while the Committee examined the State of Conservation of 247 properties in 2025.

¹⁶Article 7 For the purpose of this Convention, international protection of the world cultural and natural heritage shall be understood to mean the establishment of a system of international cooperation and assistance designed to support States Parties to the Convention in their efforts to conserve and identify that heritage.

state level, where communities and trusts have taken the initiative to drive a World Heritage nomination and have taken on the responsibility for custodianship, promotion, and management.

Nonetheless, it is the state and its heritage services that continue to be the dominant agents tasked with the responsibility for legal heritage inventories and designation, while the duty of custodianship has become more grounded in notions of socio-cultural value and the economic benefits of historic environment (urban and rural). World Heritage has had to link its policies to a mix of socio-cultural and economic concerns linked to sustainable development and tourism, with a management focus

aimed at participatory governance involving those communities who host WH properties. Multivocality in interpretation and presentation narratives have been increasingly catered for with a greater focus on universal (incl. minority) rights of access and enjoyment of heritage, while also catering for a diversity of participation and types of ownership. An examination of the development of thinking and technical advice on OUV within World Heritage demonstrates how the Convention has adapted to changing notions of heritage value that now pertain in a globalised world and the scope of its priorities. All have affected the way governance of the World Heritage has developed, and how OUV is assessed.

SECTION 5

EAC Surveys on Significance – Comparison between Countries

Katalin Wollák, Bjørn Smit, Agnieszka Makowska, Ulla Kadakas and Thor Ingólfsson Hjaltalín

5.1 The EAC “Making Choices” Surveys in 2017 and 2019

One of the primary aims of the EAC is to share knowledge about methods for safeguarding our common archaeological heritage. Every European member country has its own national, regional and local policies, regulations, guidelines and best practices when dealing with archaeological heritage, sites and remains. Exchange of information on these specific approaches is crucial so that heritage specialists from different countries can benefit from each other's experience. One of the ways the EAC contributes to this exchange is by issuing surveys in which heritage specialists from each country are asked to provide information.

During the 16th EAC Annual Meeting (2015), a programme for the future of archaeological heritage management in Europe was presented. The [Amersfoort Agenda](#) (EAC, 2015) outlined three major themes: embedding archaeology in society; the importance of conscious, explicit and transparent choices in archaeological heritage management and data

management in the digital age. The EAC Working Group on Making Choices was set up to address these issues and prepared a survey which sought to understand the way in which decision-making in archaeological heritage management was undertaken in the context of the Valletta and Faro Conventions. The result was the [Making Choices survey](#) conducted in 2017 (EAC, 2018), and this was followed by the establishment of three new Working Groups in 2019.

One of these new groups, the EAC ‘Making the Case’ Working Group, prepared a new survey in 2019 with the aim to collect information about the public benefit of development-led archaeology in Europe. The survey supported guidance to help archaeological heritage managers explain to decision makers, politicians, investors and developers, and the general public, the range of public benefits which archaeology can create.¹⁷ A number of the questions in that survey provided information relevant to the assessment of archaeological significance.

¹⁷The full survey is not published, but the results are discussed in [EAC Guidelines 4](#) and [EAC Guidelines 5](#) and in this document.

5.2 Examining Significance: the 2017 Survey

The Survey Questions

The survey considered the choices involved in: the way in which sites are defined and inventoried and the degree to which they are accorded relative importance or significance; the way investigations are planned to focus on research outcomes; how they are disseminated and archived; the way in which the public can get involved and questions of funding. The 24 questions of the survey were answered by 23 representatives from 19 countries, with more than one response in the case of countries with federal states.

Several questions in the 2017 EAC survey raised the issue of the assessment of archaeological value and significance. The questions requested answers to the following specific issues: how countries record or list archaeological sites or elements of archaeological heritage; the criteria for officially listing or protecting archaeological sites; the evaluation system for assessing sites or areas (reserves), i.e. the assessment of their value and significance; the extent to which values other than archaeological heritage are taken into account.

Analysis of the Answers

What characteristics does your state use to choose whether archaeological evidence of past activity at any location is significant enough for that place to be considered an 'element of the archaeological heritage' or as an 'archaeological site'. (A further explanation helped to interpret the question: how to define a threshold for their archaeological sites, i.e. how do you decide a site is of archaeological interest or has archaeological values? Referring to Article 1 of the Valletta Convention)

The question raised here was primarily about whether the archaeological features/remains observed are significant enough for considering the location as an archaeological site. This decision could lead to the registration of the site, and thus also determine the archaeological intervention required for any proposed development. The majority of the respondents described what the criteria or definition of archaeological heritage is in their country. More than half of the respondents indicated that there is no time limit on the definition of archaeological heritage. Where there is a time limit, it is either 100 years or dating before 1700 (Table 1).

State	Parameters for protection (in 2017)
Estonia	older than 18th century
Finland	at least one hundred years old (intellectual tradition is fixed natural objects associated with old traditions, tales or significant historic events)
Hungary	older than 1711
Iceland	over 100 years old
Ireland	with emphasis on the pre-AD 1700 period
Latvia, Lithuania	earlier than 18th century
Norway	predating 1537 AD (automatically protected + Sami sites older than 100 years)
Sweden	remains of human activity from (1) past ages, (2) resulting from ancient custom and having been (3) permanently abandoned - to be protected an archaeological site has to be older than 1850

Table 1: Parameters for protection by state, as recorded in 2017.

The majority of respondents did not specify the amount of information required to declare the status of a site. Some respondents pointed out that there is a difference between the definition of the known and the protected sites. In general, every protected site is known, but not every known site is protected as national monument in each country. The Netherlands did outline the distinction between what is known to be an archaeological site and what is specifically a site that should be preserved in or ex situ (protected), to which they apply a rating system, based on intrinsic (scientific) value, physical quality or absolute quality.

What are the criteria your state uses for choosing which 'sites' should be legally protected? (A further explanation helped to interpret the question: how decisions are reached about which specific monuments and sites are protected - Referring to Article 1-2 of the Valletta Convention)

There are countries where sites identified under a valid definition are automatically protected by law, and in some countries this applies even if the site is not yet known/explored (e.g. Germany - "Deklaratorisches Prinzip"). Generally speaking, however, in all countries different levels of protection may exist, achieved by applying a set of criteria combining spatiality (local/regional/national/ supranational levels) with various value contexts, such as:

- historical, archaeological, artistic, aesthetic, scientific, social, technical or folkloric interest (value) / architectural, traditional/ intangible value, symbolic, religious value
- rarity, uniqueness, authenticity (must have an archaeological cultural layer)
- type of the site, landscape context
- physical quality/condition of the site
- documented status
- possibility to be displayed, visibility.

The significance may be based on finds in addition to archaeological features. The condition of the site is also an aspect, but not an exclusive criterion. The resulting protection is essentially the basis for achieving preservation (in the public interest) such as preservation in situ. Methods of protection may be:

- listing (in many countries) on a named list or register
- supported by legal instrument
- protected through the planning process (part of municipal, provincial or state land-use plans, archaeological policy map (Norway, the Netherlands), and national safeguard strategies (Portugal), guidance can help the process.
- in some countries the owner of the site, or the general public may also have a role in declaring protection.

What are the criteria for choosing known archaeological 'sites' to add to an official inventory?

(A further explanation helped to interpret the question: if the inventory is selective, than what particular qualifications a 'site' needs to be included in an official inventory - Referring to Article 2 of the Valletta Convention)

Each country has different practices for registering archaeological sites. A variety of names and formats are used to describe what are essentially national inventories, including:

- Official national inventory, registry
- List of Archaeological Sites, statutory list, national list
- Sites and Monument Records/ Historic Environment Records
- Archaeological Information system

Registration in these inventories is mainly based on the Valletta Convention definition, and in almost all countries, only known sites are included in the inventory, and places that may have archaeological interest (potential archaeological sites) are not included. Bavaria is an example of an exception, where non-researched sites can also be listed based on historical and scientific significance ("Deklaratorisches Prinzip"). Some countries also list sites at risk.

In many countries, some forms of enhanced protection exist, and again these inventories of sites which benefit from higher levels of protection have different names, including:

- National List of the State Protected Cultural monuments /Sites
- National inventory
- Scheduled monuments

This higher level of protection may be based on a variety of importance/ significance criteria including:

- national importance based on historical, architectural, traditional, artistic, or archaeological interest
- the site should be visible, well remained or to be shown
- site type and dating, rarity of site type, preservation
- date range and to be authentic (criteria for determining the significance level in Lithuania)
- determining whether the site is worthy of preservation and it should be of (inter)national importance.

How does your state assign relative values and/or significance to different 'sites'? (A further explanation helped to interpret the question: how member states weigh the relative significance of archaeological sites - Referring to Article 1 of the Valletta Convention)

This question asked whether any ranking system is used. Most of the answers indicated that ranking is only used where two or more levels of enhanced protection are available. Many countries recognise some level of international protection (e.g. UNESCO World Heritage Sites), then have national or state protection for the most significant monuments or sites, then potentially some further levels of regional, municipal or local protection. In some countries, the presence of preserved built elements or specific landscape value adds to the level of protection.

The Netherlands has a very complex differentiating system to define which sites should be protected in or ex situ. A scoring system is used for 1. Sites listed by the state, 2. Sites of high archaeological value, 3. Sites of archaeological value. There were also some respondents who highlighted the complexity of social significance in addition to archaeological value – [Northern Ireland's guidance](#) providing a good example of this.

Valletta mentions the idea of physical 'context' in relation to the defined archaeological heritage. (Article 1) Does your state use the concept of context to inform decision-making? If so, how does it do this? Is 'context' defined in ways that are clear to the wider public, including developers? (A further explanation helped to interpret the question: what Valletta means by 'context' and how significant this is in later management choices – Referring to Article 1 of the Valletta Convention)

Some countries know and apply the definition of a preventive zone (buffer zone) e.g. for World Heritage Sites and to sites where the nature of the site justifies it (e.g. strongholds or burial places). In some countries, where the site includes an area large enough to preserve the remains and give them adequate space with regard to their character and significance, they may even operate within a broader 'ensemble' site definition.

Does your state identify wider areas or zones of archaeological importance (the 'reserves' referred to in the Valletta convention) which have a legal status? If so, what are the criteria for their selection? (A further explanation helped to interpret the question: how decisions are reached about establishing protected archaeological 'areas' – Referring to Article 1.2 of the Valletta Convention)

Many countries do not have archaeological reserves, and where they do, the number is low. The clear aim of this designation is in situ preservation, which includes also "non-excavation". Responses to this question tended to focus on the ways in which reserves are designated rather than on the rationale for designation (e.g. Germany (DE-BW): high value structures). The formulation of the importance or significance values that justify the selection was not really mentioned in the answers.

There are countries where the designation is for a limited period (e.g. 20 years), aiming to reduce agricultural use. The way of implementation may be buying the land, for which the priorities include: 1. On World Heritage Sites 2. Communities willing to participate 3. Land with owners willing to sell. Elsewhere these locations are called Archaeological Areas characterised by accumulation of archaeological objects and harmony of the natural environment (Lithuania), or Cultural Parks with an aim to protect the

cultural landscape (Poland) or Areas of Archaeological Importance (UK) with similar functions. They may include archaeological World Heritage Sites, National Parks, Areas of Outstanding Beauty and Conservation Areas. The definitions can also be: Area of Special Archaeological Interest – primarily the visual and physical envelope around key State Care Monuments; Area of Archaeological Potential (likely presence of buried remains within the cores of cities (e.g. Northern Ireland). Opinions also suggested that reserves are considered an obsolete category.

Assuming development is going ahead, do you balance the competing values of the archaeology against other values (economic or social, for example) of the proposed development in considering the scale of any investigation? If so, how? (A further explanation helped to interpret the question: whether cost/benefit is weighed when considering archaeological activity – Referring to Article 5 of the Valletta Convention)

The majority of answers indicated that the proposed use of the development is not taken into account. Those countries that were concerned about other values mentioned the following aspects: building owner's ability (reasonability), social value of the development / if the planning activity is important for the general public. There were some countries where all relevant factors are considered, decisions are made on the balance between them (UK), or they assess the value for society of the planned development in relation to the significance of the archaeological site and they also consider any hindrance or inconvenience that is disproportionate to the site's significance (Sweden).

In what ways are the public involved in the decision-making process when a site is proposed for investment/redevelopment? (A further explanation helped to interpret the question: in which the scale (note, article in journal, major text) and nature (online, hard copy, etc) of publication of the results is decided – Referring to Article 5 of the Valletta Convention and Article 5,12 of the Faro Convention)

In the 2017 survey responses, there are no relevant examples of the public being able to formulate an opinion on archaeological intervention. The process of Environmental Impact Assessments (EIAs) do

provide a field where engagement is possible, and in many countries both territorial plans and planning proposals are public, or the public can raise issues in relation to proposed development including heritage-related. All this suggests that the public's opinion on the importance/significance of sites was not a factor in decision-making systems when the survey was taken. However, the EAC does consider that some change has happened since the 2017 – and indeed the 2019 – survey was undertaken. In particular, with the adoption of the Faro Convention, a larger role for the general public can be foreseen in future, so this is a developing situation.

Conclusions

The survey found that EAC member countries have similar approaches to the basic concept of an archaeological site or monument, and selection in one form or another is a fundamental part of archaeological heritage management. Differences arise as to whether selection takes place at the point a site is identified or subsequently, in particular as regards level of protection assigned. No major differences were identified in site identification between countries (with considerable distinction in the chronological date). The selection of sites to be protected demonstrated different approaches (referring to automatic or enhanced level of protection - UNESCO WHS designation is a special sort), generally no mechanism can be found for ranking relative importance, only the categories and criteria for the different levels of protection could be observed. There was a clear desire and need for support to improve this position. Regarding the placing of sites in their (archaeological) context, the conclusion was that the assessment of significance of any archaeological site needs to encompass the full range of values associated with it.

State inventories of sites have taken divergent directions, and most states appear to assign relative significance in some form, but the mechanisms and criteria are not consistent or transparent. The assessment process is essentially subjective and more often than not includes some element of 'professional judgement'.

5.3 Unity in variety: the assessment of archaeological sites throughout Europe (the 2019 survey)

The Survey Questions

The 2019 survey contained 20 questions, in five parts. The first part sought to identify what EAC should spend its resources on creating. The second section requested information about the state's approach to significance – our assessment and this essay relies on the answers to these five questions. The third part of the survey gathered certain economic information about the scale and cost of development-led archaeology; the fourth some great examples of archaeology in action, and the fifth required general comments. Questions 2-6 were relevant for the subject of significance (of archaeological sites and complexes) and the way it is dealt with in each country. In total 20 countries responded to the survey.

Why do we define significance?

Reviewing the answers of the EAC member states to questions 2- 6, it became clear that the definition of significance may serve to achieve different objectives, for example:

- protecting (listing/ scheduling) sites
- preserving sites in situ (for example within the context of spatial planning developments)
- specifying the extent of archaeological intervention to be carried out, primarily in development-led archaeology, but also in research projects (including restoration, reconstruction, presentation)
- elaborating evidence-based methodology

Analysis of the answers

Question 2 focused on the methods applied when assessing significance of archaeological sites, questions 3-5 on the possible influencing factors like intangible values, changing perceptions of archaeological heritage, significance assessments of different types of archaeological remains, significance assessment of different archaeological periods, the landscape or well-being approach and the last one, question 6, intended to explore the legislative background in each country. Assessing significance or value of heritage, not only archaeological heritage but heritage in general is

period-, region-, country-, epoch- and society specific. So the assessment of significance is not a constant, although in general one might argue that within a broad bandwidth heritage in its different forms and shapes is generally regarded as important/ significant for a country, region and its inhabitants.

Due to the way archaeology is organized and has developed in each country and the way heritage management is implemented and practiced the survey revealed significant differences between responses. However, when looked at more closely there was also unity in variation and diversity. The unity was formed by the fact that all respondents stated that the protection/ listing of significant archaeological heritage is consolidated in State law or regulations, which in several countries is based or derived from the Valletta Convention, which has undoubtedly provided a positive impact on how archaeological heritage is regarded and how it can be safeguarded in the context of spatial planning developments. In other countries, heritage laws and regulations were already in place before the Valletta Convention and have a much longer history.

The diversity is shown in the manner in which each country operationalizes the aims of their own laws and regulations and the prospects of the Valletta Convention. In the text below the results for each question are summarized. For the sake of clarity the question will be presented followed by a summary and reflection on the answers given. Due to the fact that there was so much variety, the results are described qualitatively, not quantitatively.

In your state, when deciding on the significance of archaeological sites, do you have any official methods or guidelines, other than specifications included in state law, in use by heritage managers?

(We are trying to collect information on all the guidance or methodologies currently in use to establish how significant any archaeological site may be. We are aware that some states assume equal significance for all sites but that approach is not universal)

Another question in the survey asked about the existence of legislation requiring investigation as part of development. It showed that in most countries, national legislation is in place which is based around the premise that archaeological monuments are an important part of a country's past and should be taken care of. Developments which might damage this heritage are subject to legislation which both has regulation on the way the research should be done and who is responsible for the costs of the research (whether this is state funded or has to be paid by the developer).

Following on from that, this question in the survey indicated that in Europe different methods of deciding on the significance of archaeological sites exist and that combinations of official guidelines and use of expert groups (scientific committees) occur. Furthermore, in some countries national 'lists' of significant archaeological sites are used. In general, the following patterns or ways to operationalize 'the assessment of significance' can be discerned:

- involvement of the professional / scientific committees. In several countries specialist committees or archaeological professionals have an important role in the significance assessment of sites and the deciding whether sites are legally protected. In Lithuania, a Scientific Archaeological Commission is at work, which consists of scientist archaeologists and experts of heritage management. In the Netherlands assessment of sites should be done by professional archaeologists.
- using official (professional) guidelines/guidance or officially accepted evaluation methods. These might be embedded in national strategies or other policy documents (such as: Platform for Cultural Historical Assessment and Prioritisation; Conservation Principles) or research frameworks and agendas (value assessment using recognised criteria to assess significance). In general, these guidelines have in common that they have been developed by professional archaeologists (experts) and that in these guidelines different criteria are mentioned which have to be looked at when assessing the significance of a site. Criteria include: aesthetic/social value, physical value and scientific value; rarity, group value, historical associations. Several respondents stated that in their countries guidelines are used when assessing sites, however

it is not always clear from the answers whether the use of those guidelines is mandatory and which criteria are used. However, one might be inclined to reason that whenever guidelines are present and established that these in general will be used when assessing significance. The answers from the respondents from, for example, the Netherlands, Ireland, UK (England) and Sweden show that the guidelines in those countries are in general used when assessing significance. Several of the guidelines are based on international guidelines from ICOMOS or from well-established national heritage organisation like Historic England. Those types of guidelines have a high stature and are likewise used by heritage professionals. On the other hand it is notable that some respondents state that in their countries no 'official' guidelines are available, potentially resulting in more 'subjective' choices when it comes to the assessment of significance.

- definition by law: - either at the national legislative level, or in subordinate legislation. The definition can be chronological, or ipso jure: those sites are significant which are protected. Sometimes a chronological criterium is used, as described in the 2017 survey (see previous section). In Iceland all archaeological sites are deemed significant. Other countries do not have a chronological criterium but state that every site which is legally protected is significant. In Israel for example no explicit criteria are named in State law, however the law describes that "The Director (of the Israel Antiquities Authority) may declare a particular place to be an antiquity site." In Czechia the listing and adding of new monuments to the heritage list is done by the Ministry of Culture. In Ireland, the location of a site makes a difference: "there is a broad band grading between monuments of ordinary significance and those which are in the State's ownership or guardianship and the preservation of which is a matter of national significance by virtue of their historical, architectural, traditional, artistic or archaeological interest or values This latter group also contains monuments in private ownership but which are of national significance and which are under immediate threat. The latter are defined in State law."

- case by case evaluation, consideration and decision (on different levels e.g. heritage offices or officers) based on the scientific knowledge/historical value of the site – often within the frame of the planning process. Further considerations can be possibility for dissemination or experience (not the value and possible benefits of the actual development). The choice for preservation in situ can be based on the various criteria, including the characteristics of monuments, or on amenity value, beauty or remembrance value.
- using previously compiled lists /registers / inventories (urban and regional plans) e.g. list of nationally significant sites, Listing can be based on e.g. the archaeological / cultural / historical significance; aesthetic value; research/scientific value; preservation status (quality); rarity on regional/national level; landscape value.

Summing up the results, the assessment of significance and decision to protect can be based on different criteria but in general the following are in some way or other used in the different countries:

- archaeological/historical/cultural significance
- aesthetic value
- research/scientific value
- preservation status (quality of the archaeological remains)
- rarity on regional/national level and
- landscape/context value

In some countries, for example in Estonia and Iceland, values like symbolic value and accessibility are dealt with as well. In Luxembourg the physical presence such as architectural remains from buildings and other standing remains are also used in significance assessments. One could argue that these characteristics in other countries are classified under the criterium of visibility. In the Netherlands visibility is one of the criteria which has to be reckoned with although, due to the fact that in the Netherlands the majority of archaeological remains are invisible (i.e. below the surface), all 'visible' archaeological remains (like megaliths, burial mounds, terps and some more recent structural remains) are essentially 'worth preserving' and in that way are significant and should be kept in situ. Some countries, for example Estonia

and Iceland use a 'checklist of values' to consider sites and monuments against when assessing significance (see Section 6).

There are some differences in detail between countries. This is logical due to the fact that each country has its own (political) development and way how heritage management is implemented throughout past decades. Based on the answers provided in the survey, no ideal method of assessing significance can be outlined. However the different answers do provide an array of possibilities one can or might use when one wants to assess significance, and this document takes the approach of providing the solutions developed in different countries as inspiration or as best practice examples.

In your state, does change in social circumstances, beliefs, opinions and fashions through time effect on how significance of archaeological sites is evaluated?

(We are trying to understand whether the significance of a site is a "constant" that is the same at all times, or does it change through time? Something that was considered of great significance in the C19th may today be (for some reason) considered of lesser importance. We are aware that this may be sensitive because this touches on how politics can sometimes affect the evaluation of significance of sites, but believe it is very important to consider this.)

The responses of all countries show that significance is logically not perceived as a constant. Ideas about heritage management and scientific questions change in the course of time. Sometimes this is due to major developments in countries, at other times due to gradual changes in the attitude towards archaeology or heritage in general. It is country specific which change occurs and at what pace, linked to societal and governmental change and the development of topics which are in fashion or not. In some countries archaeology, but also history have been used both positively and negatively in the course of nation building and culture politics. In recent years archaeological periods which have received little attention in the past have gained more interest whether due to growing public engagement or to more diverse and inclusive practice. For example, in Iceland but also in the Norway and Poland, archaeological heritage of minorities or indigenous peoples has received more interest in recent years. Physical

evidence of major events from the 20th century, such as both World Wars, is now generally regarded as relevant archaeological heritage, which would not have been the case decades ago.

In former 'communist' countries a clear change is seen before and after the 'cold war'. In general, an increasing focus on archaeology of more recent periods can be seen, and in some countries archaeology has been used or is used in 'branding' or nation building and this can change how that archaeology is viewed. Despite an underlying principle that significance focusses on sites with high appeal to the (general?) public, tourism and 'outreach' can influence the exact nature of this, and there remains wide variety between the different countries.

From the answers it is also clear that, in 2019, assessing significance was clearly still a task of professionals or experts (people with thorough knowledge of the subject) and that in general it was done by or in consultancy with the competent authorities on national or regional level. However, as previously noted, the EAC considers the engagement of other stakeholder groups in the process of evaluating significance to be an area of development, and a change can be seen. More and more the public or different stakeholder groups within society claim in a positive way to be a part the discourse in which is decided which heritage is relevant and significant.

This trend is in line with the principles of the Faro Convention, as well as with other societal and even mondial developments. This is an interesting development which is new and perhaps sometimes feels threatening because existing paradigms and 'ways of doing' are being questioned and tested. This change is clearly illustrated by one of the survey responses which shows that significance is not a constant, and likely never will be: "Significance is significance to people: people change". So inevitably also significance and which type of archaeology or heritage is perceived as relevant or important will always be subject to change, however this does not mean that, in general, parts of archaeology or heritage will lose their significance, the range of different types of archaeological monuments which are perceived as significant will expand.

In your state, how is the context of monuments and / or sites taken into account when evaluating the significance of archaeological areas? Do you systematically evaluate the significance of archaeological complexes or landscape? If so how?

(In asking this, we recognise that a single monument may not have much value in itself, but placed in context of other monuments or sites it may gain great value, as a part of an archaeological complex, archaeological area or landscape)

The answers to this question were variable: in some countries both context and the surrounding landscape and environment characteristics are taken into account when assessing significance of an archaeological site. The ambiguous phrasing of the question means that some respondents clearly described context as 'archaeological context' whereas other respondents also addressed context as the wider landscape around the site/monument. And of course combinations exist, for example in the guidelines used in the Netherlands where the ensemble of a monument is both defined by similar or dissimilar archaeological monuments in the vicinity as by the landscape or environment surrounding the site. Context or the surrounding area of a site is not always strictly addressed in the guidelines or methods used in significance assessment, but there are examples that individual heritage managers take the surroundings of an archaeological site into account. In several countries archaeological monuments are strictly viewed as an archaeologically defined area – i.e. an area in which archaeological remains are undoubtedly present – and accompanying or surrounding areas cannot be integrated in the monument legally, due to the fact that in those areas no archaeological remains are present.

The Valletta Convention did not include the possibility of interpretation at the landscape level, which might be a reason for the rigid approach of some countries. In practical terms, when one wants to list an area as an archaeological monument because of the presence of archaeological remains throughout or spread over a landscape feature, this monument claims a large surface. The listing of a site or area in which archaeological remains are present always imposes obligations or prohibitions on owners and developers, and the larger the area, the greater the impact. An evaluation has to be made whether the listing of an archaeological monument can be substantiated enough in light of the rights and interests of other

involved stakeholders. Especially in countries which are densely populated, archaeologically-valid claims on larger pieces of land do not always match with other societal claims. Only in a few countries (e.g. Czechia, Israel) is it possible to protect larger areas or archaeological reserves, for example when sites are located in nature reserves, a similar practice can be seen in the Netherlands. Sometimes, for example in Iceland, the presence of archaeological remains in the vicinity is given extra value instead when a monument is in isolation. But in general, be it in guidelines or more ad hoc, the 'context' of a site is a relevant factor. However, it should be noted that especially in spatial planning the assessment and or accompanying research is limited to the footprint of the specific spatial planning project at hand, in these circumstances it is very difficult to take into account the wider context, which extends beyond the area which is the focus of the spatial plans.

How does your state see the connection between public wellbeing and the significance of archaeological sites?

(The importance of archaeological sites to the common human story and to the cultural development of humanity is clear. However, archaeological monuments are important to local communities and to people visiting them and participating in their investigation. We would like to understand whether archaeological heritage managers gather any information or data on this aspect of significance and public value.)

It is a relatively new development in archaeology and heritage management that monuments have a role in the public wellbeing. Of course there exists a robust tourist industry focussed on national or international heritage and in general the public appreciates heritage as an asset of a country or region, but this is mainly centred on a few 'top monuments'. The potential influence that monuments or the research of archaeological remains can have on public wellbeing more widely is an interesting development in sociological and societal research, but in classic heritage management it seems a new but growing subject. The influence of the Faro Convention is increasing, but it is difficult to translate its principles into the everyday work of assessing significance. Data on this subject is hard to find. Data is collected in various ways, sometimes nationally (e.g. UK England [Darvill et al 2019], Lithuania, Poland, Finland), or by

local museums (Denmark), however in the majority of the countries in the survey this data is not available. Furthermore initiatives are starting to enlarge the involvement of the general public in archaeology (the Netherlands), data on these initiatives has only recently become available and is more in the form of experiences with individual projects than quantitative data. In general, the 'actual' involvement of the general public is in its infancy, notwithstanding good and powerful examples. However, a growing interest in the cooperation between archaeology as a scientific and heritage management discipline and its valuation by the public is noticeable. One of the main concerns, mentioned by several respondents and which is regularly mentioned in reviews of this subject, is the short-term nature of the resources available to support this work: there seem to be no sustainable long-term initiatives. However, this might change in future.

Conclusions

The survey of 2019 shows a wide variety of methods in dealing with significance within the countries which participated. This variety is however underpinned by key similarities. In all countries there is a clear operational model for dealing with significance of archaeological remains and with the management of archaeological monuments. Legislation on archaeological heritage management has different origins but generally the principles of the Valletta Convention play a role in some way. Significance is not a constant and in particular, at the time of this publication, the relationship of groups and stakeholders (who are not heritage professionals) to archaeological heritage in general, and their involvement in the assessment of significance specifically, is changing. What the future will bring is of course unclear, but that the intentions of the Faro Convention will play a role is a certainty. At this moment everyone interested should cherish the unity in diversity and hopefully inspiration is provided by the varied ways in which different countries within the EAC community deal with significance. Hopefully 'ways of doing' and 'best practices' of other countries can be used in one form or the other within one's own significance assessments.

SECTION 6

Methods for evaluating significance – Examples of Systems¹⁸

6.1 Austria

Andreas Picker, René Ployer

Introduction

Institution responsible for heritage protection

Federal Monuments Authority Austria

Short description of the legal system

On 31 December 1850, Emperor Franz Joseph I signed the decree for the establishment of the „k.k. Central-Commission zur Erforschung und Erhaltung der Baudenkmale“ (Imperial and Royal Central-Commission for the Research and Preservation of Architectural Monuments). This was the first professionally competent monument preservation organisation in the Austrian monarchy, however without authority status or legal basis. The commission began its work in 1853, its competencies were significantly expanded in 1873, and from that year on, the institution also had its own budget.

After a reorganisation of the Central-Commission in 1911, a State Monuments Office, a Monuments Council and an Institute of Art History, were established. For each crown land, State Conservators were introduced – institutions that still exist today. Due to the resistance of the church and the nobility, however, it was not possible to pass a monument protection law.

At the beginning of the First Republic, after World War One, the State Monuments Office was given its first legal authority: in December 1918, the so-called Export Prohibition Act (Ausfuhrverbotsgesetz, StGBI. 90/1918) was passed which regulated the export of art objects from Austria and was intended to avoid an extreme sell-off of cultural goods from the struggling country. The original federal law from 1923 on the protection of monuments due to their historical, artistic or other cultural significance (Monument Protection Act – Denkmalschutzgesetz, BGBl. 533/1923) is intended to protect monuments from destruction or alteration and to prevent the unlawful transfer of protected cultural assets abroad. Amendments were made in

1959 with regard to the enforcement of monument protection and in 1965 with regard to the definition of monuments (decision of the Constitutional Court). In 1978 there was a first comprehensive amendment to the monument law, another in 1990. The Export Prohibition Act was amended in 1999 when it was merged with the Monument Protection Act. The last comprehensive amendment to the law came into force on 1 September 2024.

Significance of archaeological sites

Criteria

Which criteria must an archaeological monument meet in order to be listed?

The Austrian law does not differentiate between monuments of built heritage or archaeological heritage. As opposed to a purely declaratory “listing” of monuments, the Austrian law also emphasizes the constitutive process of how cultural assets may become protected monuments (Section 3, Monument Protection Act). Not the monument’s significance alone, but the arguable public interest in its preservation constitutes the protection status legally. New additions to the monuments list must undergo an evaluation and assessment by expert opinion. Therefore, criteria are applied that can be summarized in two groups: the “significance criteria” (“Bedeutungskriterien”) and the “evaluation criteria” (“Beurteilungskriterien”).

Are international conventions taken into account or do they play a role (e.g. Faro)?

Austria has not ratified the Convention for the Protection of the Architectural Heritage of Europe (CoE, 1985). Until 2024, the Monuments Protection Act, former Section 1 (5), stated that “generally accepted international evaluation criteria” can be included in the assessments. However, the recent amendment has included further issues of “international responsibility” (Sections 12a and 13a).

¹⁸The text in this section was largely created in 2019-2020, and reflects the situation then unless specifically indicated otherwise.

Can a monument be delisted? (if so, what are the criteria and how is the process?)

Yes. Monuments that are listed and that have lost their significance for which they were placed under monument protection – due to accidents or unlawful destruction or alteration or for other reasons (such as a scientific re-evaluation) – shall continue to be protected until the Federal Monuments Authority has determined ex officio or by application that there is no longer any public interest in their preservation. Only then can they be delisted.

System(s) applied

Is there any official system for evaluating significance in use by heritage managers?

Yes. The approach of the Federal Monuments Authority is based on a strategy of protection. The basis for this is the nationwide monument inventories, in particular the compilation of objects in the Heritage Information System (HERIS database), which is kept as an internal working tool at the Federal Monuments Authority. Within the framework of an annual examination programme, priorities are set and groups of monuments are defined for further examination with regard to their monument characteristics. Parallel to the annual programmes, it is of course also possible that an object not yet included in the inspection programme may be assessed as to its monument status. In both cases, it is the task of the Federal Monuments Authority to determine the character of the monument and to carry out a review according to established criteria. This is done by means of expert opinions, which are generally written by official experts at the Federal Monuments Authority.

At the beginning, an inspection of the monument is carried out, the results of which – together with subsequent archival and literature research – form the scientific basis for the official expert's determination of whether and to what extent monument characteristics exist. The catalogue of criteria provides guidelines for identifying the particular features of the objects in the sense of a generally applicable standard for the evaluation.

How is the assessment done?

In the first step, the "significance criteria" are applied. They represent the monument values that may be connected to an object. If such monument values exist, the object basically possesses monument characteristics and stands out among others. For this purpose, the Monument Protection Act defines three groups of monument values, namely "historical, artistic or other cultural significance" (Section 1 (1) Monument Protection Act). These categories of significance (or "values" or "meaning" of the object) cover a wide variety of monuments. As a rule, the possible properties each have different shares in the overall meaning. The individuality of the object results from the combination of "significance criteria".

While the attribution of significance is a purely professional (or even "scientific") question, the legal issue of whether there is a public interest in the preservation of the monument must be resolved by application of the "evaluation criteria" in a second step. The necessary weighing of a monument's significance results from a reference or comparative framework; therefore, the criteria can also be referred to as "reference criteria". According to the Monument Protection Act, the decisive factor for this frame of reference is whether the monument contributes to Austria's cultural heritage in terms of quality as well as sufficient quantity, diversity and distribution (Section 1 (4) Monument Protection Act). In this context, the Monument Protection Act specifies a local, regional or supra-regional comparative framework. This results in the aspects of quality, rarity or representativeness. In addition, possible individual parameters may be applied, according to which a classification can be made that justifies the initiation of a protection procedure.

What are the criteria when assessing the value of a site?

The weighing of the evaluation criteria results in the justification of the public interest in preservation. The list of criteria is not exhaustive, but exemplary. The evaluation criteria must be formed on a case-by-case basis depending on the nature of the monument. The only (and very general) evaluation criteria given for this process are "quality, quantity, diversity and distribution".

Are there different levels of protection?

No. Since the term used in this context (“Bedeutung”) has less connotation of “value” but ranges closer to semantic “meaning”, the law in general does not differ between monuments of higher or lower significance. However, an attempt at compiling a list of archaeological monuments of highest significance has recently taken place (see table 2).

Public participation**Is the public involved in the process of protection?**

No. As a matter of principle, protection is granted by the authorities, i.e. the initiative comes from the Federal Monuments Authority. It follows the legal mandate for the protection of Austrian monuments. The legal basis for this is the Monument Protection Act.

Are there lists or plans of protected archaeological sites that are accessible to the public?

Pursuant to Section 3 (3) of the Monument Protection Act the Federal Monuments Authority publishes the [list of monuments under protection](#). The list is sorted by federal state, municipality and by address (alphabetically) or by cadastral municipality number. The list is updated on 1 January of each calendar year.

Involvement of owners and their rights**Do the owners have any influence on the selection of archaeological sites for protection?**

In general, the Federal Monuments Authority defines the annual programmes for protection assessments. However, the process may also be initiated by application from the owner of the monument.

Do they have any influence on the protection procedure?

At the beginning of a protection procedure, the Federal Monuments Authority informs the owners about the planned inspection of the object. If monument characteristics exist, the official expert’s report is sent to the owners as well as the legal parties (federal state governors, municipalities and mayors), on which they can usually comment within four weeks in the form of a statement to the Federal Monuments Authority. If the deadline has expired and no further investigations are necessary, the Federal Monuments Authority issues the decision. An appeal against this decision can be lodged with the Federal Administrative Court. As soon as the declaration of protection is legally binding, the protection of the monument is automatically made visible as additional information to the land register. No further legal consequences are associated with this.

Archaeological monuments in Austria: Significance, evaluation criteria and public interest in their preservation. A path to representative selection based on monument diversity

Aside from the legal framework of the protection process described above, more detailed assessment criteria have been explored recently based on (but also extending beyond) the wording of the Monuments Protection Act. Beginning in 2018, the Department of Archaeology of Austria’s Federal Monuments Authority has pursued a project to analyse which archaeological monuments stand out among their peers, and what criteria might be useful to define such “higher” significance. The result has been a list of one hundred highest-ranking archaeological monuments in Austria – not a static fixed list, but one that is based on both selection and structured

evaluation criteria as well as the reflection thereof (Hebert et al, 2019). Initially, this approach might have seemed unusual, due to the paradigmatic tradition in Austrian heritage management not to classify monuments in terms of rank. However, in the following passage we glimpse some hierarchization when the law speaks of significance “at least from a regional or local point of view” (Section 1 (4) Monument Protection Act). The only (and very general) evaluation criteria given for this process are “quality, quantity, diversity and distribution” (see above).

Only once, following Austria's signing of the Hague Convention (UNESCO, 1954), the attempt was undertaken at ranking benchmark archaeological monuments by the greatness of their significance. In 1968 the Department of Archaeology hastily drew up a list of archaeological sites of the highest international (category A), European (category B) and national-regional (category C) significance. This list was sent to experts at several state museums for review. Category A comprised the settlements, burial grounds and mining areas at Dürrnberg near Hallein (Salzburg), the Salzberg at Hallstatt (Upper Austria), the Celtic-Roman settlement of Magdalensberg (Carinthia) and the palaeolithic hunting stations in Willendorf (Lower Austria). Category B comprised 56 archaeological monuments from all nine Austrian federal states. No less than 216 were assigned to category C. It should be noted that the current Protection of Cultural Property list has only 135 entries in total, only one (!) of which (the Magdalensberg) can be classified as an archaeological site.

At its core, the assignment of significance to an (archaeological) monument by assessment is always an individual, subjective and hermeneutical process based especially on verbal description. The "significance project" has raised the question whether a more quantifying method could be developed and applied. Concepts such as the "evaluation matrix" are well known in the field of environmental impact assessments. In this way, would we be able to define significance with "quantifiable objectivity"? But can such rigid criteria even be applied to archaeological monuments? A working group within the Department of Archaeology set to the task of answering these questions.

The process of developing a list of highest-ranking archaeological monuments in Austria (a symbolic "top 100" was the aim but not a requirement) began with the establishment of a sufficient sample of sites from each of the nine federal states. This part of the process was left entirely to the judgment of the regional supervisors in charge of each state. The resulting preliminary lists were more or less spontaneous products based on individual knowledge and experience. What might

seem like a break in the attempt to apply a more quantifying method to the evaluation process was mainly due to practical limitations. A systematic evaluation of thousands of archaeological sites from the Federal Monuments Authority's database, for example, seemed impossible for the time being. Therefore, a certain amount of trust was given to individual judgement coming from a group of experts. Also, some archaeological monuments appear so significant (even in the public opinion) that they seem above any systematic evaluation and may simply be "acclaimed" as high-ranking. This phenomenon certainly had some effect on the ranking process.

The search for applicable significance criteria must not focus on the (few and rather vague) indications of national legislation alone. The distinction between "ordinary" and "extraordinary" cultural assets is of key importance to the UNESCO World Heritage Convention, for example. The working group quickly found that the universal concepts of integrity and authenticity (though rather abstract and not above criticism) are quite suitable for measuring the significance of higher-level archaeological monuments in Austria. Especially the concept of integrity – simply understood as the "amount" of remaining original archaeological substance – represents a measurable value to some extent. Authenticity concerning archaeological monuments accounts for "the ability of the archaeological remains to truthfully convey their meaning".

It goes without saying that physical characteristics only make up a part of a monument's significance. An object's appreciation by the scientific community as well as by society in general should (as a sort of meta level) also account for as much as half of the "quantity" of significance. Scientific significance also comprises aspects of research history as well as potential for future research. Lastly, the fourth overall criterion regards social relevance, impact and perceptibility. It reminds us of the public mandate that all these considerations are based on and also corresponds to the Faro Convention. While the awareness of a monument's "social relevance" dates back to Alois Riegl's "present values" ("Gegenwartswerte") (Riegl,

1903), it has been argued more recently that the visualization of archaeological findings through excavation or prospection is in itself a form of aesthetic perception.

In order to evaluate the preliminary “state lists” a tabular scheme was created and a questionnaire provided. Regarding each archaeological site (i.e. monument) specific questions had to be answered

in accordance with the four overall criteria (Table 2). In order to obtain some form of numerical weighting, a three-point scale was used. The posed questions could be answered with “most applicable”, “partially applicable” or “least/not applicable” (equalling 3, 2 and 1 points).

Integrity
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Has the site been only partially (not completely) excavated in relation to its entirety? • Has the majority of the site been substantially preserved? • Are natural or man-made processes of decay or other negative effects under control? • Does the site qualify as a true “archaeological reserve”? • If any restoration or enhancement of the site has taken place, is it of such great importance (historically or socially) that it outweighs the loss of some original substance?
Authenticity
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is it possible to gain knowledge of the site at a high scientific level with only a relatively small invasive intervention? • Is the quality of the material and substance outstanding (also in terms of craftsmanship or artistry)? • Is the site entirely unique or singular within the region? • Is the site a particularly good example of a type or variant of monument?
Potential/Perspective
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is the site of exceptional importance for the history of research? • Is the site of particular importance for future research (“archive in the ground”)? • Is the site multi-phase or multicultural? • Is the site a special testimony to continuity or cultural transfer? • Does the site belong to a type of monument that is little known or has hardly been studied by research in the past (e.g. infrastructure, mining etc.)?
Social impact/Perception
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is the site visible (above ground)? • Is the site perceptible and comprehensible as a physical object in the landscape? • Is the site known to a broader, at least regional, public (e.g. through a long history of reception, school teaching etc.)? • Is the site of national or international importance? • Does the site have a high identification value?

Table 2: the four overall assessment criteria

The results of this first evaluation show the significance of the respective objects relative to other objects in the state. Certain peaks (both high and low) are evident, but also a broad midfield of sites that seem to be of similar significance. The rather broad division of criteria on the questionnaire as well as the rather narrow preselection lead to the fact that the majority of the objects were weighted similarly. In any case, it became quite clear which sites would become “top 100” monuments, while about one third had to be subjected to further discussion. Although designed as a kind of checklist, this evaluation never intended to generate an automated list of high-ranking archaeological monuments. Quite in the tradition of Alois Riegl, a broad catalogue of values should be up for discussion when assigning monument significance. Any representative selection must be based on monument diversity.

The current list of the “100 most significant archaeological monuments in Austria” is, of course, one of many possible lists (Fig.3). In the end, it

was nearly impossible to scale the ranking list based on actual numerical values. The application of statistical methods runs into difficulties due to lack of homogenous data when dealing with archaeological sites. Even the Federal Monuments Authority’s database with tens of thousands of datasets collected over a longer period of time by different people does not present a sufficiently structured sample for assigning “numerical” significance.

The project has successfully shown how an empirical survey among experts must address the same structured representative issues to a greater number of monuments. In this sense the list of high-ranking archaeological monuments originated from a qualitative analysis employing some quantifiable data from yes-no (and neutral) questions. Furthermore, for the first time in half a century the (high) level of significance was assigned to archaeological sites not by a one-person assessment but by an empirically structured team process.

Figure 3: Archaeological monuments of highest significance across Austria. (Austrian Federal Monuments Authority)

6.2 Estonia

Ulla Kadakas, Anu Lillak

Introduction

Institution responsible for heritage protection

The National Heritage Board (NHB) under the Ministry of Culture is responsible for the management of heritage in Estonia. It employs around 70 people, 9 of whom work directly with archaeological heritage. Day-to-day heritage protection decisions are taken by the NHB by reviewing and approving projects based on the [Heritage Conservation Act](#) (HCA) and its sub-acts. In the three larger cities (Tallinn, Tartu and Narva), the same state obligations are carried out by the municipalities themselves based on administrative contracts. All of them have heritage specialists on their staff, but only Tallinn has a designated archaeologist dealing only with archaeology, the other two cities have specialists whose job description includes managing archaeology among other tasks.

Short description of the legal system

In the 17th century, Estonia was part of Sweden, where in 1666 the king issued a law to protect its monuments. Between 1710/1721 and 1918, Estonia was part of the Russian Tsardom, where Tsarist laws were in force. The implementation of these early regulations, i.e. their real impact on the preservation of monuments, has been assessed as rather limited.

The establishment of the Republic of Estonia also brought its own legislation. The first law on the protection of antiquities was adopted in 1925. Estonia lost its independence in World War Two, and the Soviet occupation, which lasted until 1991, began. In 1961, the Estonian SSR adopted one of the first laws on the protection of antiquities in the USSR; a supra-Union law adopted in 1977 also applied to Estonia (Fig.4).

After the restoration of the Republic of Estonia, a new HCA was adopted in 1994, based on the pre-war Act and the principles of the 1992 Valletta Convention, but also considering changes during the Soviet period. The HCA was substantially renewed or amended in 2002, 2011 and most recently in 2019. The HCA is understandably related to other acts (i.e. Planning Act, Environmental Impact Assessment and Environmental Management System Act, the Building Code, the Law of Property Act), and in relation to them it is mostly a special act, i.e. a specifying act.

While in all the previous HCAs, the cultural objects deserving protection were described by means of lists, the 2019 HCA provides a general definition in the manner of the Valletta Convention, the criteria for assessing protection and the lists have been moved to a sub-act. The decision to designate a heritage site as a monument or a heritage protection area is taken by the Minister of Culture after proceedings of designation carried out by the Department. This involves presenting the expert assessment of the heritage values to the landowners and the local authority, listening to the views of the parties involved, and showing how efforts have been made to take account of the views of all parties. The decision to designate a protected archaeological site (has slightly less restrictions than a monument) will be taken by the Director-General of the NHB after a similar proceeding.

The current listing procedure considers the rights of all parties involved but is also very labour and time intensive. The bottleneck of the system is that a large part of the archaeological heritage identified does not end up in the national register, which means that these not-yet listed sites cannot be considered in planning, nor can they be excluded from the list of search areas for hobby detectorists (Fig.5).

Significance of archaeological sites

Criteria

Which criteria must an archaeological monument meet in order to be listed?

The HCA first lays down the prerequisite for placement under state protection (§10), according to which “an object or an area of cultural value must represent the most valuable part tangible cultural heritage of Estonia, which has scientific, historical, artistic or other cultural value, or the preservation duty of which arises from an international agreement.”

The HCA defines an archaeological monument as follows (§ 11-3): “An archaeological monument is the remains, thing or set of things of human activity and other traces which indicate the multiple layers of time on a cultural landscape, and which provide scientific information on the history of mankind and human relations with the natural environment. An archaeological layer is an important part of an archaeological monument.”

The law also describes what an archaeological cultural layer is (§ 6): “An archaeological layer means a deposition accumulated as a result of direct human activity or human impact, which may include the remains of construction, wrecks, human and animal bones, archaeological finds, including tools and utility articles, remains or production and similar.”

In addition to designation as a monument, it is also possible to designate an area of archaeological value as a protected archaeological site (§ 25): “A protected archaeological site is an area or land or water, where archaeological finds, human bones, remains of historical building structures or other elements referring to an archaeological layer have been found and which may still contain such elements.”

It is clear from the above definitions that there is no legal age criterion for archaeological heritage. In the context of the Intra-Community Transport, Export and Import of Cultural Objects Act, archaeological finds, coin hoards and their parts dating from before 1721 are described as valuable in the context of this Act. This does not mean, however, that later artifacts or objects may not have a prerequisite for state protection as archaeological heritage.

Are international conventions taken into account or do they play a role (e.g. Faro)?

The 2019 HCA is based on the definition of archaeological heritage in the Valletta Convention. The procedure for designation is based on the primacy of private ownership of land as a constitutionally protected value. A high degree of discretion has been imposed on heritage officials in their decision-making, a reference to the Faro Convention. Estonia signed the Faro Convention in 2021, after the last renewal of the law and even though some ideas from Faro were already existing during the law-making procedure, the current law does not yet take into account many of the Faro principles.

Can a monument be delisted? (if so, what are the criteria and how is the process?)

The HCA also provides for the possibility of alteration or revocation of the designation as a monument (§ 20). In the case of archaeological monuments, this may be due to non-compliance with the prerequisites for state protection (for example, an object previously thought to be a stone burial mound, on closer examination, turns out to be a natural deposit of rock); it may also

Figure 4: Distribution map of archaeological monuments by date of first protection. (National Heritage Board of Estonia)

be destroyed (for example, by landslides and other collapses, or as a result of an intentional act); the Act also provides for the possibility of terminating the status of a monument, mostly in the case of objects placed under protection many years ago, if the object cannot be found in the landscape and there are reasonable grounds to believe that the monument has not preserved.

System(s) applied

Is there any official system for evaluating significance in use by heritage managers?

A sub-act of the HCA is the Regulation of the Minister of Culture, which establishes the general criteria for assessing the prerequisites of national protection for types of monuments. For all types of monuments, it is necessary to assess the preservation of the original substance, the technical condition and the selectivity. The latter implies that, in the presence of many objects or sites of the same type, more representative, better preserved and of cumulative value are protected. In the case of archaeological heritage, this criterion is generally not relevant, as even monuments of the same type (e.g. stone burial mounds) are always unique in nature and there are no specific guidelines to assess

the value of archaeological heritage. The value of the site is defined for each object (or group of objects) separately.

A thing or a site may meet several criteria but need not meet all of them. Criteria may have different weightings.

How is the assessment done?

There are currently around 6750 archaeological monuments under state protection in Estonia. Over the past 20 years, at least 1500 additional sites have been discovered by archaeologists and detectorists, but due to the shortage of manpower in the NHB, new proceedings for designations are essentially only initiated on a needs basis if a site is threatened (Fig.5).

For each archaeological site, a criteria assessment must be prepared. Criteria are assessed by a specialist, who may or may not be an employee of the NHB. The expert assessment is reviewed by the NHB procedural committee, if necessary, hearing the opinion of the expert advisory council for the type of monument. The committee decides whether to initiate the commencement of proceedings for designation of monuments.

Figure 5: Number of archaeological sites discovered in Estonia between 2002 and 2022 vs. number of monuments listed during the same period. (National Heritage Board of Estonia)

What are the criteria when assessing the value of a site?

Criteria for assessing the prerequisites for state protection of archaeological monuments are:

- (1) Age and location - the location of an object originating from the prehistoric, medieval and/or modern period which indicate the multiple layers of time on a cultural landscape;
- (2) The scientific value and unique nature of the information – the monument consists of an archaeological cultural layer (including building structures and their remnants) or natural objects or deposits containing archaeological finds (including human bones) and other scientific information that cannot be obtained from other sources. The objects have an important role in researching, understanding, and interpreting the past;
- (3) Notability and unique nature – the site is notable on the landscape or has very expressive typical characteristic features of the specific monument type. The site may have associated place-lore or can be seen as a notable landscape feature with wider public or communal value;
- (4) Function continuity – the initial and modern function of the site are the same;
- (5) Reflection in written sources and educational value – the site that has written historical place-lore or other written sources or historic maps that have been analysed with source criticism; also, fully or mostly excavated site that has been fully or partially scientifically reconstructed;
- (6) Imperishability – it is preferred to preserve the site or object in its original location;
- (7) Partially or fully submerged site (underwater monument) that emphasises the preservation conditions and the unique experience of underwater environment (sunken water, air and other vehicles with their cargo; submerged dwelling and burial site etc.).

Are there different levels of protection?

In Estonia, a site of archaeological value can be designated either as an archaeological monument or as a protected archaeological site. In the case of the former, the aim of protection is to preserve the site as it has been found and as intact as possible in a changing landscape. In the case of a protected archaeological

site, the aim is to ensure that archaeological information can be retrieved from the site - if an irreversible change to the landscape is desired (building, excavation, etc.), archaeological investigation must be ensured, but further preservation of the site is not mandatory.

Public participation**Is the public involved in the process of protection?**

The law obliges NHB to listen to the views of the various parties and take them into account as much as possible in the proceedings for designation of monuments, and when projects are being coordinated. The general public is only involved in the proceedings for designation of large areas of land where the number of landowners involved exceeds 100. The heritage protection system in Estonia can be described as a top-down management system and not much public discussion about the community value or definition of archaeological sites has taken place.

Are there lists or plans of protected archaeological sites that are accessible to the public?

In Estonia, all listed monuments are in the publicly accessible [register of cultural monuments](#) and also in the [Geoportal of the Land Board](#). However, given the resource-intensive nature of the designation process for state protection, there are a great many archaeological sites that are known but not on the register. As such sites are not directly protected by law, the policy of the NHB, based on the opinion of expert organisations in the field, is not to publish the information about the sites. However, to ensure that the already known archaeological heritage can still be taken into account in planning, the NHB has provided information on archaeological sensitive areas for local authority master plans – these are not precise details of known sites, but broad areas that include these. The master plans are public and available online.

Owners of monuments and protected archaeological sites can apply to the state for compensation to a certain extent for archaeological research, but there is no such compensation for sites that are not listed. In any case, if the NHB finds that there are grounds for designating an unprotected area for archaeological survey, the focus area must be placed under temporary state protection.

Involvement of owners and their rights***Do the owners have any influence on the selection of archaeological sites for protection?***

In Estonia, the owners certainly have influence in the designation process whether they want the monument or not, but they cannot directly affect the criteria assessment, which is done by a specialist expert. In the case of archaeological heritage, the boundaries of the site must be defined and the possible scientific informativeness of the site must be decided based on limited data, which often makes non-specialists keen to call for further research. There is therefore often intensive correspondence during the proceeding for designation of monuments, usually with lawyers representing the owners. These discussions reveal the difficulty of understanding each other between specialists and non-specialists, because archaeological information is not understood in the same way.

Do they have any influence on the protection procedure?

Owners have the right to express their views on the conservation measures to be applied when the object is listed. All proposals must be considered and where mitigation is possible, it will be implemented. For example, in the case of archaeological monuments, mitigation may be possible in conditions of clearance; where a site is covered by thick layers of later fill, excavation to a certain depth without archaeological investigation may also be allowed.

6.3 Finland

Teija Tiitinen

Introduction

Institution responsible for heritage protection

The Finnish Heritage Agency together with the museums with regional responsibility are accountable for the protection of archaeological cultural heritage in Finland. The Finnish Heritage Agency is a key expert authority on the cultural environment in state administration. Its operations are steered by the Antiquities Act, the Land Use and Building Act, the Act for the Protection of Built Heritage, the Church Act, and the Act on the Orthodox Church. The Cultural Environment Services department is a national developer and influencer in its field. Producing data and providing insight on the values, usage and protection of cultural heritage is one of the main tasks of the Finnish Heritage Agency.

Museums with regional responsibility carry out cultural environment work as well. Most land use tasks related to cultural environment (land-use planning, permits based on the Land Use and Building Act) are managed by museums with regional responsibility.

The identification of an ancient site is based on the evaluation made by the field investigator. However, the final decision on a site's protection must be carried out by the Finnish Heritage Agency or a museum with regional responsibility that participates in the ancient sites' protection. The implementation of the protection

is, however, not in force until either of these organisations has included it in the National Register of Ancient Relics. The register does not have official status determined by the act now, but it is used as such. However, the law is now under reform and in the future, the register will be stated in it. The Ancient Register of Ancient Relics is available to everyone via the Kulttuuriympäristön palveluikkuna ('Cultural environment service window', in Finnish) managed by the Finnish Heritage Agency.

Short description of the legal system

The oldest directives concerning antiquities in Sweden were given in 1666 (Finland was part of Sweden till 1809), when prehistoric sites and other antiquarian monuments were declared to be under the protection of the Crown (Fig.6). Finland became a relatively independent part of Russia in 1809. At the same time, the interest in nature and heritage began to grow all over Europe and Finland followed the mainstream. The Finnish Antiquarian Society was formed in 1870 and in 1883, the regulation on protecting ancient sites was solidified. The regulation was largely like the Swedish Antiquities Act at the time. However, it was somewhat weaker than the Swedish one because in practice ancient remains were protected only if the landowner was willing to protect the site or if the State was willing to redeem the land. In 1917 Finland became independent, but the regulation was in force till 1963, when Finland's current antiquities act was passed.

Figure 6: Timeline of the history of the heritage protection in Finland. (Finnish Heritage Agency)

All the archaeological sites in Finland are automatically protected by the Antiquities Act of 1963. No specific decision to protect ancient remains is needed. According to the law, a site is protected immediately after its discovery. It is like that in theory, in practice it is not as simple as that.

The law protects all the ancient sites and monuments but, the same law also states that if the ancient site creates significant difficulties in proportion to its value, a permit to disturb an ancient remain may be issued. However, the law does not give any tools to the evaluation of the remains' value, despite the fact that museum authorities have to evaluate the significance of the remains when different kinds of land-use plans are done everywhere in Finland.

Significance of archaeological sites

Criteria

Which criteria must an archaeological monument meet in order to be listed?

The protection of an ancient site is based on the available information about the site's age, type, and its preservation. Ancient sites do not have a specific age limit. Stray finds are considered ancient remains if they are older than 100 years and the owner is unknown. The same goes for underwater objects. The Act covers both prehistoric and historical sites. The youngest items on the protection list are the defense structures from World War One. The decisions about 19th and 20th century sites, whether they are protected or not, are usually made on a case-by-case basis.

Are international conventions taken into account or do they play a role (e.g. Faro)?

Finland ratified the Valletta Convention in 1995, the Faro Convention in 2017 and the Hague Convention in 1994. A tentative list of Hague sites has been published but has not been published as the process is still ongoing. Finland ratified the World Heritage Convention in 1987. The first and still the only archaeological site designated as Finland's World Heritage Site is the Bronze Age burial site in Sammallahdenmäki, Satakunta Province. All ratified conventions must always be considered when decisions are made, but in practice they are only behind the decisions and are not involved in the process.

Can a monument be delisted? (if so, what are the criteria and how is the process?)

An ancient site may be removed from the list if it has been destroyed due to archaeological excavations or otherwise. If the area is completely excavated, it can be removed from the register of ancient monuments as protected archaeological remains, but not necessarily. If it has been restored after excavations, it usually is still protected and can be used as a tourist attraction, for example. If the excavations have been carried out due to a land use project, the remains will be removed from the register of protected sites after the excavations. The site will still be listed, but as a destroyed place. In this way, the information about the remains is still preserved and can be connected to previously unknown remains that may be found in the vicinity in the future.

System(s) applied

Is there any official system for evaluating significance in use by heritage managers?

There is no general classification system in use. This is mainly due to the Antiquities Act as all ancient remains are protected. An assessment is therefore not needed. Nevertheless, there is a project going on where the most significant archaeological sites in Finland are defined. (VARK-project shortened form "Valtakunnallisesti merkittävät arkeologiset kohteet" = Nationally significant archaeological sites in English). The aim of the project is to prepare a selection of sites that can be approved by the Finnish Government as inventory referred to in the national land use guidelines in accordance with the Land Use and Building Act. The purpose of the Inventory is to identify the areas and sites that should be considered in land use so that not only the remains themselves, but their identified values will be preserved.

The preservation of nationally significant archaeological sites is to be ensured under all circumstances. VARK sites may be subject to stricter criteria concerning the granting of disturbance and research permits than other sites. The VARK inventory is intended to be considered in regional planning, which steers the more detailed planning. The inventory was conducted in cooperation with regional museums and Metsähallitus (a state business institution managing national forest and water properties) between 2018 and 2023. The project covered the whole of Finland, except for the Province of Åland where the Act on the Autonomy of Åland (1144/1991) and provincial legislation apply.

Figure 7: Diagram showing development of the VARK project. (Finnish Heritage Agency)

How is the assessment done?

The basic material of the VARK project has been compiled from ancient remains that have previously been classified as valuable in various contexts and from sites that have been considered in the provincial plans. There are about 60,000 archaeological sites in Finland and 5% of them were included in this more detailed analysis.

At the start of the project, the base data of the sites was extracted from the Register of Ancient Remains (Fig.7). The remains for the inventory were chosen on the basis that the sites had already been assessed as significant earlier. The evaluation included the sites that were included in the selection of significant sites drawn up in 2001, the approximately 3700 sites of the highest protection category listed in the register of ancient sites and the sites which have been included in the list of nationally significant cultural property specified in the Hague Convention. In addition to these, the evaluation included four of the archaeological World Heritage Sites

located in Finland as well as approximately 600 sites marked as regionally significant in the provincial land use plans. In total, 13% (n = 4784) of all registered ancient sites were included in the evaluation process (see Figs.8&9 for example sites included in project).

The assessment was made by the Finnish Heritage Agency and museums with regional responsibility. There is a computer application which has been developed for the analysis. The assessments and their results have been made available online for everyone who has been involved in this project. Together there have been around 30 archaeologists from different organisations in the evaluation team.

What are the criteria when assessing the value of a site?

The assessment of the significance of each site was carried out by selecting a constant value for each criterion, which was then supplemented with a free-form description. The criteria used were as follows:

Figure 8: The Vanhalinna (Old castle in Finnish) fortified hill in south-west Finland had an important role as a functional centre in the Aura River valley during the Iron Age. The first structures there are Bronze Age (1300-500 BC in Finland) but the fortification is dated to the early Iron Age. The functions on the hill probably varied through time but included controlling river traffic, functioning as a cult center for the area as well as a refuge fort. From the 9th century onwards the Oxroad of Häme passed by Vanhalinna, linking the two major Iron Age settlement areas in Finland. Vanhalinna was selected to the VARK collection due its versatile remains of structures (several house remains, cemetery, walls of the fortification, well etc.) and scientific meaning. It was scored 17 out of 17 in the assessment. (Teija Tiitinen 2021, Finnish Heritage Agency).

Cultural historic significance: The assessment is based on how well the site reflects the phenomena, developments, and events of the period. The assessment was based on the research data on the site or the phenomenon that it represents. Score: 0 = not significant, 1 = modestly significant, 2 = fairly significant, 3 = highly significant.

Research value: The research value of the site is based on its research potential based on the information already obtained and the information that is still available. Score: 0 = no potential, 1 = modest potential, 2 = fair amount of potential, 3 = significant potential.

Prevalence or rarity: The assessment of the regional prevalence or rarity of the site type is based on existing archive material and literature. Score: 1 = prevalence or rarity is not a significant feature, 2 = fairly common or rare, 3 = very rare or common.

Archaeological diversity: The assessment is based on the number of observable phenomena at the site or long historic continuity. Score: 0 = no diversity, 1 = low degree of diversity, 2 = diverse, 3 = high degree of diversity.

Environment and landscape: The assessment is based on the effect the landscape around the site has to the perception of the site's environmental position in the past. The significance may increase if the site is located at a nationally significant built cultural heritage site or in a nationally significant landscape area or in a heritage

biotope. Score: 0 = the environment and the landscape have changed completely, 1 = there are unfamiliar features or damage in the environment or the landscape, 2 = the environment and the landscape around the site has some features supporting the comprehension of the site, 3 = the environment and the landscape around the site has plenty of features supporting the comprehension of the site, and the site is the central landscape feature in the area.

Degree of preservation: The assessment is based on the degree in which the observable distinctive characteristics of the site have been preserved. The site may also have been regarded as well preserved if it had been restored to a high standard. Score: 0 = destroyed, 1 = destroyed to a large extent, 2 = fairly well preserved, 3 = well preserved.

Are there different levels of protection?

All the ancient sites are protected under the law, but the definition of a site of ancient remains excludes sites which are young. Abandoned settlement areas and other monuments from the 20th century (so-called other archaeological heritage sites) can be preserved by the choices made in the land use planning. If the site is not protected by the law, it is a bit problematic. It is problematical because if an area where such a site is located is designated for construction, the authorities can suggest that archaeological excavations should be carried out before the building begins, but they cannot require it. Authorities are allowed to do it, but the developer doesn't have to pay for it.

Figure 9: Astuvansalmi, parish of Mikkeli (eastern Finland). The largest known Stone Age rock painting area in Finland, with around 80 red ochre pictures painted on a steep cliff face on the lake shore. The same elements at the landscape can still be seen now as during the Stone Age and the atmosphere is unique. Astuvansalmi area was selected to the VARK collection for its cultural historic meaning, and it scored very high in VARK assessment (16 out of 17). The Rock has an anthropomorphic shape (like a human head) and in underwater excavations among other has some amber statuettes with human face been found in the front of the rock. The paintings are dated to the end of the Neolithic era 4000-2200 BC. (Helena Taskinen, Finnish Heritage Agency).

Public participation

Is the public involved in the process of protection?

In Finland, the protection is purely led by the authorities. The public is not involved in the process.

Are there lists or plans of protected archaeological sites that are accessible to the public?

Basically, all of Finland's archaeological sites are accessible to the public. All the information about the ancient remains and their locations are available in Archaeological sites and objects in the cultural environment service window managed by the Finnish Heritage Agency. There are also so-called 'Everyone's Rights', that is to say the general public's right allows access to anyone to pass freely through the countryside, even in private areas.

Involvement of owners and their rights

Do the owners have any influence on the selection of archaeological sites for protection?

Not now. The situation may be altered after the law is reformed, which is anticipated in the next few years.

Do they have any influence on the protection procedure?

No

6.4 The Netherlands

Bjørn Smit

Introduction

Institution responsible for heritage protection

The national government is responsible for the legislation regarding cultural heritage and creates and provides the legal framework wherein regional and local administrations are able to take up their role and tasks on this subject. On behalf of the government the minister/state secretary of Education, Culture and Science (ministry of OCW) is the responsible authority. As part of the ministry of OCW, the Cultural Heritage Agency of the Netherlands is the organization which on national level is responsible for the protection of cultural heritage.

In practice cultural heritage management in the Netherlands is seen as a joint responsibility of public authorities, companies and private individuals. Legislation and governance are in general decentralized which means that also the 12 regional (provincial) authorities and around 350 local (municipal) authorities have their role and responsibility in the management and protection of cultural heritage. Central government focuses mainly on the preservation, sustainable management and improvement of access to the heritage. Provincial authorities and, above all, local authorities are responsible for the drawing-up and implementation, of policy at regional and local level.

Furthermore, owners of cultural heritage like listed built heritage or archaeological sites have a function in maintaining and safeguarding cultural heritage, but they do not have an obligation for this safeguarding. To motivate owners to take care of the monuments a system of subsidies was founded, to which owners can apply to maintain the monuments on their property in their care. In this way owners are stimulated to take care of their monuments, but they are not obliged.¹⁹

Short description of the legal system

The Dutch legislation regarding cultural heritage is based on the Heritage Act (2016), which succeeded the previous Monuments Act (1988). Cultural Heritage is in essence dealt with within the domain of spatial

developments and corresponding legislation. This means that cultural heritage is an important value which must be assessed and decided on in spatial developments like infrastructural or building initiatives.

The organisation of archaeological heritage management in the Netherlands is based on the [Valletta Convention](#) (CoE, 1992). 15 years after the signing of the Convention, in 2007, the Archaeological Heritage Management Act (*Wet archaeologische monumentenzorg*, WAMZ) and the Archaeological Heritage Management Decree (*Besluit archaeologische monumentenzorg*, BAMZ) were established (Government Gazette (Staatsblad) of the Kingdom of the Netherlands 2007, 293). In July 2016 this legislation was incorporated into the Heritage Act (*Erfgoedwet*), which provides for the protection of the cultural heritage as a whole: museums and their collections, monuments, historic buildings and archaeology (Government Gazette (Staatsblad) of the Kingdom of the Netherlands 2015, 511). The central points relating to archaeology in this legislation are: 1) preservation in situ; 2) recognition of archaeology at an early stage in the spatial planning process and 3) the 'developer pays' principle (which means that the initiator of a plan is financially responsible for the execution of archaeological research, regardless of their type, or the scale of the development). Under the influence of the neoliberal politics of the 1990s, two further elements were added: 4) devolvement of responsibility for heritage management from central government to other authorities, such as provincial and – above all – local authorities; and 5) the commercialisation of archaeological practice (e.g. Bazelmans, 2011; Van den Dries, 2011).

Archaeological heritage management is tightly interwoven with policy on spatial planning, which means that the majority of archaeological research and discovery of new sites is the result of new plans for building, infrastructure etc. The provincial and local authorities also have their own additional policies regarding the cultural heritage in the Netherlands, and thus play a key role in the protection of archaeological find spots. The vast majority of research and fieldwork in the Netherlands are performed by private companies (Verbruggen, 2016); some 25 local

¹⁹This poses a risk especially for non-visible archaeological monuments. Besides burial and dwelling mounds (terps) in general the archaeological remains are in the subsurface of the Netherlands. The majority of archaeological remains in the Netherlands are not visible so the value of these remains is not always recognized by the public or in fact it is unknown that remains (or monuments) are present. Thus 'what you cannot see is not there'.

authorities also carry out field work (Wesselingh, 2016), as do universities and the Cultural Heritage Agency, albeit only on a very small scale.

A quality assurance system has been established to ensure this system is managed properly. It is based partly on legislation and partly on self-regulation (Willems, 2005). In this way, central government and provincial and local authorities ensure that the archaeological heritage is cared for appropriately. To ensure that only parties who are properly equipped for the task are involved in archaeological field research, since 2016, excavations may be performed only with a certificate. A Dutch Archaeology Quality Standard has been developed to guide the quality of research (*Kwaliteitsnorm Nederlandse Archaeologie* [KNA]; Willems and Brandt, 2004). And this quality standard is the base of the certification system, in which companies, individuals or governments with a certificate are assessed on regularly basis by a system of internal and external audits. The external audits are performed by accredited certification companies. This certificate system ensures that parties working in archaeological heritage management and perform the majority of the archaeological work in the Netherlands is on par with the Dutch Archaeology Quality Standard and in line with the relevant (national, regional and local) legislation. Furthermore, a system of certification provides the archaeological sector itself maximum responsibility

for assuring the quality of archaeological research (Lauwerier, 2017, p.14). The Heritage Inspectorate monitors on a macrolevel the Dutch cultural heritage and central government's information management systems. The Cultural Heritage Agency of the Netherlands lists national archaeological monuments and develops knowledge products to assist those working in the field and is an important partner for the national government to assess and if necessary, change or improve the modus operandi or legislation.

When making decisions during development, the (national, regional, local) administrations have to weigh, based on information and reports written by archaeological specialists, the heritage value and gains against numerous other interests. This will be strengthened in the near future when the new Environmental and Planning Act (*Omgevingswet*) of the Netherlands is in effect (2024). So whereas listed monuments and the archaeological system fall under the Heritage Act (2016), research of archaeological remains and the weighing of the value of these remains is placed in this Environmental and Planning Act (2024). To aid this process the Archaeological Heritage Management (AHM) cycle has evolved: a continuous process of gathering information within an iterative process, which means that old and newly gathered information is integrated and research in the end is synthesized (Fig.10).

Figure 10: The archaeological heritage management cycle (the Netherlands)

Significance of archaeological sites

Criteria

Which criteria must an archaeological monument meet in order to be listed?

The listing and protection of archaeological sites at national level in the last decades at national level has been operationalized through 'listing programmes' which ran for several years. These listing programmes in general had their own focus like the programme which ended in 2011 which was mainly focused on Roman archaeological sites. The following listing programme focused on sites which were seen as lacking from the existing list. At that time, it was felt that assemblage of listed archaeological heritage sites was skewed and had a focus on visible archaeological sites like burial mounds, terps (settlement mounds), and furthermore a predominance of sites dating to the Neolithic, Bronze age, Iron age and Roman period.

The focus of the new listing programme was aimed at adding sites which were 'missing' from the list. Sites dating to the Stone Age and sites dating to the Middle Ages and younger were listed to balance the record. A crucial criterium in this listing programme was the support of the landowner and the municipality where the site was located. Around 2015 the idea arose that the list of listed archaeological monuments could be regarded as complete. However due to the fact that more and more archaeological sites were excavated in the realm of spatial planning developments, governments were not really active in listing sites on regional or local level and due to the feeling, that the list of listed sites was still unbalanced, research was done to see which types of sites should be protected (Smit et al, 2020). The research concluded that in a way the list of scheduled monuments should have a dynamic character: new scientific insights but also societal developments will result in new ideas about which archaeological remains are deemed relevant and should be safeguarded for the future, in a way that allows future archaeologists to study protected sites with new ideas and insights.

Furthermore, in this research and corresponding advice it was concluded that in a way the general public should be more involved, and the broader context (be it landscape or culture historical) of the sites must be considered. In addition, remains from periods which are not always regarded as archaeology have to be taken into account, e.g. periods after 1850, archaeological remains from World War Two and perhaps even the Cold War. Recently

with the establishment of the Lower German Limes as UNESCO World Heritage Site several archaeological sites from the Roman period were listed or existing listed monuments were enlarged.

At regional and local level, the listing of regional and local archaeological monuments has a more variable format. The basic principle is similar sites that are listed have been assessed using the general valuation scheme. The additional or specific listing criteria are regionally or locally decided upon based on regional and local legislation and interests. However, when sites are regionally or locally listed in general a system of permits is set up to safeguard the monuments in a similar way as is done for nationally listed sites.

Are international conventions taken into account or do they play a role (e.g., Faro)?

The Netherlands' system of archaeological heritage management is based on the principles of the Valletta Convention. At this moment discussions are going on about the ratification of the Faro Framework Agreement, it has been decided that the principles of Faro are or will be implemented, so the treaty will be ratified by the Netherlands. The process of ratification has started, and as a result the principles of Faro will play a role. However, the exact implementation is work in progress. In good Dutch custom it is already possible to benefit from or use the principles of the Faro Framework Agreement. In November 2023 as part of the Implementation Agenda Faro a total of 26 initiatives received funding from the Dutch government. The implementation agenda aims to aid the introduction and sustainability of the Faro principles in heritage practices. The adoption of the Faro principles (besides future ratification) is seen as a both public and private responsibility, so the Dutch government focusses on public-private corporations, this being in line with existing legislation regarding (cultural) heritage. The recent funded initiatives range from projects to facilitate the introduction and dissemination of Faro principles in education, to increase volunteer involvement in heritage projects and practices but also initiatives which critically address and question well established and current heritage practices. Specific archaeology initiatives focus on subjects like citizen science projects, the participation of archaeological volunteers but also on accessing and safeguarding 'old archaeological collections' from volunteers and an initiative to research the possibilities for participating in

Figure 11: The decision matrix for the 'delisting' of monuments (the Netherlands).

heritage studies for people with disabilities. Furthermore, the UNESCO underwater heritage treaty (2001) is likely to be ratified in the near future, which would mean a big step for the safeguarding of underwater archaeological heritage in Dutch waters.

Can a monument be delisted? (if so, what are the criteria and how is the process?)

A listed site may be removed from the list if it has been destroyed as a result of archaeological research and this research is performed and reported conform the quality standard of Dutch archaeology. However, for these situations a good motivation must be provided, and one needs a permit, and, in the end, the Cultural Heritage Agency of the Netherlands decides. The research in general is performed by private archaeological companies and the 'developers pay principle' is used. The Cultural Heritage Agency in a way dictates the research questions and – aims and also monitors the research. Furthermore, the research must comply with the national agreed standards. excavations or otherwise. If the area is completely excavated, it can be removed from the register of listed monuments as protected archaeological remains. Of course monuments can also be endangered by natural erosion and misconduct (deliberate, not deliberate). In both instances the damage is assessed and when possible, the monument is restored and additionally (physically) protected. However sometimes the remaining (archaeological) value is so limited that it can be decided that the monument is 'delisted'. When that occurs generally a form of research is done to gather the remaining archaeological value/information. Recently a decisions matrix was developed (Fig.11) which aids decision making for specialists in cultural heritage to decide whether a listed monument might be excavated definitively (Mauro et al, 2022). This matrix will have to prove its value or fitness in the future.

System(s) applied

Is there any official system for evaluating significance in use by heritage managers?

In the Netherlands in general, all archaeological sites discovered within the context of spatial planning projects are assessed and a standard is used to establish both the physical quality as the intrinsic (scientific) quality of the site. This standard is part of the Dutch Archaeological Quality standard and is used by all professional archaeologists. To be listed as scheduled monument

additional criteria are used, depending on the listing programme at hand.

How is the assessment done?

The identification of an archaeological site is based on the evaluation made by professional archaeologists either working for commercial companies or one of the government agencies. In the Netherlands about 95% of all archaeological research (fieldwork) is executed by professional private archaeological companies, and all parties who perform fieldwork have to be certified (SIKB 2022; Willems and Brandt, 2004). Archaeologists who are responsible for so-called 'critical actions' during the fieldwork/research are registered in a national register of archaeologists. Both the quality system and the register act to safeguard the (minimal) quality of research conducted.

When an archaeological site is discovered, its value is assessed by means of a standardized score list that focusses on the physical and scientific or intrinsic quality of the site (Groenewoudt, 1994; KNA 4.2 bijlage IV.). If a site is deemed worth preserving, meaning that its physical and scientific quality is good, and conforms to the basics of the Valletta Convention: the site is preserved in situ, excavated or, a third not desirable option, is decided that no action is necessary. It has to be mentioned that the third option is luckily hardly used. In general sites are preserved or researched.

The decision about what happens with a site after the assessment of the professional archaeologist is made by the proper authorities, depending on the situation, these are national, regional or local authorities. Again it should be noted that these decisions are made in the context of the spatial planning process.

In general the assessment is performed by professional archaeologist (registered archaeologists) after a sufficient amount of research (fieldwork) is done. The goal is that after archaeological remains are found and studied, statements about the nature, size, age and conservation of the archaeological site can be made. For this assessment several criteria are used.

Figure 12: The weighing matrix used in site assessments (the Netherlands).

What are the criteria when assessing the value of a site?

Information on the nature, extent, date and preservation of the site is gathered. Regulations serve as guidelines in the evaluation of individual archaeological sites.²⁰ In general when an archaeological site is discovered this site is assessed for its value. This assessment is based on several criteria which have to be scored (Fig.12). At the end the different scores are weighed and based on the total score it is decided whether a site is worth preserving. The first criterium used in this procedure is perception which has as parameters: aesthetic value and experience value. It has to be noticed that this only have relevance for archaeological remains that are visible, such as castles, terps, burial mounds, megaliths etc. The majority of the archaeological remains in the Netherlands is to be found in the subsoil, therefore the main criteria that are used in the assessment of a site are: physical quality and intrinsic quality. The physical quality in fact pertains to the conservation of the archaeological remains (intactness and preservation). The intrinsic value focusses on the archaeological information of the remains (its rarity, information value, group value and representativity).²¹

The majority of sites are situated in the subsoil and are assessed on physical quality first. Sites with a score of five or six points on the parameters integrity and preservation are worth preserving. The sites of high physical quality (≥ 5 points) are furthermore assessed on the first three intrinsic quality criteria (rarity, information value and group value). A site having a score, on intrinsic quality, of 7 points or more is worth preserving. Sites having a low

score on the physical quality also have to be evaluated on intrinsic quality, which provides the possibility to protect sites with a low physical quality but a high intrinsic quality.

In summary in the Netherlands a valuation system of archaeological sites is in play which grades sites in different classes: sites with a high physical quality (≥ 5 points) and a high intrinsic quality (≥ 7 points) are worth conserving. Of sites with a low physical quality (≤ 4 points) but with a high intrinsic quality (≥ 7 points) a representative sample has to be preserved. Sites with lower qualifications are not worth preserving.

Are there different levels of protection?

Nationally listed archaeological sites are protected under national law, the Heritage Act. Furthermore, archaeological sites can be protected in spatial planning legislation, meaning that these sites are mentioned in zoning plans of regional and local governments. However, those sites listed nationally have the most strict regulations.

All the three levels of authorities have the possibility to list archaeological sites, however the Cultural Heritage Agency of the Netherlands acting on behalf of the national government decides which sites are nationally listed. The first Monuments and Historic Buildings Act, which was introduced in 1961. In 1967 several (visible) burial mounds dating to late neolithic/bronze age were the first to be listed, based on the premise that these archaeological remains warranted protection being

²⁰See appendix IV Dutch Archaeological Standard version KNA 4.2, this scheme is similar to the schemes presented by Groenewoudt 1994; Groenewoudt & Bloemers 1997 and Deeben et al. 1999; but some modifications are added. For a recent (in Dutch) description and critical note on the criteria see Bazelmans 2021.

²¹In practice the last content criteria representativity is not scored in the evaluation of sites, appendix IV KNA 4.1.

archives for archaeological research in future. So, when the listing started the main objective was to safeguard part of the archaeological archive as a scientific resource for future generations of archaeologists. At this moment about 1450 archaeological sites are listed as national archaeological heritage site. Regional and local listed archaeological sites are known, but unfortunately figures about these listed sites are hard to come by and not all have the same degree of protection as nationally listed sites. National listed sites are labeled and classified as monuments for which a system of permits is developed. Several 'listed' or known provincial or municipal archaeological monuments are safeguarded within spatial planning regulations ('zoning plans'), which in general are not as strict as monuments legislation.

Public participation

Is the public involved in the process of protection?

In the Netherlands, operations are purely led by local and national authorities. The public is not involved in the protection process, however more and more the public is involved in providing input about which cultural heritage is relevant. Especially on the local level there are some developments, for example groups who address 'new' types of cultural heritage or groups raising awareness for lesser-known cultural heritage or archaeological remains. One must be honest, this is a new development, in line with the principles of the Faro Convention, but it is not standard yet, although interest is growing. Furthermore, according to the system the assessing of archaeological sites must be done by a professional archaeologist and the decisions whether a site is worth preserving is as said above, a decision of the proper authorities. The public can influence, by suggesting sites or themes, but has no decisive voice and at the moment no large-scale listing programme is in play. At the moment only one or maybe two sites can be listed each year and one has to realize that the process of listing a site is time consuming because a large number of parties are involved.

Are there lists or plans of protected archaeological sites that are accessible to the public?

All Dutch archaeological sites are accessible to the public in some kind of digital form. Information on archaeological sites listed and not listed can be found in the national registration database ARCHIS, however for this website a login is required. Furthermore, information is available on other national, regional and

local websites. Information on listed monuments can be found in the national registers of national monuments in which besides about 65,000 built monuments also the archaeological monuments are described. The national museum of Antiquities has a site which is especially aimed at schoolchildren and the general public which shows basically archaeology in your own backyard. Physical accessibility, however, is a different aspect, listed sites which are located in the public domain can be visited, signs and information is provided in numerous different ways. Listed sites located on private property are generally not accessible, exceptions excluded.

Involvement of owners and their rights

Do the owners have any influence on the selection of archaeological sites for protection?

In the last major listing programmes owners have had involvement, meaning that their approval was a key factor in whether a monument was listed. The idea behind this is that monuments are listed for the generations of the future, so you want proper care of the (land) owner and therefore the owner has to be involved.

Do they have any influence on the protection procedure?

Not so much on the procedures, as said above if a (land) owner is not willing to cooperate it is not likely that a monument will be listed. However, in the Netherlands there is an extensive (legal) system of checks and balances in decision making procedures in which the public and stakeholders can voice their arguments, interest and objections.

It has to be noted that owners of monuments also face some restrictions in the use of their property (buildings, land) which are or contain monuments. A system of permits is in place for several activities in or on monuments. For example, disturbances are not allowed on archaeological monuments and when some form of negative activity cannot be avoided the owner/initiator needs to apply for a permit, which states the activities which are allowed and which ones are not.

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank my colleagues Tessa de Groot and Neelson Witte (both Cultural Heritage Agency of the Netherlands) for valuable comments and suggestions on earlier drafts of this paper.

6.5 Poland

Agnieszka Makowska

Introduction

Institution responsible for heritage protection

The General Monument Preservation Officer, acting on behalf of the Minister of Culture and National Heritage, is the highest authority for the cultural heritage protection in Poland. The Officer oversees the activities of sixteen provincial heritage managers, the Voivodship Monuments Preservation Officers (VMPOs), who are part of the local level of state administration, in organisational and financial terms. With regard to archaeology, state heritage services carry out administrative and protective activities regarding listing and inventorying of archaeological monuments, archaeological research and metal detector search permits, accidentally-discovered objects and archaeological sites, spatial planning etc.

The National Institute of Cultural Heritage (NICH) provides the Minister of Culture and National Heritage with expert and advisory assistance in the field of heritage protection. The Institute is not a part of state administration. Its main tasks are to gather and disseminate information on heritage, set standards for its protection and conservation, and raise social awareness of cultural heritage of Poland.

Short description of the legal system

The system of protection of monuments in Poland has its roots in the *Decree of the Regency Council on the guardianship of monuments of art and culture* issued in 1918, just after Poland regained its independence. Under this act, all care-related activities were the responsibility of Monuments Preservation Officers, appointed by the Minister of Religious Denominations and Public Enlightenment. Archaeological relics were protected as monuments and they could not be destroyed, reworked, renewed or reconstructed without the permission of the Monuments Preservation Officer. All immovable and movable monuments, existing for at least 50 years, were under the law protection even before they were entered into the inventory of monuments. The act emphasized that archaeological relics were also automatically protected.

The system functioning in the interwar period was finally shaped by the provisions of the *Regulation of 6 March 1928 of the President of the Republic of Poland* about the guardianship of monuments. On its basis, a register of monuments was established. They also defined the structure and organization of monuments' guardianship authorities, assigning duties in this respect to the state administration.

According to the binding Act of 23 July 2003 on the protection and guardianship of monuments, an archaeological monument is an immovable monument constituting surface, underground or underwater remains of human existence or activity, composed of cultural layers and works or traces thereof contained in these layers, or a movable monument constituting such work. To meet this definition, it must first meet the definition of a monument, and its preservation must be in the interest of society due to its historical, artistic, scientific or academic value. There is no age limit. According to the law, archaeological monuments are subject to automatic protection, and, consequently, whoever, during the carrying out of construction or earth works, discovers an object potentially being a monument, shall: stop all works that could damage or destroy the discovered object, secure the place of its discovery and immediately notify the VMPO. In practice this is not always the case. Furthermore, if somebody is intending to carry out construction works regarding listed monuments or earthworks in the area where archaeological monuments are located, which could lead to their transformation or destruction, they must cover the costs of archaeological research and their documentation. Carrying out archaeological research requires a permit from the VMPO. The mode and manner of issuing permits defines the Regulation of 2 August 2018 of the Minister of Culture and National Heritage concerning the implementation of conservation, restoration and construction works, conservation and architectural research and other activities carried out in registered monuments as well as archaeological research and search for movable monuments. Archaeological objects belong to the State.

Separate legal regulations apply to the keeping of the register and record of monuments, Regulation of 26 May 2011 of the Minister of Culture and National Heritage concerning the keeping the register of monuments, national, voivodship, and commune record of monuments and the national list of stolen or illegally exported monuments.

Significance of archaeological sites

Criteria

Which criteria must an archaeological monument meet in order to be listed?

It must meet the legal definition of an archaeological monument quoted above. The binding act lists several types of structures that should be subject to protection and guardianship regardless of their state of preservation, including, but not limited to: field remains of prehistoric and historical settlements, burial grounds, tumuli, relics of economic, religious and artistic activities. They do not have a specific age limit. The basic assumption, however, is that there are no objectively insignificant archaeological sites.

Are international conventions taken into account or do they play a role (e.g. Faro)?

Poland ratified the [Valletta Convention](#) in 1996. Until recently its provisions were almost without exceptions adopted in the existing Act of 23 July 2003. New preferential rules for amateurs searching for artefacts with electronic equipment (mostly metal detectors) have been introduced by the Act of 13 July 2023. Adopting these tenets may result in actions that are inconsistent with the provisions of the Convention (cf. Article 3). The Act is set to come into effect on 1 January 2027.

Issues relevant to the archaeological heritage protection are still dealt with in respective acts on spatial planning and road constructions, and related ordinances and regulations. Moreover, the mission of the National Institute of Cultural Heritage, the organisation established by the Minister of Culture and National Heritage in 2007, is the echo of the Valletta Convention premise connected with the sustainable protection of cultural heritage. In situ protection and priority of remote sensing research are important planks of the Minister of Culture and National Heritage grant programmes, operated by NICH (Oniszczyk, 2014).

In addition, a new national strategy, the [AZP+ Programme](#), is being implemented. Its main purpose is to identify archaeological heritage more effectively using remote sensing methods and provide tools for more effective protection of the archaeological heritage in situ. It will also deal with issues of public access to knowledge about archaeological heritage. In terms of promoting the protection of the archaeological landscape, the AZP+ Programme is in line with the objectives of the [Landscape](#)

[Convention](#). Poland also ratified the [Faro Convention](#) (2005) in 2022.

Can a monument be delisted? (if so, what are the criteria and how is the process?)

According to the binding Act, 'monuments entered into the register which have been destroyed in a way resulting in the loss of their historical, artistic or scientific value', or their value has not been confirmed by new scientific research, shall be removed from the register. This shall apply to a part of a monument.

Removal from the register shall take place on the basis of a decision of the Minister of Culture and National Heritage. The proceedings may be initiated ex officio or upon a request from the monument owner or the perpetual lessee of the land on which the site is located. The request is sent through the VMPO to the Ministry. The Ministry may ask the National Institute of Cultural Heritage for a substantive opinion. The opinion is then prepared on the basis of an analysis of Historic Environment Records, including the results of previous research and existing open-access remote sensing data. Depending on the situation, geophysical survey is recommended. The lack of archaeological structures must always be proven through trench survey.

Objects reconstructed after excavations, such as burial mounds, are mostly not removed from the register despite the absence of original archaeological layers. This is because their significance to the local community is also considered.

System(s) applied

Is there any official system for evaluating significance in use by heritage managers?

There are no officially accepted evaluation methods in Poland. The binding Act of 23 July treats all archaeological remnants of human activity equally (Art. 6. 1. Protection and care shall apply, regardless of their state of preservation: to archaeological sites being, in particular: a) field remains of prehistoric and historical settlements, b) cemeteries, c) burial mounds, d) relics of economic, religious and artistic activities) and does not suggest how to choose sites to be listed.

All ancient remains are protected. Every archaeological relic should be then considered a source of information and of different values.

How is the assessment done?

As a rule, it is the respective VMPO who decides how to assess archaeological structures. In most cases, however, the basis for the assessment is the recommendations made by the researchers. Results of field walking survey are usually sufficient to list a site in the national inventory of archaeological sites (Polish Archaeological Record). More detailed analysis, i.e., geophysical prospection, remote sensing methods and survey trenches are used nowadays to provide data and assess significance in the procedure for entering a site in the archaeological monuments register. But this was not always the case. The first entries of archaeological relics into the register took place in 1929. Since then, in the absence of national guidelines, different criteria and methods for defining significance have been used by succeeding provincial heritage managers. As a result, the national register of archaeological monuments is not homogeneous.

Between 2010 and 2017 the National Institute of Cultural Heritage carried out a project of verification of all registered archaeological sites. The aim of the project was to update the national register. A dedicated field survey was carried out and compared with the results of previous research. Analysis of open access aerial photographs and Lidar data was also handled. One of the tasks of archaeologists involved in the project was to check whether the documentation indicated the values based on which the site is protected. It was not about ranking and identifying the more important sites. It was about the values of an individual nature that distinguish it from other sites, so that they can be invoked in a critical situation. It also aimed to identify the most urgent actions to be taken to protect archaeological remains. Furthermore, the state of preservation, land use, threats, documentation, etc. was assessed. This included the identification and selection of sites for detailed analysis due to current threats and the worrisome state of preservation of cultural features and layers, as well as the inaccurate delimitation of the protection zone in the documentation.

What are the criteria when assessing the value of a site?

There is no formal assessment procedure. Different schools of thought are applied in different provinces, at different times. In practice, the most commonly used criterion is the presence of the terrain form. Similarly, protecting archaeological structures of a unique type (such as rondels, longhouses or megalithic tombs) that

are clearly visible on aerial photographs and digital terrain models have become a common practice. Usually, the emphasis is on scientific significance, uniqueness in a particular area or time period, and the spectacular nature of the remains. Significance for cultural landscape, educational and local community relevance may also be an assessment criterion. In some cases, the state of preservation, hazards, planned development or political issues matter. Archaeological artefacts collected from the surface are sufficient for the listing of an archaeological site. Thus, the significance of an archaeological site can be analysed in many dimensions (Nowakowski et al, 1999). One of the recommendations on the structure of significance criteria suggests public perception as a starting point, i.e., aesthetic value, historical value, symbolic value, economic value. The next suggested step is then an assessment of the state of preservation of the stratigraphic system, with artefacts in situ (and directly related scientific potential), and then, optionally, as a representative example (Kobyliński and Wysocki, 2012). The National Institute of Cultural Heritage believes that it is crucial to study and record ancient features and landscapes in advance, using non-intrusive methods. This is essential in order to set the suitable scale of values, taking into account the individual attributes of the archaeological relics. This allows for the planning of necessary protection measures, financial resources and the involvement of the heritage managers, appropriate to the assessed significance (Konopka, 2016). It is important to remember that all data and value assessment are based on current knowledge and may be subject to be revised as a result of future research. It also depends on whether the assessment is done by locals or outsiders, as perspective can be very influential.

The criteria for assessing the significance also vary according to circumstances and changing needs. This was particularly evident during the post-war reconstruction of Poland, when the archaeological heritage was used for political and propaganda purposes. In 1948, on the initiative of the communist authorities of the time, a scientific programme, popularly known as the Millennium Studies, was launched. The project was related to the upcoming celebration of the 1000th anniversary of the Polish state in 1966. Various sites associated with times of its formation were excavated. However, the programme was heavily focused on "proving the existence of Slavic and proto-Polish roots" of the western and northern territories, formerly part of the state of the first historical ruler of Poland, Mieszko I, but as a result of the complicated 1000 year history of Central Europe,

they were largely inhabited by Germans. These lands, propagandistically called the Recovered Territories, were annexed to Poland as a result of the decisions of the Yalta and Potsdam conferences. The results of the Millennium Studies were intended to confirm the validity of this solution.

Are there different levels of protection?

There are almost 500,000 archaeological sites listed in the national inventory of archaeological sites. Most of them were recorded as a result of the Polish Archaeological Record programme. This is a field survey project that has been running since 1978. Standardised documentation of each site is the basis for all decisions made by heritage managers.

Selected sites are entered into the register of monuments (c.7,800). The selection is made by the respective VMPOs, using various criteria. A listed site that is of special cultural importance can be recognised as a monument of history by a presidential decree. On the initiative of local authorities, cultural parks can be established. They are of great importance as they can help to build a local identity.

The last of the legal forms of monuments preservation is protection laid down in a local spatial development plan or in various administrative decisions (on the construction of road, railways or public airport, on the land use conditions, on the location of a public purpose investment).

Public participation

Is the public involved in the process of protection?

The process is managed by the authorities only.

Are there lists or plans of protected archaeological sites that are accessible to the public?

The National Institute of Cultural Heritage publishes geospatial data and a popular [online presentation of heritage resources](#). It contains descriptions, documentation, photographs, 3D models, point clouds and films of monuments, including archaeological sites.

Involvement of owners and their rights

Do the owners have any influence on the selection of archaeological sites for protection?

The owner may apply for entry or removal of an archaeological site from the register.

Do they have any influence on the protection procedure?

The owner is a party to the procedure for entry in the register. According to the Act of 23 July 2003, the owner is responsible for the guardianship of a monument. This consists in particular in providing conditions for: scientific examining and documenting, carrying out conservation works, protection and maintenance in the best possible condition, and for popularisation and dissemination of knowledge on a monument and its meaning for history and culture.

The owner has the right to appeal against any decision of the Voivodship Monuments Preservation Officer.

SECTION 7

Evaluating Significance – Examples

7.1 Archaeological Cultural Landscape of Carnuntum, Austria

René Ployer

Location and surroundings

The archaeological cultural landscape Carnuntum is located in the east of the province of Lower Austria, close to the border with Slovakia and extends directly south of the Danube over the communities of Petronell-Carnuntum and Bad Deutsch-Altenburg. It is situated between the western outskirts of Petronell in the west, the Danube river in the north, the Pfaffenberg hill in the east and the large agricultural areas in the south. With the gradual incorporation of the Eastern Alps and Danube region into the Roman Empire during the reign of Emperor Augustus (27 BC-14 AD), the area around Carnuntum became a hub for the connection between Northern and Southern Europe. Its location on the northern border of the Roman Empire formed by the Danube and the so-called Amber Road was decisive for this.

Carnuntum is the easternmost site of the Austrian section of the Danube Limes, which is part of the Frontiers of the Roman Empire World Heritage Site. The Austrian Limes section is about 357 km long and runs along the river Danube from the border of Germany (Bavaria) close to Passau through Upper and Lower Austria and Vienna to the area east of Hainburg/Wolfsthal beside the Slovakian border and the city of Bratislava. The first demarcation line of the Danube Limes came into existence when the frontier territory was turned into official Roman provinces around AD 40. For over 400 years this fortification system was the outer borderline of the Roman Empire, protecting it from the tribes to the North.

The frontier system in Austria consisted of a chain of fortifications along the south bank of the river Danube using the river as an additional obstacle and as a communication, supply and trade route. Along the course of the river lay legionary fortresses, forts, fortlets and watchtowers. The individual military installations and other ancillary features were linked by a supra-regional road, the Limes road. Besides the fortresses, forts and fortlets existed civil settlements and cemeteries.

Figure 13: Area of ancient Carnuntum with areas prospected by geophysics and partial interpretation of prospection results. © 7reasons Medien GmbH / LBI ArchPro.

Reasons for assessment

Since 1977, individual areas of Carnuntum have been placed under monument protection. These include the legionary fortress, the auxiliary fort, the so-called Heathen's Gate (Heidentor), parts of the canabae legionis, the two amphitheatres and parts of the civil town.

It was planned for a long time to place all the free archaeological areas of Carnuntum under monument protection, which failed due to the lack of knowledge of the exact extent. Within the framework of the research project "ArchPro Carnuntum", which was carried out from 2012 to 2015, the Roman city area of Carnuntum (more than 10 km²) was completely prospected with geophysics under the direction of the Ludwig Boltzmann Institute for Archaeological Prospecting and Virtual Archaeology (Fig.13). The result

Figure 14: Archaeological cultural landscape Carnuntum: areas under monument protection (orange = before 2019; blue = new areas 2019).

© Austrian Federal Monuments Authority

Figure 15: World Heritage Site "Frontiers of the Roman Empire – The Danube Limes (Western Segment)", ID 1608bis-071, Carnuntum (red = property, blue = buffer zone).

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was a complete layout of the ancient city with its entire infrastructure, such as roads and water pipelines, as well as numerous farmsteads and temporary camps around the town.

One of the main reasons for the protection was the forthcoming submission of the Danube Limes in Bavaria, Austria, Slovakia and Hungary as a UNESCO World Heritage Site. By ratifying the World Heritage Convention, each State Party agrees to preserve its World Heritage Sites with the highest level of national protection. Therefore, the site was added to the 2019 official annual list of monuments to be assessed for the status of protection by law. The assessment of the site was carried out in the same year, followed by an expert report. The protection status was proclaimed by notice from the Federal Monuments Authority on 3 October 2019. There were some appeals against the decision by landowners. After several negotiations at the Federal Administrative Court, the last parts of the archaeological cultural landscape Carnuntum were finally legally listed in 2022 (Fig.14).

Since July 2021, Carnuntum has been on the World Heritage List as a component part of the World Heritage Site "Frontiers of the Roman Empire – The Danube Limes (Western Segment)" (Fig.15).

Description of site

The centre of ancient Carnuntum comprises the area between Petronell and Bad Deutsch-Altenburg, where the legionary fortress with the surrounding military settlement (canabae legionis) and the auxiliary fort are located. To the east of this was the town hill with its sanctuaries (Pfaffenberg). To the west, in Petronell, was the walled civil town, adjoined to the west and south by the civil suburbs, which reached almost as far as the Heidentor (Heathen's Gate) to the southwest. Carnuntum's burial grounds were located along several exit roads leading out of this core zone. The water pipelines coming from the west and south served to supply the legionary fortress and the town with water. Numerous temporary camps and some farmsteads have been found around the core zone.

The oldest verifiable traces of Roman settlement in Carnuntum date back to the middle of the first century AD, when the legio XV Apollinaris was transferred to the Danube and established its base in Carnuntum. An extensive settlement (canabae legionis) subsequently developed around this legionary fortress. About 1.2

Figure 16: Area of ancient Carnuntum with redrawing of features from aerial photographs. © 7reasons Medien GmbH / LBI ArchPro.

kilometres southwest of the fortress, an auxiliary fort for a 500-man cavalry unit was built to reinforce the legion, probably under Emperor Domitian (81-96 AD).

Following this, the civilian settlement areas developed towards the west, which led to a constant expansion of the settlement, so that it was already granted the rank of a city (*Municipium Aelium Carnuntum*) in the reign of Hadrian (117-138 AD). During the reign of Septimius Severus (193-211 AD), who was proclaimed emperor here in 193 AD, it was elevated to the status of a *colonia* (Fig.16).

Carnuntum was repeatedly the residence of Roman emperors and the site of political decisions of importance for the entire empire. From the second half of the 4th century AD, probably due to a catastrophic earthquake, gradual decay set in, so that the fortress and urban settlement areas became completely deserted from the 5th century onwards.

Carnuntum is considered to be the most important archaeological site in Austria, extending from the Pfaffenberg in the east to beyond the western end of Petronell. Building ruins, burial sites and important individual monuments such as the Heidentor and the two amphitheatres still reveal the importance of this military and economic centre of the Roman Empire.

Due to the diversity of its archaeological monuments, Carnuntum represents all aspects of a northern frontier town of the Roman Empire. Each of these sub-areas offers a variety of historical and cultural information on its own and is at the same time an integral part of an archaeological site of pan-European significance.

Assessing significance – methods

Two different methods played a role in assessing the significance of the archaeological cultural landscape Carnuntum: the assessment of the monument's "historical, artistic or general cultural significance" based on the Austrian Monument Protection Act and the criteria for the assessment of Outstanding Universal Value according to the World Heritage Convention. As a World Heritage Site, the archaeological cultural landscape Carnuntum meets criteria ii, iii and iv according to the [World Heritage Convention](#) (UNESCO, 1972).

Historical significance

Carnuntum is the largest archaeological cultural landscape in Austria and thus a first-rate historical resource. The large area of ancient Carnuntum and the comparatively good preservation of the ancient

archaeological monuments are unique. Roman cities and military installations as well as the archaeological monuments directly connected to them, such as the remains of their buildings, cemeteries and infrastructure, including roads and water pipelines, are among the most important monuments of antiquity in the Austrian region. They served as administrative centres with numerous military, fiscal and legal functions. The municipium Carnuntum, which was later raised to the status of a colonia, was even the administrative seat of the province of Upper Pannonia from the 2nd century AD. The legionary fortress and town owed their rapid rise, among other things, to their favourable location at the crossroads of two transcontinental trade routes (the so-called Limes Road along the Danube and the north-south running Amber Road). Carnuntum was repeatedly at the centre of important historical events during the Roman rule over Pannonia.

Such Roman towns and military installations, as in Carnuntum, together with their surroundings, represent historical sources of the first order for a period from which very few written records are available. Historical and archaeological investigations of various ancient settlement areas provide insights into their function, the time of their construction, building history, possible destruction and restoration measures. In addition, the daily life of soldiers, traders, craftsmen and other civilians, who often came from distant regions of the Roman Empire, becomes tangible.

The areas of Carnuntum that are not built over in a modern way have been preserved largely undisturbed below the earth's surface due to their current use as meadows and farmland. The individual elements of the archaeological cultural landscape Carnuntum each occupy a prominent position within their monument category, as almost all comparable Roman structures in the immediate vicinity of the towns and settlements have been destroyed or influenced by overbuilding or other human activities. Every single element in Carnuntum's civil and military areas is therefore a historical source of the greatest historical and scientific importance. Only a small part of the area has been archaeologically investigated, but future archaeological investigations of the previously untouched areas will offer the possibility of making comparisons between older and more recent results with further refined scientific methodology.

Due to the lack of comparable Roman towns and military camps with their surroundings, Carnuntum thus has a unique historical significance throughout Austria. As large areas of Carnuntum are almost undeveloped, the ancient remains are therefore preserved below the surface. The presence of original structures has been proven in many cases by excavations in the 20th and 21st centuries. Aerial photographs and geophysical measurements from 2012-2015 prove that the ground monuments have been preserved over a large area. This makes it possible to document history in a way that is unique in Austria.

General cultural significance

The cultural significance of the Roman buildings along the Austrian Danube Limes that are still preserved in the ground or standing upright today is based on several factors. The section on the Austrian Danube forms an integral part of the vast and complex frontier system of the Roman Empire, which once stretched from Scotland to the northern edge of the Sahara and from the Atlantic to the Black Sea. Along the Danube frontier, which had been continuously occupied since the 1st century AD, forts and legionary fortresses as well as the associated civilian settlements were built at irregular intervals and had different military and infrastructural functions. They represent life on a northern border of the Roman Empire and its relationship to the Germanic settlement areas north of the Danube for a period of about half a millennium.

Carnuntum represents the most important archaeological site in Austria and with the diversity of its archaeological monuments shows all aspects of a northern frontier town with a legionary fortress of the Roman Empire. Each element of the archaeological cultural landscape Carnuntum in itself provides a variety of cultural insights and is at the same time an integral part of an archaeological site of pan-European significance. The elements of the civil and military areas of Carnuntum that have been preserved upright standing and underground to this day are not only a unique testimony to military activity and civil Roman settlement activity on the Austrian Danube Limes, but also evidence of a planned development of the entire region. At the same time, they make it possible to experience the Roman past of eastern Lower Austria.

Two legionary camps were built along the Pannonian Danube Limes in Austria, of which the one in Vienna is located in today's city centre and has been completely built over. The same applies to all the associated military and civilian structures. The same fate is shared by former Roman cities with legionary fortresses in neighbouring Austrian states. Thus, the civilian and military areas of Carnuntum are of unique cultural significance for the area along the middle and upper Danube, even beyond the ancient provincial borders or the present-day state borders.

7.2 Alpine Landscape at Pitschenbergalm, Austria

Andreas Picker

Location and surroundings

The Pitschenbergalm is an alp (high alpine meadow used for seasonal grazing by cattle and sheep) located in the Pfarrwerfen municipality, c.33 km south of the city of Salzburg in the rugged and heavily karstified Tennengebirge range, a part of the Northern Limestone Alps. The only area with enough vegetation for grazing is a valley-like gap running c.4 km north to south at an altitude of 1730-1930 m above sea level. This area is made up of the "outer" Vordere Pitschenbergalm and the "inner" Hintere Pitschenbergalm (Figs.17 & 18), divided by a rocky outcrop (the Windischriedel) at c.1925m above sea level, which holds the only recent man-made building, a hiking hut called the Leopold Happisch Haus. All other agricultural building and fencing structures from prehistory to the 20th century have been abandoned and are (for the most part) still visible as ruins or stone alignments.

Reasons for assessment

From 2012 to 2015, research and archaeological investigations by the Federal Monuments Authority and ANISA, the Association for Alpine Research, led to the identification of a whole series of deserted alpine pastures, which were then surveyed and photo-documented. Small finds and dating of samples (taken mostly from sondages of 20 × 20 cm) allow a chronological assignment of the ruined structures, ranging from the Early Bronze Age (mid-20th to early 18th century BC) to the Modern Age (18th to 19th

century AD). The finds of flint artefacts on the headland of the small pond on the Vordere Pitschenbergalm make it clear that the area was already known to people in the Neolithic period (5th-3rd millennium BC). However, no trend could be attached to these scattered single finds so far. Based on these research results, the Federal Monuments Authority in 2020 placed the Pitschenbergalm on the (purely tentative) list of the highest-ranking archaeological monuments in Austria, as part of an in-house evaluation project. The site was therefore added to the 2021 official annual list of monuments to be assessed for the status of protection by law. Due to unfavourable weather (early snow) in this high altitude, the assessment in the field was carried out in the following summer, which resulted in an expert report on the site's significance. The protection status was proclaimed by notice from the Federal Monuments Authority on 15 November 2022.

Description of site

The relatively remote location of the mountain pasture has favoured the particularly good preservation of the archaeological monuments. A total of 19 prehistoric and historic building structures have been documented. These remains of alpine huts, stables as well as pens, enclosures and a lime kiln have only been known to science for a relatively short time. They are found mostly in places with favourable sunlight and little danger from avalanches, as well as offering dry ground on slightly elevated positions. The structures reveal themselves as dry-set stone layers of limestone, with (in the case of formerly roofed buildings) an approximately rectangular ground plan and openings for the entrance.

Figure 17: Vordere Pitschenbergalm (view to the north). (Andreas Picker).

Figure 18: Hintere Pitschenbergalm (view to the east). (Andreas Picker).

Figure 19: Hintere Pitschenbergalm: Bronze Age U-shaped hut site. (Andreas Picker).

On the Hintere Pitschenbergalm, there is evidence of human activity beginning as early as the Early Bronze Age and continuing into the Late Bronze Age (Urnfield Period). Two hut sites can be identified by heavily abraded, U-shaped ground plans of approximately 5 × 5 m dated to the 14th to 12th century BC (Fig.19). A larger, multi-roomed structure yielded dates from the 20th to 12th century BC, but there is also a late medieval date of the late 13th to early 15th century AD. The prehistoric ruins might have been re-used or made habitable later. Human activities of the Late Iron Age can be attested at the Vordere Pitschenbergalm for the 2nd to 1st century BC. In two cases, rocks or lintel blocks were used as shelter from wind and weather. A rectangular hut ground plan on the Hintere Pitschenbergalm proves that the high alpine site was also in use during the Roman imperial period (late 1st and first half of the 2nd century AD). Both alpine pastures were also used in the early Middle Ages: a two-roomed building with an attached animal pen (at the foot of the Windischriedel) as well as a small structure on the Hintere Pitschenbergalm date to the 7th and 8th centuries AD respectively. The first written document regarding the Pitschenbergalm dates from 1749. This source presumably refers to the building in the northwest of the Hintere Pitschenbergalm, the foundation walls of which are still well preserved above ground (Fig.20). A wood sample from within dates to the early 18th century. The Hintere Pitschenbergalm was already partly abandoned in the second half of the 19th century. The impressive, now ruinous remains of the two-storey house in the north of the Vordere Pitschenbergalm, however, bear witness to the alpine dairy production and hunting grounds of the 19th and early 20th centuries. By 1978, the agricultural installations were no longer in operation.

Figure 20: Hintere Pitschenbergalm: Ruin of the early modern alp hut. (Andreas Picker).

Assessing significance – methods

Based on Austrian monument protection law, the assessment of the monument's "historical, artistic or general cultural significance" is based on "quality, as well as sufficient quantity, diversity and dispersion" and "to what extent a historical documentation can be achieved through the preservation of the monument".

Historical significance

The remains of alpine huts, stables and pens on the Pitschenbergalm date back to those periods in which humans increased seasonal high alpine pasture use and alpine farming in the Eastern Alps: from the Bronze Age, the late Iron Age and Roman periods, the Early Middle Ages and from the Late Middle Ages to the more recent Modern Age. Its outstanding historical significance is due to its long or repeated use through the ages. In a relatively small area, almost four millennia of human activity can be traced. Therefore, the Bronze Age to modern remains of alpine huts, stables and pens on the Pitschenbergalm are of national (or supra-regional) historical significance.

Diversity/Dispersion: Even though remains of deserted buildings and structures on high alpine pastures are quite common in Austria, the Pitschenbergalm stands out among other places. This assemblage of individual objects shows great cohesiveness within a definable space. Also, there are few comparable sites that have been researched and explored so well. For example, nearly all the structures on the Pitschenbergalm have been radiocarbon dated, which results in a concise picture of settlement development. In contrast to other archaeologically dated deserted alps (such as on

the Dachstein plateau or other sites in western Austria), all the periods are well attested in a relatively small area on the Pitschenbergalm.

Historical documentation (scientific potential/perspective): The “historical significance” of the Pitschenbergalm’s remains is not just a general attribution based on intrinsic factors like age and state of preservation. They are valued material sources pertaining to the historical development of seasonal alpine pasture use and therefore form an “archive” in the ground for future scientific research. The remains possess a particularly high degree of intactness and authentic preservation.

General cultural significance (social impact/perception)

The Pitschenbergalm may be regarded as an entire cultural landscape characterised by archaeological monuments, most of which are (partly) visible above ground due to the slow formation of soil. The remoteness of this high alpine pasture, which is still used today for sheep grazing, has led to a good preservation of the archaeological remains. Their situation within a relatively closed micro-landscape between high mountaintops is in itself a defining aspect of the monument, even though purely “natural” elements are not included in monument protection. Despite their remoteness, the archaeological remains are just visible and accessible enough to hikers and small groups of visitors. Therefore, they show great potential as relatable landmarks and identity-forming places to society today.

7.3 Archaeological landscape in Kurese, Estonia

Ulla Kadakas

Location and surroundings

The village of Kurese is in the southwestern part of Estonia, in Pärnu County, Lääneranna Municipality, in the West-Estonian lowlands. The post-glacial land reclamation of the area began around 9300 cal BC. Kurese is in the central-southern part of the lowland, where the lowland lime plains alternate with large swamps and marshes. The lime plains are covered by thin soil (Arold 2005, p.295–308). The village is 20 km from the present coast.

Lääneranna municipality includes seven historical parishes, Kurese village is in the largest of them (Fig.21), Mihkli parish. The area was Christianised at the beginning of the 13th century, but the parish division probably dates to the pre-Christian era, i.e. churches were established in the old centres of settlement.

The centre of the later Mihkli parish in the Late Iron Age was the rural stronghold of Soontagana on a

marsh island, which dates to the 7th–8th centuries and the peak of its use dates from the 11th to the 13th century (Tõnisson 2008, p.266–269). The village of Kurese, the closest settlement to the stronghold, was first mentioned in written sources in 1534, but archaeological evidence suggests that agricultural settlement there began as early as the Bronze Age (1750–500 BCE). From the 8th–9th century onwards, settlement has been continuous (Mandel 2022, p.216–226).

Before World War Two, Kurese had 23 farms. In the post-war years, i.e. during the occupation of the Republic of Estonia by the Soviet Union, there were many resistance fighters, the so-called forest-brothers, living in the Estonian forests. There were also many of them in the Kurese region, which is why the village was hit particularly hard by Soviet repression – most of the inhabitants were deported to Siberia. The village then became deserted, the last inhabitant died in 1973. The village's land was unsuitable for Soviet period large-scale agriculture, and therefore remained unaffected by land improvement.

Figure 21: The map of Lääneranna municipality, historical parishes, and the location of Kurese village.

Today, all the farmhouses in the village are dilapidated, and in the overgrown courtyards only the limestone remains of collapsed stoves and walls can be seen. However, stone fences have been largely preserved and the village road is passable. The village's arable land had been overgrown, but over the last 20 years it has been reclaimed as pasture and kilometres of stone fences have been restored.

Reasons for assessment

Since the end of the 18th century, Soontagana stronghold has been repeatedly described by historians. The first small archaeological excavations were carried out in 1895, but the most thorough excavations were carried out in 1965–1971. At that time, about 400 m² of rampart and courtyard area in the eastern part of the stronghold were excavated. The village of Kuresse is located about 2.5 km south-west of the stronghold, and a historic bog road between the village and the bog island has been preserved.

The Soontagana stronghold was placed under state protection in 1925, a stone grave and a small part of the ancient fields of Kuresse village in 1973 and a cup-marked stone in 1979. A small part of the village of Kuresse was placed under nature protection in 1976 ([Environment Portal](#)), the whole village was listed as landscape reserve in 2007 ([Protection Rules](#) 2007). The purpose of the reserve is to preserve heritage landscapes, habitat types and several protected species.

After the restoration of the Republic of Estonia, property reform took place – real estate seized by the Soviet regime was returned to its rightful owners. It was possible to reclaim the property or receive compensation for it. Land that the rightful owners did not want back could be privatised by others.

The village of Kuresse had been abandoned in its entirety, and it seemed to most of the descendants of the former owners that it would be very hard to restart former land use, so nature conservation specialist Urmas Vahur managed to buy up most of the land in Kuresse. In 1998, the new owner started restoring the marshland – clearing the former hay meadows and pastures from the hedgerow revealed more ancient clearance cairns, stone graves, strongholds, ramparts, and cup-marked stones (Paluoja, 2019). Vahur invited Mati Mandel, an archaeologist from the Estonian History Museum, to help him identify, describe and study the discovered sites. The work started in 2005,

with more in-depth research taking place between 2015 and 2020 (Mandel et al, 2016; Mandel, 2017, 2018, 2019; Mandel and Allmäe, 2021).

Vahur proposed to the National Heritage Board (NHB) already in 2006 to declare the core of the village of Kuresse and the surrounding land as a heritage conservation area, because in addition to the individual monuments, the entire historical structure of the village is uniquely well preserved. At the time, the NHB and the Ministry of Culture did not consider its designation as a heritage conservation area justified, as it was already under nature protection as a landscape conservation area, and they did not wish to apply double protection. However, upon a new application by Vahur in 2015, the NHB started the procedure for the designation of the Kuresse ancient sites as monuments, as the restrictions resulting from the landscape protection area were not sufficient to preserve the special values of Kuresse. For example, it could not be used to regulate the activities of hobby searchers-detectorists. As a result of the lengthy procedure, 26 archaeological sites in the village of Kuresse were entered in the register of cultural monuments in 2018. They, together with the previously protected monuments and the Soontagana stronghold, were granted a common buffer zone of almost 900 hectares.

To summarise, the reason for the reassessment was, on the one hand, the richness and integrity of the archaeological heritage elements discovered during the archaeological survey of the landscape, and, on the other hand, the need to establish rules for detectorists and for possible development, i.e. should there be an interest in using the village land for something other than agriculture. The owner's exceptional persistence in highlighting and presenting the values of Kuresse was certainly a key factor in the whole process.

Legal background of heritage protection in Estonia

Under the Estonian Heritage Conservation Act (HCA), it is possible to declare sites of cultural value as monuments (archaeology, architecture, art, history, technology, natural sites) or to designate heritage conservation areas covering several sites and structures. In Estonia, the medieval town centres and the surrounding Early Modern and Modern suburbs have been recognised as heritage conservation areas,

as well as a rural area near the capital city Tallinn-Rebala, a well-preserved historic-agricultural structure comprising several villages.

In addition, a buffer zone may be established for monuments and heritage conservation areas to ensure that they are preserved in a suitable environment. The constraints on the landowner are greater for monuments and less for the owner of the buffer zone (Fig.22).

As of 2019, the NHB itself is allowed to take archaeological sites into lighter protection as protected archaeological sites. In that case the landowner will only be required to carry out an archaeological survey prior to excavation, and detecting is also prohibited, but the NHB cannot require the preservation of archaeological heritage features. Working out the procedure for the listing of protected archaeological sites took a lot of time for the NHB, which is why the first three protected archaeological sites were listed only in 2023. Accordingly, it is not possible to describe the efficiency of such protection as there is no sufficiently representative practice yet.

However, the HCA lays down an obligation to preserve monuments – everyone must refrain from any activity that may endanger, damage, or destroy a monument. The law also says that a monument may be used in a way that is appropriate for the needs of the modern age, but not in a way that might endanger the preservation of the monument or parts of it.

An archaeological monument is defined by law as remains, things or a set of things of human activity and other traces which indicate the multiple layers of time on a cultural landscape, and which provide scientific information on the history of mankind and human relations with the natural environment. The HCA specifically states that the archaeological cultural layer is an important part of an archaeological monument. Consequently, restrictions on archaeological monuments relate to construction, excavation and other earthworks, as well as felling and afforestation. These activities are not prohibited, but the owner must negotiate the planned works with the NHB and obtain its consent. The NHB must make a judgement on a case-by-case basis as to whether the proposed work

Figure 22: The common buffer zone of archaeological monuments of Kuresse village and Soontagana stronghold and the bog island.

can be carried out without damaging the monument, whether mitigation measures are available (e.g. whether there can be conducted archaeological excavations, but most of the monument still preserve) or whether the owner should refrain from carrying out the work to preserve the monument. The latter is rare, as it is usually possible to find a compromise on the extent of the works or survey, or to move the construction works away from archaeological layers and structures.

Description of site

In the village of Kurese, 26 sites are protected as separate monuments, and the buffer zone includes beside them also the Soontagana stronghold. Among the monuments, the Bronze and the Early Iron Ages (1750 BCE–550 CE) probably include small cup-marked stones, a few stone graves, circular ramparts, but a settlement layer in the village enclosure, a burial place with cremation burials, some of the stone graves, fields banks and clearance cairns, etc., belonging to the Late Iron Age (550–1225 CE).

Assessing significance – methods

The protection arrangement for the Kurese monument complex, i.e. the establishment of such a large common buffer zone, is a rather exceptional case in the practice of archaeological heritage protection in Estonia. In most cases, the environment in which the archaeological heritage elements were created has changed significantly, which is why archaeologists and heritage conservationists deal with the preservation of the landscape's temporal multi-layered character in a rather localised way. An example is the attempt to keep stone graves or cup-marked stones in the middle of historic farmland in urban sprawl areas accessible to the public. For this, they should be retained in recreational areas between new residential blocks. There is no current or foreseeable risk of intensive landscape change in Kurese associated with high population density, but this ancient cultural landscape could be threatened by over-management of forests or fields, as well as by the construction of mines, etc. Hobby treasure hunting (detecting) cannot be regulated without protection measures as well.

The Kurese ancient sites were placed as archaeological monuments under national protection in 2018, i.e. before the entry into force of the new HCA. However, the criteria of assessment had already

been developed by the NHB and were used as a basis for the assessments of the Kurese monuments – their age, location, scientific value and uniqueness of information, prominence and distinctiveness, continuity of function, written sources and educational value, and preservation. The Order of the Minister of Culture for the listing of the sites states: 'The Kurese complex is an invaluable resource for the study of Bronze Age and Iron Age society, religion, economy and life. It is possible to study the relationships between burial places, fortresses, settlements and cult sites, and their position in the society and way of life of the past. The Kurese complex is of high scientific and cultural value.'

An archaeological heritage element identified by archaeologists does not have to meet all the criteria listed above to qualify as a monument, as even a partially preserved monument provides scientific information about the history of mankind and man's relationship with the natural environment (see definition of monument). At Kurese it is possible for everyone to appreciate the multiple layers of time on a cultural landscape and for archaeologists and environmental scientists to study the various aspects of the extremely well-preserved agricultural landscape dating back to the Bronze Age (Fig.23).

Figure 23: View of the Kurese cultural landscape and archaeological sites from the northeast. Drone photo: Maili Roio (NHB)

7.4 Mapping Archaeologically-sensitive Areas for Municipalities' Comprehensive Plans

Ulla Kadakas

Introduction

Based on the current Heritage Conservation Act (HCA, 2019), elements of the archaeological heritage can be taken under state protection in Estonia as an archaeological monument and it is also possible to designate an area of archaeological value as a protected archaeological site (see section 6.2). The listing procedure for both is time-consuming and labour intensive, and as a result, a large number of certain archaeological sites have accumulated over the past 20 years, which are not yet officially protected (section 6.2, Fig.5), i.e. their existence may not be known to the landowners, but certainly not to planners in local governments or hobby detectorists. This means that all four threats mentioned in the [Valletta Convention](#) (comprehensive planning schemes, natural risks, clandestine or unscientific excavations, and insufficient public awareness) are a daily problem

in Estonia concerning the archaeological sites that are known, but not yet under state protection.

In 2015-2017, an administrative reform took place in Estonia, after which most of the 79 remaining local governments had to adopt a new comprehensive plan, which must assess among other things the possible impact of planning on cultural heritage. The National Heritage Board (NHB) prepared a guide for local governments preparing the comprehensive plan on how to deal with cultural heritage, including archaeological heritage. In addition to instructions on monuments, attention was also drawn to the archaeological heritage which has not yet been protected. The principle is that the sooner one is aware of the heritage when planning landscape changes, the greater the chance of making better and more inclusive choices. As the local authorities were not willing to organise the mapping of the archaeological heritage themselves, the NHB took on this work. Since 2020, to the point of writing, possible archaeologically sensitive areas have been mapped in 57 municipalities (Fig.24).

Figure 24: Municipalities where archaeology-sensitive areas have been mapped. (National Heritage Board of Estonia).

Mapping focus

Places with a clear human impact can be everywhere, but their most likely location can be predicted to some extent. Thanks to the archaeological research carried out so far, archaeologists have an idea of where archaeological sites from different periods are likely to be found. For example, the settlements of Stone Age hunters-fishers-gatherers were concentrated mainly on the banks of water bodies, but over the millennia, former beaches are now often deep inland or, in some places, submerged. In Estonia, farming became the predominant way of life during the Bronze Age – households were located sparsely in the landscape, left behind only a weak cultural layer, and are indicated by cup-marked stones and stone-cist graves. The current settlement pattern in Estonia largely developed during the Late Iron Age (6th-13th century AD), i.e. there is a high probability of finding cultural layers of the households of that time in the existing old villages and their surroundings. The burial tradition that has changed over the millennia has left different types of burial sites in the landscape, the location of which in relation to the habitat can also be predicted. In addition to these, there are also sites in the vicinity of habitats that indicate all kinds of economic activity (ancient field systems, iron smelting and processing sites, etc.). For all these sites, it is better to know in advance their existence, since it is impossible to notice fragments of stone flakes and ceramics or human bones, burnt stones, etc from the excavator. The focus of the mapping is on Stone Age hunter-gatherer and Bronze, Iron Age and medieval agricultural settlements and their burial places (Kadakas et al, 2021).

Mapping method

The mapping of archaeologically sensitive areas is based on a compilation of available data and a map-based analysis, which results in the delineation of areas most likely to contain archaeological features.

The mapping of archaeologically sensitive areas has been made possible thanks to a large amount of preparatory work carried out for other purposes within the framework of various research projects.

The main source is the geoinformation database of Estonian archaeological sites, compiled by the University of Tartu, which for years has collected all available archaeological records, including information from archaeological surveys and stray finds in museum collections, as well as any occasional mentions of archaeological sites in archives or published sources. The Institute of the Estonian Language has compiled a database of place names, which also includes the date of the first mention of the name (in the Estonian context, the oldest written sources start from the 13th century). The NHB collects information on finds discovered by hobby detectorists and the places mainly visited by licenced detectorists²². Historical and current maps are used to analyse the site data. The National Archives of Estonia's public map server has many digitised historical maps from the 17th century onwards and the Estonian Land Board geoportal has current relief maps and aerial photographs from the 1940s-1950s, which provide information on the landscapes before the massive land reclamations during the Soviet occupation.

Purpose and legal framework

The main purpose of the mapping of archaeologically sensitive areas is to inform the public about the archaeological heritage and to create the preconditions for taking this heritage into account in large-scale planning. However, the archaeologically sensitive areas cover quite large territories compared to actual archaeological sites, i.e they are not very precise and include many possible sites as well as "blank" plots in between them. These areas are subject to two somewhat contradictory considerations: 1) their designation must allow to take archaeological sites which are not yet listed into account when planning; 2) their designation must be sufficiently general to prevent looting on these not yet protected sites. The purpose of the mapping is not to give precise estimates of properties, but to indicate broad areas based on archaeological sources, so that during the planning procedure, advice can be sought from the NHB.

²²In Estonia, after completing the training, hobby detectorists can apply for a permit to search from the NHB. During the training, they will be introduced to the nature of archaeological heritage, the main types of finds and how to proceed when they find something. Detectorists are allowed to pick up finds from the ploughed layer, but they are not allowed to excavate in situ finds, which can only be excavated by an archaeologist. Detectorists must inform the National Heritage Board of the search time and the location, and submit a report afterwards.

The setting of special conditions to archaeologically sensitive sites is currently optional for local authorities, as there is no obligation to do so under the current HCA. However, the Planning Act allows to set them and most municipalities, in cooperation with the NHB, have stipulated in their comprehensive plan that, as part of the environmental impact assessment, as well as when initiating detailed plans or granting permission for the construction of a building or complex larger than 500 m², the opinion of the NHB on the need to carry out an archaeological survey in an archaeologically sensitive area is sought. The NHB can then reassess the feasibility of commissioning a preliminary survey or can advise the owner on what could be found during the build and when to inform archaeologists.

Conclusion

The Estonian HCA, essentially referring to the Valletta Convention, provides for two main values of archaeological monuments: they are indicators of the temporal multilayered nature of the cultural landscape (carriers of collective memory) and they provide scientific information on the history of humankind and its relationship with the natural environment. These values are to some extent contradictory: if the monument is intact on the landscape, it plays the role of a time capsule, but we gain information only by exploring, i.e. excavating, but in doing so we are reducing the authenticity of the object in the landscape. Therefore, in assessing archaeological heritage we must constantly consider whether and how much to explore or preserve. However, in decision-making only what is known and what is acknowledged can be considered.

7.5 Raseborg Castle, Finland

Teija Tiitinen, Sari Mäntylä-Asplund

Location and surroundings

Raseborg (Finnish: Raasepori) Castle Ruins are located in the southernmost part of Finland on the coast of the Gulf of Finland. It is about 15 km to east of Tammissaari town and about 100 km southwest of Helsinki (Fig.25). The castle was built on a high rocky hill during a time when the place still was a small island. The island has now merged with the mainland due to post-glacial land uplift. The castle was in use for over two hundred years and during that time major changes both in the environment and landscape happened. It seems that at latest by the 16th century the castle was no longer reachable by large ships. One of the reasons why the castle was abandoned was the loss of its good position near the waterways. Nowadays the castle is surrounded by fields, meadows, and grazing lands. On the southern side of the castle there is the Raseborgså river. Less than a kilometre away to the north there is the Snappertuna hamlet and chapel.

Description of the site

Raseborg castle founded in the 1370s was the administrative, military, and economical centre of Western Uusimaa in the late Middle Ages. The castle and its castellan controlled a province consisting of eight parishes. The founding of the castle took place when Western Uusimaa was transferred under the control of Bo Jossan Grip the Chief Justice of Sweden (Finland was a part of Sweden till the year 1812, forming

the eastern part of the kingdom). The main purpose for the foundation of the castle was to form a strong fortress which guarded the Gulf of Finland and the coast of southern Finland.

Raseborg castle was built in stages. The main castle is joined by two outer castles. It consists of a ring wall with towers at the north and southwest ends (Fig.26). In the 15th century, a rectangular courtyard was formed in the main castle, when series of rooms were built on its east and west sides. At the same time, the horseshoe shaped perimeter wall was doubled and covered with brick. In the 1470s, a round tower was built in the southeast corner. At the beginning of the 15th century at the latest, the castle was surrounded by an underwater piling system, which was built to restrict the landing of the ships in front of the castle walls.

In 1540, King Gustaf Vasa set Raseborg castle under the direct administration of the crown. In those days the castle was in bad condition, and it had lost much of its former importance. Ten years later, the administrative centre was transferred to Helsinki, where a new royal manor, as well as a town, were founded in 1550. Some years later, the old castle was abandoned and was never settled again.

On the eastern and northeastern side of the castle there is a field called Bastuå kern (Fig.27). In test excavations, foundations of buildings and an ancient channel filled with clay and mud layers have been found. The material that has been found in the area consists mostly of imported goods. The interpretation is that a trading area was located there in the late medieval ages.

Figure 25: Location map. The Finnish Heritage Agency

Figure 26: Aerial photo of the area. Photo Vesa Laulumaa, The Finnish Heritage Agency

Figure 27: Bastuäkern was the place where among other things trade happened. It has been abandoned since the beginning of the 16th century and never habited again. Since that it has mainly been used as a grazing area. (Sari Mäntylä, The Finnish Heritage Agency).

Reasons for assessment

Raseborg castle was assessed as part of the Nationally Significant Archaeological Sites in Finland project (VARK) in 2022 (see section 6.3). Raseborg castle is one of eight medieval stone castles in Finland. All the castles from the Middle Ages are situated in the southernmost part of Finland. They were evaluated during the VARK project and all of them have been assessed as nationally significant sites. Raseborg castle is a special case among the castles in Finland because its surroundings have been very well preserved. All the other castles are situated in such places where the modern land use has destroyed at least some parts of their outer yards' area. The outer yard was the place where all the activity – excluding defence and administration – connected to the castle happened. This included activities like handcrafting, iron smithing and trade.

The assessment of Raseborg castle became necessary also due to the disturbance of the area in 2017. Almost

three hundred pits had been made in the vicinity of the castle in spots which had been located by metal detectors. The incident led to a court hearing and a verdict was given in 2020.

Assessing significance—methods

In the beginning of the VARK-project, the criteria for assessing the significance of archaeological sites were created. All the sites were assessed by:

1. cultural-historical significance;
2. archaeological research value;
3. prevalence or rarity;
4. archaeological diversity;
5. environment and landscape; and
6. preservation of the area.

Figure 28: Raseborg castle seen from the north. It was surrounded by the sea until the beginning of the 16th century. Photo Sari Mäntylä, The Finnish Heritage Agency

The evaluation of the objects also included scoring. The evaluation scale varied between 0-2 points or 1-3 points depending on the criteria. A site may thus have received a total of 1-17 points for its archaeological importance. If there were many items of the same type with the same score in the selection phase, some other variables were also considered. For example, if the archaeological site was in a nationally significant landscape area or a nationally significant building heritage area, the site's location might have added to the value of the site. The intention of the inventory is that sites with a nationally significant VARK-status will be preserved in all circumstances in the future and permits to disturb the site will no longer be given (see Section 6.3). However, if a permit is granted, there must be exceptionally good justification for it.

The assessment of the Raseborg area

Cultural-historic significance

Raseborg castle and its surroundings are very significant in terms of cultural history. Its establishment and use are directly linked to Finland's political history and the development of defence strategy in medieval Finland. It is also directly connected to the formation and development of society and its structure.

Score: 3 The area has great cultural-historic significance.

Figure 29: The Raseborgsa river was the only way to reach the castle by boat. Photo Sari Mäntylä, The Finnish Heritage Agency

Research value

Archaeological excavations in the area have been carried out since 1890. Regardless of that, the castle and its surroundings still have great research potential. In the beginning, archaeological research was done as part of restoration work that has been going on since the end of the 19th century. Both restoration and research are still going on. Raseborg castle has also played a key role in the development of restoration methods in Finland. Despite several excavations and criminal activities by amateur metal detectorists, the site still has great research potential.

Score: 3 The area has significant research potential.

Prevalence or rarity

The whole area and the type of the archaeological site is very rare for Finland. There are only a few medieval stone castles in Finland and compared to the other castles the surroundings of Raseborg castle have been exceptionally well preserved. Because it was abandoned in the late medieval ages it was preserved from later activity and heavy modern land use. This means it is a rarity in Finland.

Score: 3 The site is very rare.

Archaeological diversity

Raseborg castle and the outer yard which are essentially related to each other are both relatively versatile both in their structures and their findings. Together they are corresponding to a medieval city in their nature.

Score: 3 High degree of diversity.

Environment and landscape

The landscape around the castle is relatively well preserved even though the castle has been a part of the continent for centuries, unlike during the time when it was built. At the beginning of the 14th century, the area still was an island but there still are such elements in the environment which support the understanding of the site and why the castle was built exactly there.

Score: 2 There still are ancient features in the environment and the landscape (Figs.28 & 29).

Degree of preservation

The Raseborg area is known for its well-preserved outer yards which were abandoned already during the late medieval period and never habited again. Severe damage to the area was done in 2017 when amateur metal detectorists dug almost three hundred pits there, but luckily most of the structures remained untouched. Otherwise, it has remained much in the same condition in which it was abandoned almost five hundred years ago. The surroundings of the castle have never been cultivated because the stoniness of the ground. Instead of that, the area has been grazed which has kept the area pretty much open.

Score: 2 Fairly well preserved

Raseborg castle received 16 points out of 17 in the assessment. There were several reasons why it was selected to the collection of nationally significant archaeological sites. The site is a unique example in Finland of a well-preserved medieval stone castle and with an outer yard. Together they form a rare and significant whole. Even though there have been numerous archaeological excavations during the 1800-1900 centuries, there are still large areas that have not been excavated or otherwise damaged. Its archaeological value is unique in Finland. In the evaluation also the fact that it is located in the area of a nationally significant built cultural heritage site and in a Nationally Valuable Landscape Area has been taken to account.

7.6 The Vrouw Maria wreck, Finland

Sallamaria Tikkanen, Maija Matikka

Location and surroundings

The wreck of the Vrouw Maria is located in the northern Baltic Sea in southwestern Finland in Finnish territorial waters approximately 90 km off the city of Turku (Fig.30). The archipelago around the wreck consists of countless islands and islets. The wreck is located at a depth of 41 m in a small dip surrounded by underwater shallows.

The owner of the sea area is the Finnish government land authority Metsähallitus. The wreck is situated in the Natura 2000 area of the Archipelago National Park. The area is also a restricted zone in the national park, in which entry, landing and scuba diving is prohibited all year round without a permit from Metsähallitus.

Since 2006, the wreck has been surrounded by a protection zone based on the Antiquities Act of 1963. The area is circular and has a diameter of 1,500 m. No vessels are allowed to anchor in the protected area and diving is prohibited unless linked to the sea rescue of

a vessel in distress or engaged in research under the permission of the Finnish Heritage Agency. The Border Guard maintains surveillance of the area and the Finnish Heritage Agency monitors the wreck by visual check-ups.

Reasons for assessment

After the discovery of the wreck of the Vrouw Maria in 1999, a wide public discussion about the study, possible raising, museumization and ownership of the wreck rights started immediately. In 2007, the Finnish Heritage Agency published the Vrouw Maria Report. The aim of the report was to give information, background data and different options to cultural political decision-making and to the future of the wreck of the Vrouw Maria. The report was also a source of information to be used when studying the protection, safeguarding, research and display of underwater cultural heritage. An important part of the report was the evaluation of the cultural-historical significance of the Vrouw Maria.

Figure 30: Location map. (Finnish Heritage Agency).

Figure 31: The bow of the wreck of the Vrouw Maria seen from above. (Jouni Polkko, Badewanne team 2019).

Figure 32: An artist's view of the wreck of the Vrouw Maria in its underwater environment at the depth of 41 metres. Underwater rocks are shown behind the wreck and underwater vegetation in front of the wreck. (Tiina Miettinen, Finnish Heritage Agency).

The wreck of the Vrouw Maria was reassessed as part of the Nationally Significant Archaeological Sites in Finland project (VARK) in 2022 (see section 6.3).

Description of site

The hull of the wreck is approximately 26m long and 7m wide. The masts rise to a depth of 22–24 m. Parts of the structure and the rig lie on the seabed around the wreck (Figs.31 & 32).

The Vrouw Maria was a Dutch merchant ship on her way to St Petersburg from Amsterdam. The Vrouw Maria is one of the few wreck sites in the Gulf of Finland that has been identified with certainty based on archival sources. She started her last voyage in early September 1771 and passed the Danish custom station in Sound on 23 September. According to the Sound customs register her cargo included zinc, dyestuff, sugar, coffee beans, cloth, mercury, cheese, butter and some valuable pieces of art and silver. Some of the art was bought for the Russian Empress Catherine the Great. The ship got lost in the Gulf of Finland and ran aground. The ship did not sink immediately, and the crew tried to save her and her cargo for several days. Some silver and pieces of art were salvaged, but most of the cargo was lost when the ship finally sank. After her loss there were

attempts to find her for salvaging the lost goods. The attempts failed and the ship was forgotten for more than 200 years.

The Vrouw Maria's story was known from archive sources since the 1970s and several divers tried to locate the wreck without succeeding. An association called Pro Vrouw Maria managed to locate the wreck in 1999 by using side scan sonar. The wreck was investigated in 2001–2004 as part of the international MoSS project (Monitoring, Safeguarding and Visualizing North-European Shipwreck Sites). The other active research period took place in 2010–2012 during the Finnish Heritage Agency project "Vrouw Maria under Water".

Assessing significance – methods

According to the Finnish Antiquities Act, a wreck is automatically protected by the act, if the wreck can be supposed to have sunk more than a hundred years ago. The cultural-historical significance of wrecks does not need to be defined separately in more detail. When deciding on the use of limited resources, however, prioritization must be done, so it is about choosing what to study. For prioritization, the cultural-historical significance of a site should be defined based on the agreed criteria.

Figure 33: An artist's view of the wreck of the Vrouw Maria based on photos of the wreck. (Tiina Miettinen, Finnish Heritage Agency 2004).

Definition is a mechanism by which the significance of an object is evaluated and described based on selected criteria. Finally, a summary is made of the described values. The definition also includes a comparison of the object with other similar objects at the local, regional, national and international levels. It is a difficult task to develop generally acceptable evaluation criteria suitable for the mutual comparison of ancient remains. Using these criteria is also tricky. The evaluations are never final, but always relative, because they only discuss the current situation. New targets may change the ranking order.

At the time the Vrouw Maria was found in 1999, the Finnish Heritage Agency did not have a broader evaluation method for determining the significance of archaeological sites and objects. The only officially used evaluation system was a three-level classification, where objects were classified into categories 1–3. In this system the Vrouw Maria was classified as a first-class archaeological site, which meant that the wreck was nationally significant, and its preservation must be secured under all circumstances. To determine the significance of the Vrouw Maria in more detail, a new system was created. In creating this new system and suitable criteria, the following existing systems were used as examples where applicable: the criteria developed under the international maritime archaeological MoSS Project (2001–2004), the ICOMOS Australia's [Burra Charter](#) criteria (ICOMOS Australia, 2013), and the Advisory Committee on Historic Wreck

Figure 34: Anchor on the port side of the wreck near the bow. (Jouni Polkko, Badewanne team 2019).

Sites criteria. On the basis of these three systems, the aesthetic and experiential value and condition of the site, the ship type of the wreck and the shipbuilding historical value, the typicality of the ship type of the wreck and/or the rarity, volume and variation of the wreck's material, as well as the historical value of the wreck were determined. The Vrouw Maria was evaluated on the basis of the selected criteria in collaboration with many experts, then described in full and in a shorter summary.

The evaluation process shows that in the cultural-historical sense the wreck of the Vrouw Maria is of great significance both nationally and internationally. The wreck is exceptionally well preserved; approximately 90% of the hull is preserved as well as the rigging. The Vrouw Maria represents a typical snow rigged merchant vessel of its time, the end of the 18th century. These ships sailed the Baltic Sea with a cargo of miscellaneous goods. There is only one other snow rigged ship known from the end of the 18th century that is as well preserved as the Vrouw Maria. That ship, the Sjöhästen, located in Swedish territorial waters, was a war ship and thus differs from the Vrouw Maria. What makes the cultural-historical importance of the Vrouw Maria even greater is the volume and variation of the wreck's findings, the possible art treasures that were on their way to Catherine II of Russia, and the number of archive materials and historical persons connected with the ship.

The assessment

When the wreck of the Vrouw Maria was reassessed in 2022 during the VARK project, the following criteria were used and the significance of the wreck was described in the following way:

Cultural-historic significance

The ship is a merchant vessel commonly used in 18th-century traffic in the Baltic Sea. The wreck is a concrete manifestation of an important sea route and trade between Russia and Western Europe.

Score: 3 = significant potential.

Research value

Since its discovery in 1999, the wreck has been studied mainly with non-destructive methods. Only a few objects have been lifted and no large-scale excavations have been carried out. The wreck has a lot of research potential both in terms of shipbuilding and cultural-historical artefacts. It is known that the ship's cargo contained, e.g., works of art and art objects purchased for the Empress of Russia.

Score: 3 = significant potential.

Prevalence or rarity

There are approximately 70 wrecks or wreck parts in the Finnish Heritage Agency register of ancient sites and monuments, which are assumed or known to date from the 18th century. Only a minority of them have a well-preserved hull and contain plenty of cargo and objects.

Score: 3 = very rare or common.

Archaeological diversity

The wreck is located in the outer archipelago area, where three other historic shipwrecks are known to exist within a 5 km radius of small islets.

Score: 2 = diverse.

Environment and landscape

The wreck is located in the outer archipelago, in an area whose environment and underwater landscape has not been changed by construction projects. The location is in the Archipelago National Park and nature reserve. The hull rests in a small depression surrounded by rocky islets, where the depth is about 41 m.

Score: 2 = there are features in the environment and the landscape making it easier to understand the site.

Degree of preservation

The hull is well preserved and most of the cargo remains in the ship's hold. Only a part of the cargo could be saved after running aground. The lower parts of the masts are upright (Figs.32 & 33).

Score: 3 = well preserved.

Overall, the Vrouw Maria received 15 points out of 18 in the assessment. The wreck was nominated for the list of nationally significant archaeological sites as a well-preserved wreck of a merchant ship related to 18th century international trade shipping in the Baltic Sea, with great research potential.

7.7 More than a funeral, the protection of tumuli in Hungary

Melinda Koller, Katalin Wollák

Introduction

Based on Hungarian practice since 2010, preliminary archaeological documentation should be prepared before large-scale developments. This documentation process can be divided into different phases depending on the nature of projects. Risk analyses are carried out as the first phase of documentation in cases of long-term development – for example new motorways, bypass roads or industrial parks. This phase consists of data collection and classification of known archaeological sites. The following four categories are used for classification:

- Risk 1 has impact which threatens the realisation of the investment, in this case the impact reduction strategy is avoidance. Legally-protected archaeological sites and architectural heritage features preserved in situ belong to this category.
- Risk 2 may endanger the realization of the investment or require a lot of costs and time, so the risk management is also avoidance. This situation applies to sites where there is potential for archaeological elements to emerge which need preserving.
- Risk 3 does not endanger the realization of the investment, but it requires costs and time. Therefore, preventive excavation is used to reduce the impact. In these cases full-surface excavations are employed.
- Risk 4 has minimal cost and time requirements, the risk management means archaeological observation, which is the other type of preventive excavation.

In the next phase non-destructive methods are carried out, firstly with field surveys. At this time the project is still in the design stage, and it is possible to make particular adjustments. Certain types or parts could be avoided depend on the importance of the archaeological sites – especially built heritage, such as a Roman villa, a medieval church ruin and surrounding cemetery, tumulus, hillfort or other types of monuments.

There are thousands of tumuli [kurgans] in Hungary dating from the Late Copper Age to the Roman period. The first appearance of these phenomena in the Late Copper Age/Early Bronze Age (3400-2800 BC), was connected to the nomadic peoples of the Yamnaja culture who came from Central Asia. The medieval Kun population was the last community to build mounds in the Great Hungarian Plain, but these can be found in smaller numbers. Many of the mounds have been ploughed up or partially removed due to material extraction. For example, of the 366 mounds known from the Százhalom site in Százhalombatta which surround the Middle Bronze Age to Late Iron Age fortified settlement, many are now only visible on geophysical surveys or aerial photographs, because of agricultural cultivation.

These cultural monuments are not simply graves or archaeological sites, but complex phenomena that are associated with historical legends, folk traditions and beliefs. They stand as landmarks next to streams, ancient roads, along old and occasionally still existing borders (e.g. settlement or county borders). They were also popularly used in later periods as communal or ritual places, mainly for burial purposes, and often churches were built on them during the Árpáadian Age. Although there are single kurgans, most of them are in pairs, or in small, loose groups, in line, or dense groupings. It is common to find one or more smaller kurgans next to a taller one. The importance of the tumuli for nature conservation – primarily botanical – is also outstanding, as valuable plant associations and ancient steppe vegetation (species-rich loess vegetation) have survived on the surface of the less disturbed kurgans.

In many cases of large-scale developments, the planning areas contain kurgans which can be easily identified with the naked eye. But although the mounds often have landscape significance, most of them do not enjoy outstanding or enhanced archaeological protection.

Short description of the legal system

There is a long tradition of cultural heritage regulation in Hungary, with the first law on the protection of historical monuments dating back to 1881. In the Act of 1929, there is the first mention of prohibited areas: those significant archaeological sites where excavations can only be carried out under appropriate conditions. The current Act on the Protection of Cultural Heritage and its accompanying regulations were adopted in 2001 and have undergone several amendments since then. According to the regulation archaeological sites can be classified into three categories: protected sites (with outstanding or enhanced significance), registered sites and potential sites (Fig.35). Protected sites are subject to additional legal procedures to registered sites: they are identified, verified by professional tools and entered in the central, official register and are subject to general protection by the force of law. Nearly 3% of the registered sites in Hungary are protected .

The Act on Nature Conservation (1996) also provides protection for earthworks, tumuli and caves (e.g. the register contains 1548 tumuli), most of which, however, are not subject to archaeological protection.

The most important instrument for determining significance in the past decades has been the declaration of a site as protected, whereby scientific documentation of the site's values was prepared, followed by a proposal to classify the site to outstanding (national-international significance) or to

enhance protection category (regional significance). The reinforcement of protection through legal instruments ensured that these sites should be avoided by developments. A protection strategy was developed in the early 2000s, identifying the most important types of sites: 1.Prehistoric settlements, 2.Prehistoric and Early Middle Age fortifications, 3.Prehistoric and Roman Age burial mounds, 4.Roman Age forts, medieval castles, 5.Roman and medieval towns, 6.Roman Age villas, 7.Medieval churches, monasteries, other stone buildings, 8.Other sites (e.g. settlements of the Migration Period or the Middle Ages, cemeteries with particularly large number of grave goods, etc.).

The following criteria were taken into account during the evaluation: the uniqueness of the archaeological/historical value, its place among similar archaeological monuments of the period, the existence of one or more periods, its rarity, its extent, its richness of finds, its vulnerability to erosion and its tourist attractiveness. In justified cases, archaeological buffer zones and/or option for public pre-emption were determined. However, the importance of the archaeological sites was evaluated on a case-by-case basis and the protection categories (regional or national importance) are not clarified in a transparent evaluation system.

Since the second half of the 2010s, the role and function of the protection has been declining, with no new protection decree since 2017. The 2018 regulation extended the circle of sites that should not be disturbed by developments: in addition to sites declared protected, sites of registered landscape importance and archaeological monuments/architectural heritage features preserved in situ in their original context without physical deterioration should be avoided by investments (Figs.36 & 37).

A new archaeological strategy which is under elaboration, also indicates that the designation-protection and classification of sites must be based on a new basis, taking into account the aspects of social benefit. This case study illustrates how preliminary archaeological documentation can help in the long-term preservation of significant sites.

Figure 35: Site categories (prepared by K Wollák)

Figure 36: Registered Hungarian sites (prepared by L. Reményi).

Figure 37: Protected Hungarian sites (prepared by A. Bődöcs).

Location and surroundings

The archaeological site, Füzesgyarmat – Bárδος-halom is situated on the Great Hungarian Plain, in the lowland, on the Dévaványa plain. This area is located between two rivers, the Hortobágy-Berettyó and the Körösök. The Bárδος-, or as it was formerly called Bárda-kurgan stands on the south-east bank of an ancient bend of the Berettyó river, now called Bárda-stream, in an agricultural area.

Most of the tumuli on the Great Hungarian Plain are built on the high banks of rivers and watercourses, often on the highest points of the waterless zones. So far, 74 kurgans are known from the Füzesgyarmat area, and 20 of them still have landscape importance.

Numerous tumuli surrounding the Bárδος-kurgan are lined up along the Bárda-stream (Fig.38).

Reasons for assessment

The planned track of the M47 motorway would have passed through the Bárδος-kurgan. Initially, a field survey of the sites affected by the infrastructure project examined the built heritage and archaeological sites of high archaeological risk, so that there was a chance to avoid them in the planning phase. In constant consultation with the designers, it was possible to modify the route of the track (Fig.39). Thanks for this protocol the planned road would avoid completely the kurgan itself.

Figure 38: The Bárδος-kurgan and its surrounding area with other tumuli on the First Military Survey Maps (1782-85) (drawn by M. Koller)

Figure 39: M47 motorway through the archaeological site of Bárδος-halom. The previous line – magenta, and the new one – blue (drawn by M. Koller)

Description of the site

The height of the tumulus is 2.7m, the longer diameter is 75m, the shorter 55m and it is under agricultural cultivation. In the Füzesgyarmat microregion this is one of the biggest mounds, its character remarkably well preserved despite the fact that it is ploughed (Fig.40).

In 2019, an archaeological site was identified around the mound that was inhabited through several archaeological periods – Neolithic, Copper Age-Early Bronze Age, Iron Age, Sarmatian, Avar, Árpáadian Period and Late Middle Ages. The site also includes a smaller, nameless kurgan, and nearby, about 210 m west of the Bárδος-kurgan, there is another small mound (Fig. 41). The surrounding archaeological site, which appears to be intense on the surface, could not be avoided by the planned investment, because the area is rich in hydrocarbons and is being exploited in the deeper eastern area outside the site.

Assessing significance – methods and results

Tumuli like these should be assessed primarily for their role in the landscape and for the aspect of nature protection, because these are the best way to ensure their practical conservation. Therefore certain categories can be established for the ranking of tumuli based on their large number and different condition, further their historical and landscape value.

Figure 40: The Bárδος-kurgan from South in 2009 (source: Bede 2014,166.)

The first category are significant kurgans which are defining landscape features in terms of their size and appearance, and further preference for their categorisation is the vegetation on them – for example natural plant associations, ancient grassland, etc. – and also other historical values such as a medieval church or cemetery. These features should be avoided by development and preferably be declared a protected archaeological site. The tumuli of the second category are more disturbed so they cannot dominate the landscape, are no longer considered to be significant.

Figure 41: Bárδος-halom and the archaeological site in its vicinity. Result of the intensive field survey supported by GPS (drawn by M. Koller)

Destroyed mounds form a further category, which have either been completely ploughed or removed, so that the above surface part has been destroyed, but the central burial remains below ground. A variant of this is where both the burial and the mound is completely destroyed. The last two categories can be excavated with full-surface excavation, however the completely destroyed kurgans can be documented by archaeological observation.

Conclusions

Economic interests usually do not take archaeological heritage into account. But occasionally, heritage management can intervene to accomplish the following goals:

- The significant kurgans or other heritage values are not damaged, destroyed or covered by the investments.

- Different types of protection can be extended to same site, for example the cooperation with nature conservation institutions can successfully be used on archaeological sites, especially on kurgans (Fig.42).
- Arousing the interest of local communities usually works in the case of visually significant archaeological sites.

Possible equipment of the heritage management consists of:

- constant communication with designer offices
- collaboration with nature conservation institutions
- education (presentation) and interaction with local communities in frames of community archaeology.

Figure 42: Ancient steppe vegetation on Szálka-kurgan in Hortobágy National Park (source: <https://hu.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kunhalom#/media/F%C3%A1jl:Szalkahalom.jpg>)

7.8 The Pilis Mountains and the Szentendre Island Programme, Hungary

József Laszlovszky, Tibor Ákos Rác

Introduction

This case-study provides a methodological proposal for the process of assessing archaeological significance, considering not only the academic importance and the protection of archaeological sites, but also the social implications of cultural heritage with the help of a community archaeology pilot project. Building on earlier developments, from the 1960s a major archaeological programme, the Archaeological Topography of Hungary introduced a complex system for mapping and interpreting sites. This project delivered continuous methodological development, including survey techniques, documentation, and interpretation of sites. However, the assessment of significance in the context of mapped and identified archaeological sites cannot be seen in a similar way in these processes. Various factors were taken into consideration in the context of academic research, such as the importance of finds from a site, or standing monuments at a site, but no standard system has developed for these aspects. In addition, there is no transparent protocol in the evaluation system (see section 7.7 for outline of Hungarian legal system) which would be desirable both for academic research, and in the context of contract archaeology.

To date, Hungarian archaeology has not applied any prioritisation in its excavation strategy during development led or contract archaeology projects. The principle applies that everything must be explored. Investors are bound by law to finance the excavation of affected sites, more precisely the part of the site affected by the building operations. A recent legislation introduced the principle of covering archaeological sites of less importance. However, the assessment of the importance depends on the actual and highly variable circumstances and is not based on factual information. A generally applied and well-structured system is highly needed, not only to determine the fate of sites impacted by development, but also for scientific reasons. The system should be designed to help scholars in deciding on the extent and methodology of their excavations, and also the arrangements applied after the accomplishment of the fieldwork: conservation of unearthed elements, covering the walls, or presentation

of the results on-site.

In Hungary, museums with archaeological collections and excavation rights operating under regional competences have the closest connection with archaeological sites. New information is regularly added to the museum repositories and frequently provided to investors for developments or to central research institutes for their research projects. Therefore, it is essential to keep the information on the extent, intensity, or importance of sites up to date. Collecting, storing, and sharing data, interpreting archaeological heritage is an increasingly complex responsibility. Supervision of archaeological sites is the task of the cultural heritage authority (government office), however, neither museums, nor the authority have enough resources for this. At the same time, the growing importance of community archaeology in Hungary offers now new possibilities to meet these challenges.

The scheme of the project presented here has been developed based on the Hungarian legal system, the daily practice of a museum with a strong programme in community archaeology, and with the goal to develop a standardized, but flexible system, which can be followed by similar organisations. The new system uses practice-based solutions, the assessment process has been tested in a pilot project at an important historical and archaeological region with diverse archaeological sites.

Reasons for the assessment

The regional museum of Pest County frequently faced the above-described problems and discrepancies during its field operations. Particularly the regular control of archaeological sites has created growing problems in a period when development-led archaeological programmes occupy most of the working hours of the archaeologists of the museum. Therefore, the museum requested aid in 2021 from the Community Archaeology Association in regularly monitoring archaeological sites. This also offered an opportunity to invite volunteers of the association to take part and to contribute to heritage protection in a meaningful way. Furthermore, members of the association were able to develop their skills in

detecting, surveying, and interpreting archaeological sites with the guidance of expert archaeologists. A survey was thus realised in 2022 within the frames of an experimental community archaeology programme with volunteers and students. The project provided an excellent opportunity to classify the sites under supervision and draw methodological conclusions on the assessment process.

The starting point was a programme of ten field events to research archaeological sites (with outstanding or enhanced significance) under special protection in Pest County using modern site diagnostics methods. The programme focused on surveying the condition of the sites, concentrating mainly on gathering data on already known archaeological sites, rather than discovering new ones. The work was a collaboration between the Cultural Heritage Studies Programme of the Central European University (CEU, Budapest-Vienna), archaeologists from the Ferenczy Museum Centre of Pest County (Szentendre) and a research project by the Community Archaeology Association. Representatives of the authority also participated in several field events.

Location and surroundings

In the frame of this experimental community archaeology programme, the Pilis Mountains and the Szentendre Island was chosen for multiple reasons: these regions are easy to access from Budapest, which was important as most participants lived in the capital or close to these areas. Furthermore, the region played a key role in various historical periods. Important fortified prehistoric hilltop sites can be found in the inner area of the Pilis Mountains, with long research history on their archaeological heritage. In Roman times, the construction of the Danubian Limes, a defensive system along the river, brought about the emergence of a chain of fortifications (burgi and castra). During the Middle Ages, the region became part of the Medium Regni, the central and most developed area of medieval Hungary that comprised four of the five royal seats. The exceptional settlement network that had emerged in the area included clusters of administrative seats, monasteries, and royal estates. The region is rich in archaeological sites of different periods, preserved in various conditions and subject to archaeological fieldwork for a long time, but with significant potential for further research. During the field trips 21 archaeological sites were surveyed, 11

Figure 43: Archaeological fieldwork and metal detector-aided survey at Pomáz, Kő-hill. On-site introduction of the archaeological site for the participants of the project. (Rácz, T.)

of which were under special protection. Significant amounts of new finds were recovered from eight sites and data on the extents of six was updated.

The research project ran under the name of OpenHeritage (a project supported by the Horizon2020 scheme), and it was conducted within the frames of the CEU Cultural Heritage Studies programme. It studied how local communities can be involved in protecting cultural heritage by developing the cultural heritage site at Pomáz– Nagykovácsi-puszta for local education and cultural tourism purposes. One of the aims was to understand the perspectives of civilians regarding the importance of archaeological sites. On every occasion open lectures by leading experts of the relevant archaeological period were organised for volunteers (Fig.43), and after the lectures field surveys were conducted, where new information on the condition and scientific potential of the sites was gained. The detailed descriptions were in fact assessments of the cultural values of different locations. The core activities were archaeological fieldwork and metal detector-aided survey as well as droned-based aerial photography and high-precision (RTK) geodetic surveys when necessary. Photo documentation, accurate description on the state of locations was completed.

Assessing significance – methodological considerations

While preparing the assessment several aspects needed to be considered. A system of criteria suitable for practical application and valid for different kinds of sites needed to be created, where the differences could be expressed in a measurable form. These needed to include all scientific aspects possible and besides that, the special aspects of local communities and volunteers. Furthermore, the study also took into consideration social values and benefits in the context of archaeological site evaluation. Setting the criteria and their application is of course subjective, depending on the experience and knowledge of the surveyor and always valid in a particular relational system. It is desirable for the surveys to be conducted by a team, discussing the issues raised and summarising the views of the participants.

The evaluation system used in the project was conceived in the form of a spreadsheet, containing a wide range of criteria, grouped into 5 larger units. The

individual characteristics were marked with points ranging from 0 to 3 in accordance with the lower or higher degree of validity regarding the site. The more data available on the site the more accurate the assessment will be. From experience during the pilot project, it is highly recommended to complete the assessment while visiting the site. It requires significant preparation before the site visit, as the assessment takes also into consideration the previous archaeological research. If there had been previous field research projects, excavations, or field surveys, one can make the assessment with high precision.

The first part of the evaluation estimated the scientific significance of the site. Standard categories used in archaeological research and heritage assessment were listed: general characteristics of the site, like the level of preservation, rarity and uniqueness of the site, complexity of archaeological phenomena. Particular attention was paid to the research potential of the site i.e. the importance of the site for future investigations based on the recovered archaeological finds and features, the available academic results and scholarly interpretations, and the present condition of the archaeological heritage at the site. The assessment continued with the individual features and finally concentrates on the finds.

The second unit dealt with the cultural heritage significance. Here broader heritage aspects were listed, like historical narratives or connection to natural heritage values which have the capacity to enhance the value of a site. Elements of built heritage for example have a great and lasting impact on the appearance of the site. Mentions of an archaeological site in literary works (poetry, drama) relate to a special status, values which are obvious for non-archaeologists also. These aspects are particularly important in the case of places and sites which can be associated with great historical events, like a battle, or are connected to great historical figures. Additional points were given for the presence of religious locations, churches for example.

The next unit displayed key aspects for the protection of the site, forming a summary of a risk assessment expressed in points, including short- and long-term factors, and among them human and natural causes. An inverse evaluation was applied: the more endangered is the site, the more points it gets, bearing in mind that the appraisal might contribute to its protection. Volunteers and local communities could add several new aspects to the values of cultural heritage locations,

Figure 44: Bronze Age sword. Pomáz, Kő-hill. (Rácz, T.)

which must also be considered during the assessment of sites. Local awareness of the site, local historical events, legends, memorials, statues represent non-scientific considerations, but create living connections between a community and a historical location.

The last section explored the possibilities of 'valorisation': income generating possibilities, like tourism, or social benefits with particular emphasis on educational aspects. This involves the interpretation of the site. Furthermore, conditions and infrastructural aspects of a visit were also taken into consideration, including recreational possibilities, facilities and infrastructure (toilets). Accessibility and available information at the site on the archaeological heritage meant additional points for the site.

Description of the sites

Four archaeological sites of different ages and of very different character (fortification, settlement, church, and a hoard) were selected for the survey, to demonstrate the complexity of the assessment process, and they were also used as test cases to see the applicability of the spreadsheets used in the pilot project.

The first site was the fortified hilltop settlement at Pomáz, Kő-hill, which is an important prehistoric complex in the region with a long research history. The natural heritage of the site is its most attractive element, and it is a popular hiking place for visitors from Budapest. The archaeological features (earthworks, terraces) are parts of the natural landscape, but they are not presented for the wider public (no information display at the site). Social events are also organized here. An annual memorial event takes place each year on 15 March to commemorate

the 1848 revolution. This is connected to the fact that a renowned nineteenth century poet, Sándor Petőfi, wrote a poem here, and he was also a key figure of the revolution and of the war of independence in 1848-49. During the survey a great quantity of Bronze Age pottery and one of the best finds of the whole campaign, a Bronze Age sword, was found here (Fig.44). The project also contributed to a survey of the site which extended the boundary of the archaeological features.

Figure 45: Finds of a metal detector-aided survey at Budakalász, Dunai Kisföldek (Havas, V.)

Figure 46: The remains of a medieval monastic manorial complex at Pomáz, Nagykovácsi-puszta, with the finds of a metal detector-aided survey. (Harmath, A.)

The second example represents a depot from Budakalász, Dunai Kisföldek. This was discovered by chance in the context of the condition assessment of an adjacent site under special protection, when metal detector survey was carried out in a small grassland area. In 1954, only a fragment of a Roman milestone was found here, but surprisingly during the project, in addition to a few bronze coins, some 60 Roman brooches and brooch fragments were unearthed, as well as a Celtic coin (Fig.45). It is assumed that the brooches and other accessories refer to a hidden treasure trove or a Roman cemetery. This is a major change in knowledge of the site, and the academic research potential of the archaeological features below the surface is now much bigger, compared to previously.

The third site represents a different archaeological heritage and a complex research history. Ruins in the area of Pomáz, Nagykovácsi-puszta have been recorded since the nineteenth century. They were identified as medieval, but the function and the identification of the remains of a stone-built building complex was very much debated. During the last fifteen years complex investigations (field survey, remote sensing, landscape archaeology, environmental archaeology, building survey, excavation, etc.) were carried out at the site and in the area around the ruins. Parts of a complex water system, traces of agricultural fields, iron and glass production were identified. The church and the workshop

Figure 47: Visegrád, Sibrik-hill. Remains of the Roman and medieval fortification. (Buzás, G.)

buildings represent a manorial complex connected to a major Cistercian monastery nearby (Fig.46). Research was carried out in the framework of field schools, university educational projects and community archaeology programmes. The present pilot project was also connected to this site, as introductory lectures and educational programmes were organized in the buildings of the modern farm nearby.

Our fourth example, Visegrád, Sibrik hill is a key site for Hungarian archaeological research. It was a Roman fort, and further used by different populations later (Carolingians, Slavs) and rebuilt after the foundation of the Hungarian state. First it became a county centre and while displaying complex forms of settlement development, it was later a royal centre, but the visible remains are less attractive for the general audience. Recent archaeological investigations (geophysical survey, remote sensing, GIS, landscape archaeological studies, etc.) confirmed the exceptional research potential of the site (Fig.47).

Assessing significance – situation report

The spreadsheets (see tables 4-7) display a great variety of factors in the evaluation process. Pomáz, Kő-hill received average values in the general assessment. For the scientific significance we suggested 21 points, while the cultural heritage significance valued only 8 points. It is moderately exposed to destruction and

Figure 47: Archaeological trail at the Pomáz, Nagykovácsi-pusztasite. Remains of the medieval water system. (Laszlovszky, J.)

looting (4 points). It is an important site for the research of a particular archaeological period. It is also highly important for the local community (9 points) but its importance cannot be compared to Visegrád, for example. It offers an excellent location for a complex (archaeological, geological, natural) educational trail with significant amenity values (12 points). The site scored a total of 54 points.

Significantly lower values came out in case of Budakalász, Dunai Kisföldek (a total of 32 points). Both its cultural heritage significance and importance for the local community was worth 0 points. It is an unknown site, without any visible features. The value of the site lies in its uniqueness, its potential for new scientific results and the types of artefacts. The area nearby holds considerable aesthetic values and recreational possibilities; thus, the character of the site can be changed. On the other hand, the danger of looting the site is relevant, as illegal metal detecting can destroy undetected archaeological finds and features.

The archaeological site Pomáz, Nagykovácsi-pusztasite has received a relatively high overall score: 69 points. Compared to the historical significance of the other medieval site in our pilot project (Visegrád, Sibrik-hill: 71 point) this high point of the Pomáz site can

be seen as a surprise. The spreadsheet clearly shows that in this case the scientific importance combined with the research potential and the social benefits of the site made up together this high figure. The relatively unknown research topics (monastic manorial complexes, medieval glass production) make this site unique. The educational and community archaeology programmes also create a significant interest for this historical monument. Thus, for the assessment of importance this complex heritage practice should also be taken into consideration, which is also shown in the relatively high figures in cultural heritage importance and amenity values, 14-17 points respectively (Fig.47).

The scientific significance of Visegrád, Sibrik-hill received almost the maximum of points (37 points). Its cultural heritage significance is also above average (15 points). However, cultural heritage interpretation of the site is less developed, it does not show the significance of the site. These aspects are clearly visible in the low values in the social benefit and touristic attraction aspects (11 points). The site is well protected, continuously monitored and researched – it is not exposed to destruction or looting (1 point). It has the potential to enhance public understanding of history in case it would receive infrastructural development. We granted a total of 71 points to the site.

Conclusion

The process of bestowing archaeological sites with a protected status has a long history in Hungary. Between 2004 and 2016, numerous sites were declared protected with an institutional framework. Currently there is no elaborated methodology available to researchers for expressing the value of a site. In our study, we developed a new classification system.

Besides strict scientific approach, several new criteria needed to be added based on the results of our surveys, for example the perspectives of citizen science. A key aspect of our research project was the involvement of non-professionals. Our research has shown that the more information we can obtain about a site, for example through excavation or metal detecting, the more its value increases as its characteristics become identifiable. The disclosure of the values of sites buried, unexplored or unpublished helps scholars to deal with the site according to its real scientific importance and can strengthen the identity of the local communities concerned.

Archaeological sites have different scientific or cultural values. Therefore, their heritage management, research and protection require different procedures. Any

decision can only be taken based on a responsible assessment of the site. The evaluation must be elaborated by experienced scholars intensively working on the respective archaeological sites. This interpretation needs to be harmonized with expectations and different value systems: the perspectives of museums, volunteers, local residents, infrastructural investors must also be included in a scientific assessment of cultural values. Therefore, the proposed scheme is an integration of such different perspectives.

The procedure can have various outcomes. Several sites need extra protection and attention because of imminent destruction. Treasure hunters and illegal metal detectorists had been known to raid archaeological sites prioritized by heritage protection. In other cases, archaeological sites had been endangered by unauthorized construction works by landowners and developers. Others can enhance tourism due to their potential and several locations can be used for educational or recreational purposes. The assessment can provide actionable data for protection and heritage utilization. This scheme can also be further developed by using international best practices and other assessment systems.

TABLE 4: Assessing the significance of the Pomáz, Kő-hill archaeological site

0= non-valid/ no data/ very low. 1= low. 2= average. 3= high.

Scientific significance	0	1	2	3
level of preservation of the site			x	
rarity and uniqueness of the site			x	
complexity of archaeological phenomena			x	
complexity of cultural layers and historical periods			x	
potential for new discoveries and scientific results			x	
complexity of scientific information		x		
importance revealed in published scientific literature or documentation		x		
special conditions (waterlogged, sunken or closed environment)		x		
significance of individual features		x		
representative of a given period or culture			x	
overall quality of archaeological finds			x	
quantity of archaeological objects		x		
diversity of archaeological finds and features			x	
treasure finds, hoards or rare types of artefacts	x			
Evaluation expressed in points		5	16	
Total	21			

Cultural heritage significance (archaeological, historical, architectural)	0	1	2	3
historical city centre or other monumental environment	x			
historical landscape features			x	
natural heritage (nature reserve, biodiversity, geological significance)			x	
association with important historical events	x			
association with important historical figures	x			
mentions in historical sources		x		
presence in historical illustrations		x		
visible built heritage, historic buildings	x			
mentions in literary works (poetry, novel, drama, etc.)			x	
features of art historical importance	x			
cultural practices of a particular society or civilization (intangible heritage)	x			
religious, ceremonial location, proof for ritual practices	x			
Evaluation expressed in points		2	6	
Total	8			

0= non-valid/ no data/ very low. 1= low. 2= average. 3= high.

Exposure to destruction and looting	0	1	2	3
danger of destruction by building operations		x		
danger of destruction by agricultural works	x			
exposure to illegal excavation, looting and vandalism		x		
exposure to illegal metal detecting		x		
erosion and other natural deterioration		x		
Evaluation expressed in points		4		
Total	4			

Importance for the local community	0	1	2	3
local awareness of the site				x
place of remembrance, location of a memorial or statue			x	
local historical events or associated legends			x	
local community events organised on-site			x	
Evaluation expressed in points			6	3
Total	9			

Amenity values (tourism, recreation and education)	0	1	2	3
accessibility			x	
visibility and aesthetic value			x	
connection to other sites or cultural/touristic routes		x		
recreational possibilities			x	
facilities and infrastructure			x	
potential to enhance public understanding of history		x		
potential to understand archaeological heritage		x		
valuable remains for educational purposes		x		
Evaluation expressed in points		4	8	
Total	12			

Overall collected points: 54.

TABLE 5: Assessing the significance of the Budakalász, Dunai Kisföldek archaeological site

0= non-valid/ no data/ very low. 1= low. 2= average. 3= high.

Scientific significance	0	1	2	3
level of preservation of the site	x			
rarity and uniqueness of the site				x
complexity of archaeological phenomena	x			
complexity of cultural layers and historical periods	x			
potential for new discoveries and scientific results				x
complexity of scientific information		x		
importance revealed in published scientific literature or documentation		x		
special conditions (waterlogged, sunken or closed environment)	x			
significance of individual features	x			
representative of a given period or culture			x	
overall quality of archaeological finds		x		
quantity of archaeological objects			x	
diversity of archaeological finds and features		x		
treasure finds, hoards or rare types of artefacts				x
Evaluation expressed in points		4	9	4
Total	17			

Cultural heritage significance (archaeological, historical, architectural)	0	1	2	3
historical city centre or other monumental environment	x			
historical landscape features	x			
natural heritage (nature reserve, biodiversity, geological significance)	x			
association with important historical events	x			
association with important historical figures	x			
mentions in historical sources	x			
presence in historical illustrations	x			
visible built heritage, historic buildings	x			
mentions in literary works (poetry, novel, drama, etc.)	x			
features of art historical importance	x			
cultural practices of a particular society or civilization (intangible heritage)	x			
religious, ceremonial location, proof for ritual practices	x			
Evaluation expressed in points				
Total	0			

0= non-valid/ no data/ very low. 1= low. 2= average. 3= high.

Exposure to destruction and looting	0	1	2	3
danger of destruction by building operations		x		
danger of destruction by agricultural works		x		
exposure to illegal excavation, looting and vandalism		x		
exposure to illegal metal detecting			x	
erosion and other natural deterioration	x			
Evaluation expressed in points		3	2	
Total	5			

Importance for the local community	0	1	2	3
local awareness of the site	x			
place of remembrance, location of a memorial or statue	x			
local historical events or associated legends	x			
local community events organised on-site	x			
Evaluation expressed in points				
Total	0			

Amenity values (tourism, recreation and education)	0	1	2	3
accessibility				x
visibility and aesthetic value			x	
connection to other sites or cultural/touristic routes			x	
recreational possibilities			x	
facilities and infrastructure	x			
potential to enhance public understanding of history	x			
potential to understand archaeological heritage		x		
valuable remains for educational purposes	x			
Evaluation expressed in points		1	6	3
Total	10			

Overall collected points: 32.

TABLE 6: Assessing the significance of the Pomáz, Nagykovácsi-puszta archaeological site

0= non-valid/ no data/ very low. 1= low. 2= average. 3= high.

Scientific significance	0	1	2	3
level of preservation of the site			x	
rarity and uniqueness of the site				x
complexity of archaeological phenomena				x
complexity of cultural layers and historical periods			x	
potential for new discoveries and scientific results			x	
complexity of scientific information				x
importance revealed in published scientific literature or documentation			x	
special conditions (waterlogged, sunken or closed environment)				x
significance of individual features			x	
representative of a given period or culture			x	
overall quality of archaeological finds			x	
quantity of archaeological objects				x
diversity of archaeological finds and features			x	
treasure finds, hoards or rare types of artefacts				x
Evaluation expressed in points			16	18
Total	34			

Cultural heritage significance (archaeological, historical, architectural)	0	1	2	3
historical city centre or other monumental environment	x			
historical landscape features			x	
natural heritage (nature reserve, biodiversity, geological significance)			x	
association with important historical events		x		
association with important historical figures	x			
mentions in historical sources		x		
presence in historical illustrations	x			
visible built heritage, historic buildings			x	
mentions in literary works (poetry, novel, drama, etc.)		x		
features of art historical importance		x		
cultural practices of a particular society or civilization (intangible heritage)			x	
religious, ceremonial location, proof for ritual practices			x	
Evaluation expressed in points		4	10	
Total	14			

0= non-valid/ no data/ very low. 1= low. 2= average. 3= high.

Exposure to destruction and looting	0	1	2	3
danger of destruction by building operations	x			
danger of destruction by agricultural works	x			
exposure to illegal excavation, looting and vandalism	x			
exposure to illegal metal detecting	x			
erosion and other natural deterioration		x		
Evaluation expressed in points		1		
Total	1			

Importance for the local community	0	1	2	3
local awareness of the site		x		
place of remembrance, location of a memorial or statue	x			
local historical events or associated legends	x			
local community events organised on-site			x	
Evaluation expressed in points		1	2	
Total	3			

Amenity values (tourism, recreation and education)	0	1	2	3
accessibility		x		
visibility and aesthetic value			x	
connection to other sites or cultural/touristic routes		x		
recreational possibilities			x	
facilities and infrastructure			x	
potential to enhance public understanding of history				x
potential to understand archaeological heritage				x
valuable remains for educational purposes				x
Evaluation expressed in points		2	6	9
Total	17			

Overall collected points: 69.

TABLE 7: Assessing the significance of the Visegrád, Sibrik-hill archaeological site

0= non-valid/ no data/ very low. 1= low. 2= average. 3= high.

Scientific significance	0	1	2	3
level of preservation of the site				x
rarity and uniqueness of the site				x
complexity of archaeological phenomena				x
complexity of cultural layers and historical periods				x
potential for new discoveries and scientific results				x
complexity of scientific information				x
importance revealed in published scientific literature or documentation				x
special conditions (waterlogged, sunken or closed environment)	x			
significance of individual features				x
representative of a given period or culture				x
overall quality of archaeological finds				x
quantity of archaeological objects			x	
diversity of archaeological finds and features				x
treasure finds, hoards or rare types of artefacts			x	
Evaluation expressed in points			4	33
Total	37			

Cultural heritage significance (archaeological, historical, architectural)	0	1	2	3
historical city centre or other monumental environment		x		
historical landscape features			x	
natural heritage (nature reserve, biodiversity, geological significance)			x	
association with important historical events			x	
association with important historical figures			x	
mentions in historical sources			x	
presence in historical illustrations		x		
visible built heritage, historic buildings		x		
mentions in literary works (poetry, novel, drama, etc.)	x			
features of art historical importance		x		
cultural practices of a particular society or civilization (intangible heritage)	x			
religious, ceremonial location, proof for ritual practices		x		
Evaluation expressed in points		5	10	
Total	15			

0= non-valid/ no data/ very low. 1= low. 2= average. 3= high.

Exposure to destruction and looting	0	1	2	3
danger of destruction by building operations	x			
danger of destruction by agricultural works	x			
exposure to illegal excavation, looting and vandalism	x			
exposure to illegal metal detecting	x			
erosion and other natural deterioration		x		
Evaluation expressed in points		1		
Total	1			

Importance for the local community	0	1	2	3
local awareness of the site				x
place of remembrance, location of a memorial or statue				x
local historical events or associated legends	x			
local community events organised on-site		x		
Evaluation expressed in points		1		6
Total	7			

Amenity values (tourism, recreation and education)	0	1	2	3
accessibility			x	
visibility and aesthetic value			x	
connection to other sites or cultural/touristic routes				x
recreational possibilities		x		
facilities and infrastructure	x			
potential to enhance public understanding of history		x		
potential to understand archaeological heritage		x		
valuable remains for educational purposes		x		
Evaluation expressed in points		4	4	3
Total	11			

Overall collected points: 71.

7.9 Hveravellir in Northern Iceland

Thor Ingólfsson Hjaltalín

Location and surroundings

Hveravellir is a geothermal area situated in a spectacular landscape of mid-highland Iceland, about 600m above sea-level on the Kjölur plateau. The highlands are a vast area of land predominated by mountains, lava fields and glaciers. Because of harsh natural conditions this central part of Iceland is unsuitable for living or residence, except for trolls and other creatures of folktales. Hveravellir is located at the old Kjölur mountain route, connecting south with north and is like an oasis in the deserted landscape and has for centuries served as a resting place for travellers. The geothermal area is about 2.5 km² with boiling pits and hot springs of distinct types and with some grass fields in a small valley with good pasture for horses.

Reasons for assessment

In 2007 the Icelandic government decided to set up working groups of experts in the field of natural sciences and archaeology to evaluate geothermal power plant options in high-temperature areas by assessing the impact of such projects on nature and cultural monuments. A total of 19 hot temperature areas were surveyed, including Hveravellir, where the importance of archaeological remains in the areas was evaluated by score grading. Such an overall assessment of natural and cultural heritage was then used as a basis for whether certain areas were classified for protection or put in the utilization class. The survey of the archaeological remains and evaluation of Hveravellir took place in 2008 (Hjaltalín, 2008).

Legal background of heritage protection in Iceland

According to the Cultural Heritage Act (nr. 80/2012), all archaeological remains in Iceland, older than 100 years, are protected, put in law originally in 1989. This new approach for protection had a significant impact on heritage management and preservation of archaeological remains in the country. By this, two levels of protection were implemented, the “100-year rule” and “listed sites” that enjoy greater protection. The Cultural Heritage Agency of Iceland (Minjastofnun)

may lift such automatic age protection that falls under the “100-year rule”, for example in connection with construction work. The other is a category of listed sites/monuments, which are considered to be of special value. They enjoy special protection in law, and it is the minister of environment that is responsible for their inclusion or omission from that list, usually after consultation with Minjastofnun. The “100-year age rule” ensures that the heritage managers get many different cases for review, but these remains are certainly considered to have very different values. Each case is viewed and evaluated individually and the age of the finds/remains matters in terms of classification into “remarkable” and “less remarkable”. Remains from Viking or Middle Ages are as a rule excavated totally if it is necessary. Less demand is usually made for younger remains, but sometimes they are highly valued. However, there is a need for clearer procedures or classification systems to assist in the decision making.

Minjastofnun sets out the requirements for the necessary survey and research to be undertaken because of development work and decides whether to allow archaeological remains to be removed or not, and under what conditions. The Agency may therefore reject projects if it assesses that the remains have a high value. But if remains are allowed to be removed, then decisions are made under what conditions that can happen and that usually involves some kind of research. How much research will depend on the evaluation of the value of the remains and their potential to provide information. The work is then offered on the general market (which is very small in Iceland). So, it's the free market that calculates the price. The disadvantage of that is that the buyer can always choose the cheapest offer, and possibly this may affect the quality of the research. Minjastofnun must, however, observe that the work is well done and in accordance with the original requirements.

But regarding the listed sites, the process is more complicated than when Minjastofnun lifts the age protection. Minjastofnun takes special care of listed sites, which are around 850 in the whole country. Excavation does not occur at these sites except in exceptional circumstances, e.g. if they are in danger or if there is a need to obtain further information about them. In that case, a thorough research plan must be made. These sites have a 100m sanctuary area around them. Construction or development at

Figure 48: In 1918, a film was made about the lives of Eyvind and Halla by the Swedish director Victor Sjöström (1879-1960), *Berg-Eyvind och hans hustru*, based on a play by the Icelandic playwright Jóhann Sigurjónsson (1880-1919).

listed sites is not allowed except in connection with improving access or providing information about the site, i.e. projects that relate to the sites themselves. The list of the listed sites is currently under review, and ideological work has also started to sharpen the criteria that sites /monuments in this category need to fulfill. Most of the monuments that are on this list were put there around 1930, and their significance was evaluated based on the dominant views in those days. A large proportion of these remains relates to the Viking Age and the Icelandic medieval Sagas. So, there is still a lot of work to do in defining which values sites that are in this category need to have. Today, more emphasis is being placed on protecting cultural environment / landscape that is considered to have high value. A list of protected archaeological sites can be found on the Cultural Heritage Agency of Iceland website.

Description of site

The site of Hveravellir is mentioned in several medieval sources and of later times, sagas, annals, and folklore. Sæluhús (shelter house for travellers) have stood at Hveravellir for centuries. The place is also famous for being a hiding place for fugitives or outlaws, seeking refuge from the authorities. The most famous was Eyvindur Jónsson (1714-1783), or the legendary Mountain-Eyvind and his wife Halla who were on the run from sheriffs for decades because of theft. They managed to survive in the harsh conditions of the Icelandic highlands and their lives have become a source of inspiration for poets and artists, playwrighters

Figure 49: The hot spring stove of Mountain Eyvind. In the background is Eyvind's hut, hidden in a "lava bubble". (Thor Hjaltalín 2008).

and filmmakers (Fig.48). Today Hveravellir attracts tourists in the summertime but in winter the area is hardly accessible.

A total of 19 archaeological remains were recorded in the Hveravellir area. Ten of them were cairns, while nine are relics of a different kind. The remains were classified into three categories.

In the first category are remains that can be linked to the presence of outlaws in the area. The four ruins that fall under this category have all been associated with the name of Mountain-Eyvind. He and his wife stayed at Hveravellir from around 1762. The oldest source that mentions ruins connected to the couple is *Ferðabók*, or Travel book by Ebenezer Henderson, but he came there in the summer of 1815. There he describes the ruins of a hut where he believed outlaws had lived a few decades earlier. The building stones had been loaded into a crack in a lava bubble and it must have been difficult to distinguish it in the lava from a distance. The place was also conveniently chosen because it is only a few steps out to a boiling spring (Fig.49). Stones have been piled up there so that meat or other food could be placed on the stones to boil. These ruins now bear the name of Eyvind and are called *Eyvindarkofi* (Eyvind's hut) and *Eyvindarkofi* (Eyvind's spring). In addition to this, there are two other monuments in the area that bear his name, but that is *Eyvindarhellir* (Eyvind's cave), about 550m south of the hut ruins, and from there about 470m to the south, is *Eyvindarrétt* (Eyvind's sheep-enclosures), which is filled in a crack in a lava rock.

Figure 50: The last building stage of the Hveravellir shelter house or sæluhús, built in 1922. (Thor Hjaltalín 2008).

In the second category are monuments that relate to transport, roads, and routes. That includes the ten cairns that were registered in the area. The oldest written source about cairns on this mountain road is Landnámabók (The Book of Settlement), which tells about the settlement of Iceland in the Viking Age but was originally written c.1150. Cairns have served for centuries as guideposts for people travelling on the country's mountain roads, and they make a big impression on the landscape of old Kjölur route.

The third category includes structures that have served people who have stayed in Hveravellir during their journeys through the highlands, and there are three monuments that fall under that category. Sturlunga saga is one of the most important contemporary written sources on the history of Iceland in the 12th and 13th centuries. There is found an account on the chieftain Þorgils Skarða's journey across Kjölur in 1258 and his stay in a sæluhús, which likely stood in Hveravellir. It is likely that there was a shelter house there for much longer. Travellers who passed through the area in 1752 mention the ruins of a building that may have been an ancient sæluhús. A shelter house still stands in Hveravellir, built in 1922 on top of older ruins (Fig.50). It may therefore be that a sæluhús has stood in that place for centuries, and that the soil holds remains of it, possibly dating back to the Viking Age. The other two monuments in this category are a cattle enclosure, which probably served

as a restraint for travellers' animals, and a hot spring, which is said to have been used as a boiling pot and for washing clothes.

In addition, two other monuments were recorded in the area that were not considered to be of high value and fell outside the above classification. There are also old written records of few other archaeological remains in the area that could not be found or located.

Assessing significance – methods

The method used to assess the value of the monuments in the area was, first of all, to check whether specific monument groups or complexes could be defined and then assess the monuments and the groups based on ten different value ranges. The method is based to some extent on the Danish SAVE method but has been modified especially with regard to the assessment of collections of remains. The collections of monuments that were evaluated at Hveravellir are the three categories mentioned above, Útilegumannaminjar (remains connected to outlaws), Vörður (cairns or remains connected to transport, roads, and routes) and Áningastaður (remains connected to travellers). For the sake of explanation, it will be discussed here how the evaluation of the remains connected to outlaws, which received a very high score in the evaluation, was done.

	Úrval	Sjaldgæfni	Rannsóknar-og heimildagildi	Upplifun	Upprunaleiki	Menningarlandsl. Minjaheild	Táknrænt glídi	Aogengi	Notkunargildi	Asigkomulag	Útkoma
Hveravellir Útilegumannaminjar	+	+	0	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	9
Hveravellir Áningastaður	0	0	+	+	+	+	0	+	+	+	7
Hveravellir Vörður	0	0	0	0	+	+	0	+	0	+	4

Figure 51: Table showing the evaluation of monuments at Hveravellir according to three categories. (Thor Hjaltalín 2008).

As can be seen from the table (Fig.51), the question asked was if a particular set of archaeological remains had value in ten different areas and the answer is either, yes, it has value in this area (+) or no, it has no special value in this evaluation area (0). The ten areas used in the assessment were:

Selection (Úrval): The question is whether the remains are unique in some way - stand out because of their peculiarities. Regarding the remains from the outlaws, they can be considered unique on a national level. Buildings meant to be hiding places in the highlands stand out and are like no other. (+).

Rarity (Sjaldgæfni): It can be said that there is nothing in the country comparable to the ruins of Eyvindarkofi, together with the hot spring with the stone construction for boiling food. Archaeological remains from hiding places of fugitives are to be found in more places in the highlands of Iceland, and some are attributed to Eyvind, but these remains must be classified as rare. There are not many of them. (+).

Research value (Rannsóknargildi): Certainly, all the ruins have some research and documentation value, and in each case, if remains can give answers to particular research questions they are indeed of value. However, the remains from the outlaws are all simple and probably do not require much further investigation except for Eyvindarkofi, where an excavation could provide additional information about the type of structure and a floor layer. In comparison, the research value of the shelter house (sæluhús) is much greater,

as older remains of shelter houses and structures can be expected underneath the one now standing, going back even to the Viking Age. (0).

Experience (Upplifun): "Every child" in Iceland knows stories about Mountain-Eyvind and Halla, and stories of outlaws and fugitives are a part of traditional folklore. The experiential value of the ruins for travellers to Hveravellir is therefore significant. It gives a site and particular ruins higher value if they can be connected to named historical figures. In this case, there is a great deal of documentation available about the life of the legendary Mountain-Eyvind and his wife Halla. (+)

Authenticity (Upprunaleiki): The ruins are in their original place and have not been tampered with, except by the unkind forces of nature. (+).

Cultural landscape (Menningarlandslag): Here, the remains connected to outlaws at Hveravellir have been grouped together as one cultural complex and all of them have been connected to the name of Mountain-Eyvind, although with some uncertainties regarding the cave and the sheep-enclosure. The experiential value of the ruins lies no less in the fact that they are an integral part of the environment, in a hot spring area and lava fields, making up the cultural landscape. These ruins in Hveravellir can also be seen as part of even a larger group of remains that have been related to Mountain-Eyvind, i.e. Eyvind-monuments far and wide across the country, from Hrafnfjarðareyri in the Westfjords and east to Hvannalindir in the highlands. (+).

Symbolic value (*Táknrænt gildi*): It is difficult to say much about the symbolic value of the ruins, and they can hardly be seen as symbolic for certain ideological systems or national image. However, the ruins and the landscape are an integral part of folklore and tales that are commonly known by Icelanders. They are a testimony to man's perseverance in difficult situations, in harsh natural conditions and a punishing 18th century society. (+).

Accessibility (*Aðgengi*): The site is in the highlands and the Kjölur gravel road is not suitable for small cars. But at the site, access to the archaeological remains is good, as there are paths around the area. A service centre for Hveravellir is located close to the site. There you can access information about the area. There is also a restaurant and internet café, and travellers also have access to a natural hot water bathing pool. Rangers from the Environment Agency are also located at Hversvellir in summertime. (+).

Value of use (*Notkunargildi*): Regarding the use-value of the archaeological remains, the ruins will hardly be used for the purpose they originally served. However, their utility can consist in creating value from them in relation to cultural tourism. It is likely that the number of tourists will still increase in the coming years, just like in recent years. The number of tourists on the road over Kjölur will probably increase significantly, not least if the idea that Kjölur road will be paved comes to fruition. Hveravellir will then become an important site of interest in the future. (+).

Condition (*Ásigkomulag*): The ruins are not in any particular danger, but it is important for the Cultural Heritage Agency (Minjastofnun) to cooperate with the local planning authorities with the aim of ensuring the preservation of the archaeological remains and at the same time using them in a sustainable way. (+).

Conclusions

A total of 19 archaeological remains were recorded at Hveravellir. None of them are listed sites, but all are protected due to the 100-year rule. Due to plans for geothermal power plants, it was necessary to make a further assessment of the value of the ruins. The area was valued not only for archaeological remains, but also for nature, such as geology, animal and plant life. It is clear that such an assessment will inevitably be largely subjective, but with the method described above, an attempt was made to assess the value of the monuments in an organized manner, and, above all, an effort was made to make the assessment transparent and understandable. A similar approach to the assessment of archaeological remains was carried out in all the high temperature areas that were considered for power plants. The method here consisted not least in defining a collection of ruins or remains. One cairn may not be so remarkable in itself, but when it is in a system of cairns on an old route, it has become a remarkable part of a larger whole. The Hveravellir area scores so high, both due to archaeology and nature, that it has received a place in the protection category.

7.10 Þjórsárdalur, Iceland: Significance of cultural landscape

Uggi Ævarsson

Location and background

Þjórsárdalur (valley of the river Þjórsá) lays at the skirt of the southern interior highlands of Iceland. One of Iceland's longest rivers, Þjórsá, meanders by the valley's mouth. The volcano Hekla looms over the valley to the south. The valley is heavily eroded and vegetation sparse, and is regularly blasted by pumice from Mt. Hekla along with other volcanos. The valley is fork shaped with the mountain Reykholt and a batch of pseudo-craters in the middle splitting it in two (Figs.52 & 55). River Fossá (waterfall-river) runs along the western side of the valley and enters it from the northeast plateau with quite an entrance: 122 m high waterfall, Háifoss. The devastating forces of nature, erosion, accumulative elements of ash – fall and the constructive vegetation have been duelling through the centuries.

Roughly in the mid-19th century Þjórsárdalur was systematically surveyed by an antiquarian, Brynjúlfur Jónsson from neighbouring farm Minni-Núpur (Ragnheiður Gló Gylfadóttir, 2021). It was the first time in Iceland that archaeological survey was carried out systematically. By this time the valley had been eroding for decades and cultural ruins were slowly being exposed by wind and lack of vegetation, with remains of around twenty sites slowly coming to light. In Brynjúlfur's eyes the valley was like a stage design for the settlement era – the Viking age.

Figure 52: Site of Reykholt, looking north. (Uggi Ævarsson).

In 1939 a team of pan-Nordic archaeologists excavated six sites in Þjórsárdalur, Skallakot (Aage Roussell), Stöng (Aage Roussell), Snjáleifartóftir (Mårten Stenberger), Áslákstunga fremri (Mårten Stenberger), Skeljastaðir (Matthías Þórðarson) and Stórhólshlíð (Jouko Voionmaa). It was a breakthrough, and this expedition marked the beginning of archaeology as a scientific profession in Iceland. Furthermore, it yielded the development of tephrochronology as a dating method: where each volcanic ash layer is sourced and dated from its composition and bearings to other ash layers. As well as this important scientific breakthrough, the work in the valley was conducted by a number of young archaeologists who went on to become significant figures in the profession, and indeed the nation (one became president of Iceland).

The significance of archaeology as scientific research is quite apparent in the case of Þjórsárdalur: not only did the findings and conclusions of the excavations make a huge impact on understanding the past in general but also established archaeology, tephrochronology and osteology as professions in Iceland. Þjórsárdalur is considered – by Icelandic archaeologists at least – to be the cradle of archaeology in Iceland, because of the actual remains themselves and the development of archaeological method.

It is our role as heritage managers to develop and broaden ideas, and Þjórsárdalur is a good example of the development of the concept of cultural landscape protection, rather than just sites and monuments.

Figure 53: Remains of a byre, site of Stöng. (Uggi Ævarsson).

Figure 54: Excavation at Bergsstaðir, looking south. (Uggi Ævarsson).

Reasons for assessments and assessing significance

Þjórárdalur was mostly abandoned in the beginning of the 12th century due to a devastating ash-fall from Mt Hekla in 1104. In 1300AD Hekla expectorated heavily and sealed the valley's fate. The interior of the valley was never to be inhabited again. Which means that the cultural landscape is 'frozen' in the early 12th century; it is untouched by later agricultural use or other landscape development.

Since 1927 the ruins in Þjórárdalur have been protected. Only a small number of archaeological investigations have been carried out since 1939, although in recent years more has taken place: in Sandártunga, Bergsstaðir, Reykholt, Stöng (Figs. 52 & 54). Even though there have been different opinions within the heritage management of how and if protected sites should be excavated still there is a consensus of the importance of these sites in Þjórárdalur. In later times the idea that the space between the sites is of equal importance to the sites themselves – the cultural landscape as a whole – has developed. The term "búsetulandslag" (settlement landscape) is used along with the term cultural landscape in a bit

narrower sense: it covers the farms and the belonging structures, the routes between farms, fields, meadows and pastures, hunting and fishing grounds, placenames, stories and memories; the land people lived in, were formed by and formed themselves (Orri Vésteinsson, 2020).

The main 'threat' to the cultural landscape in the valley today is not the wind but the tourists which have grown in numbers and are expected to continue to do so in the near future. As elsewhere in Iceland there is a strong will to plant trees everywhere but it is vital from the perspective of the cultural landscape to control the planting in a dialogue with the forestry department and the Environmental Agency. In 1969 the first mega hydro-electric power plant in Iceland was completed at the valley's mouth. It is still going strong and has been extended in recent years.

The municipality and other stakeholders in the area respect the archaeology and its significance, even though it takes some arguing at times. For the first time in Icelandic history a vast area of land – a whole valley of 140 km² – was declared protected in 2021 (Fig.55). A few farms were excluded since they were hesitant to become a part of a protected area, which complicated

Figure 55: Map showing areas of the valley under Cultural Landscape Protection (red) and Environmental Protection (blue). (Oddgeir Isaksen)

the boundaries of the area a little but not dramatically. The Environmental Agency of Iceland protected certain areas in the valley as well. Since cultural and environmental landscapes go hand in hand these two institutions are leading the development work in the valley: building shelters over ruins, making parking areas, trails, bridges, toilets and interpretative material, with backup from the municipality which the more basic infrastructure leans on.

The aim of the Cultural Heritage Agency is to make Þjórsárdalur attractive to guests because of the

archaeology without compromise – resting on the truth value instead of creating a ‘theme park’. The only way to do so is to research and cherish the sites (and the area between them!) and make them inviting to guests through well designed infrastructure. How to mediate archaeological sites is of great importance. The Heritage Agency is focusing on ways to communicate the past in such a way it does not take over the ambience of the deserted valley: concentrating on low-key, low-tech solutions that make the guests become a part of an experience and inspiration rather than being passive consumers.

7.11 Waterford City 'Viking triangle', Ireland

Margaret Keane

Location and surroundings

The site is located at 32-37 Barronstrand Street within the urban core of Waterford City, Ireland. It is an area of rich archaeological potential, at the edge of Waterford's 'Viking Triangle'.

Reasons for assessment

Redevelopment of the site was intended, which consisted of the revamping of a large retail premises and an expansion into an adjacent plot, the former site of 'Egan's Pub'. A planning application was submitted to the Local Authority, Waterford City Council. The initial planning permission was granted by Waterford City Council but the decision was appealed to the higher planning authority An Bord Pleanála. Legislation relating to planning and development in Ireland requires that the Local Authority refer planning applications which may affect or be unduly close to an archaeological monument (in this case within the historic town of Waterford) to the National Monuments Service – the state body charged with protection of the archaeological heritage for their review. In this instance, as with many such referrals to the National Monuments

Service, the relevant officer made a request for further information requiring that an archaeological assessment should be carried out in advance of any planning decision to consider the impact of the proposed development on archaeological material within the site (Pollock, 2005a). The planning permission was finally approved, allowing development to proceed in July 2006.

Description of the site

The site lay within the Viking city at Waterford: it straddled the line of the 13th century town wall and was also located within the precinct of the neighbouring Dominican priory with gardens and monastic buildings and late medieval burials extending across the site, buried below later structures (Fig.56). Prior to submission for planning permission an examination of the upstanding structures within the development site was carried out by archaeological contractors Archaeografix. This had identified a length of possible medieval walling surviving through two floors within the development site (Pollock, 2005 a and b). Further examination established this as being an upstanding portion of the 13th-century Anglo-Norman town wall, a key factor in decision-making for the archaeological remains on the site.

Figure 56: Oblique sketch of the development site showing key standing buildings and archaeological features. (Dave Pollock).

Legal background of heritage protection in Ireland

Protection for the archaeological heritage in Ireland is a product of both legislation and interpretative policy. It has developed over time, reflecting external factors such as the ratification of the Valetta Convention by Ireland in 1998 and European Court of Justice decisions and reflecting internal factors like important Irish court decisions (Keane, 2015). Policy in relation to the archaeological heritage is articulated in two seminal published documents (DAGHI, 1999a and b).

- Framework and Principles for the Protection of the Archaeological Heritage
- Policy and Guidelines on Archaeological Excavations

In terms of levels of protection, in the National Monuments Acts (1930-2014) provided two broad grades: an ordinary level for monuments included in the Record of Monuments and Places and an enhanced level for monuments of national significance in the Ownership and Guardianship of the Minister or Local Authority or those covered by a preservation order. Monuments of national significance include those monuments or the remains of a monument, the preservation of which is a matter of national importance by reason of the historical, architectural, traditional, artistic or archaeological interest attaching thereto (National Monuments Act 1930, Section 2).

The National Monuments Act and Amendments thereof (1930-2014) have recently been replaced by the Historic and Archaeological Heritage and Miscellaneous Provisions Act (HAHMP Act) of 2023. Large portions of the Act remain to be commenced but the new law is on the statute books and will be enacted over the coming years. The HAHMP Act completely replaces rather than consolidates the previous legislation, however some of the fundamental aspects of the previous suite are mirrored in the new Act but there are important differences.

The new legislation (HAHMP Act) specifies general and special levels of protection to monuments entered into a new Register: this is a single Register, with varying levels of protection. A suite of factors must be reviewed when determining if an entry into the Register is merited, for example, the level of archaeological interest, the physical integrity of the monument, the likelihood of protection in situ or the extent to which a monument or thing is already subject to protection

under another enactment. The latter can relate to buildings of architectural interest which are Protected Structures under the Planning and Development Acts.

The Act contains a key provision relating to proposals for works to be carried out at or on a monument to which general protection applies. Either a licence is needed to conduct any works, or a notification procedure must be completed. Once a notice has been sent, the Minister must consider whether the registered monument in question requires special protection. If special protection is decided upon, then anyone wishing to carry out, or direct or authorise the carrying out of works at that monument, then a licence is required.

In considering whether to apply or cease to apply special protection, the Minister must review a number of criteria specified under the Act, namely, the interest, character, integrity or amenity value of the monument in terms of its archaeological, architectural or historic heritage, taking into account whether the monument is, in terms of such heritage, of special or particular interest, character, integrity or amenity value, whether at a local, regional, national or international level. (Chapter 4, Section 20, (3))

In some cases – where a monument is a national monument, a wreck 100 or more years old, or a monument in the guardianship of the Minister or a local authority – it cannot be decided that special protection ceases to apply.

The Act also allows consideration of the significance of a monument at several important junctures, the first is to what classes of monument automatic protection is applied. These are 'prescribed' monuments – general protection applies to all such classes notwithstanding their entry or otherwise into the Register. Secondly when including a monument in the Register, the Minister shall consider whether general or special protection applies or should apply. Thirdly when notice has been sent to the Minister of a proposal to carry out works to or at a monument, the Minister must then review whether that monument should attract general or special protection.

Assessment of significance- methods

For the Waterford site, part of the focus of the assessment was a detailed examination of the party wall between the existing retail premises and the proposed extension area (Fig.57). Archaeological

Figure 57: View of the archaeological site from the East, showing the protected town wall on the right. (Dave Pollock).

Figure 58: Burials in the cloister walk of the medieval priory. (Dave Pollock).

policy in Ireland (DAHGI 1999a) provides for “that the particular benefits to the community of the continued existence of archaeological monuments with visible above ground features should always be a consideration and only the most compelling reasons can justify the removal of such monuments. The question of the fabric and antiquity of the party wall earmarked for demolition was in question, and the request for further information required stripping back and recording of the party wall which being of 18th and 19th century date was deemed to have little archaeological significance.

The focus of Irish policy, particularly in relation to development in historic towns within urban areas is as follows:

Every effort should be made to secure the preservation in-situ of surviving upstanding features or structures of archaeological interest located in historic towns, in particular town walls, all medieval and seventeenth century buildings or remains of such, and post 1700 AD buildings which are of archaeological interest.

This policy was reinforced in 2008 with the publication of a specific policy document ‘National Policy

on Town Defences’ (Department of Environment, Heritage and Local Government 2008). This enhanced framework professed that all town defences were to be considered a single National Monument treated as a unit for policy and management purposes with a presumption in favour of the preservation in situ of archaeological remains and the preservation of their character, setting and amenity. Although this policy document was published after planning permission had been granted, in 2006, the planning decision, which was written by An Bord Pleanála (ABP) contained many of the precepts which were to be encapsulated in the National Policy on Town Defences. It set out the conditions for the preservation of the town wall and conditions for its context within the development, providing that the town wall be set within a void in the floor slab “to ensure that this feature of national importance is properly treated and displayed to the public in compliance with the provisions of the currently development plan for the area.” The nature of the town wall as a national monument²³ and the public benefit provided by its conservation and presentation to the public is clearly articulated within the planning decision, prompted by the recommendations of the National Monuments Service.

²³“The expression “national monument” means a monument or the remains of a monument the preservation of which is a matter of national importance by reason of the historical, architectural, traditional, artistic, or archaeological interest attaching thereto and also includes (but not so as to limit, extend or otherwise influence the construction of the foregoing general definition) every monument in Saorstát Éireann to which the Ancient Monuments Protection Act, 1882, applied immediately before the passing of this Act, and the said expression shall be construed as including, in addition to the monument itself, the site of the monument and the means of access thereto and also such portion of land adjoining such site as may be required to fence, cover in, or otherwise preserve from injury the monument or to preserve the amenities thereof” (National Monuments Act 1930 Section 2).

In relation to the upstanding monuments within this development site, decision making relating to their significance, followed explicit national policy articulated firstly in Framework and Principles for the protection of the archaeological heritage (DAHGI 1999a), secondly in terms of the objectives and policies of the Waterford City development plan, concepts which were articulated more expansively subsequently in the National Policy on Town Defences.

The buried deposits on the development site also posed questions in terms of their significance and subsequent treatment prior to construction. These included a pre-town wall clay bank, the external ditch associated with that bank and town wall, a tower base marking the corner of the medieval city wall, as well as burials and building remains associated with the Dominican priory and earlier occupation (Fig.58). The potential impacts of the proposed development on these deposits and structures was dependent on the type of foundations to be used, the proposed finished floor level and the depth and location of lifts, escalator wells, and service trenches.

Once the nature of the upstanding wall on site was established, Ministerial consent was required for any more excavation in proximity to this structure. Thus a programme of archaeological investigation followed – under the relevant consents – across the demolished Egan's Pub and then within the large retail area. The development was then able to proceed, taking into account the decision-making required by the archaeological discoveries (Fig.59). This case study thus shows that some of the decisions and selections were made according to explicit legal and policy requirements, whereas some were based on factors specific to the site itself.

Figure 59: Section of the preserved town wall on display within the new retail premises. (Dave Pollock).

7.12 The Tuba-Zangariyye Dolmen Field, Israel

Yael Alef, Eran Mordohovich, Uri Berger

Introduction and management context

The Tuba-Zangariyye dolmen field demonstrates how the assessment of cultural significance aided in incorporating the remains into a development plan, thereby reducing destruction that threatened them. It illustrates a shift in the Israel Antiquities Authority's (IAA) approach to preserving dolmens in situ.

Located on the southern edge of the Tuba-Zangariyye village in northern Israel, the dolmen field (area of megalithic burial structures) was threatened in 2015 when the Ministry of Housing and Construction proposed a residential neighbourhood development on the site. This proposal was made without consulting the IAA, although the area is designated as an antiquities site under the Antiquities Law, which requires IAA approval for such developments. In response to the proposal, an archaeological survey mapped the remains within the planning area. At this stage, significance assessment was not conducted, resulting in only a few dolmens being identified for preservation in isolated locations. The

IAA conditionally approved the development plan, contingent on a salvage excavation being carried out. This ultimately condemned most of the dolmens and the megalithic landscape to destruction. As the planning progressed, it only partially adhered to the IAA conditions, and infrastructure was planned close to the remaining dolmens, which would have practically eliminated them had the plan been implemented.

This reflects the common approach in Israel until recently, where the dolmens did not receive appropriate attention from most archaeologists and have been largely overlooked by development and major archaeological enterprises. With the growing development pressures in the last decades, the practice of salvage excavation as a management policy has resulted in the destruction of numerous dolmens in the Golan Heights and the Korazim Plateau. Despite their historical and cultural significance, dozens of dolmens have been damaged by basalt mining in the Golan Heights and the Korazim Plateau for the construction of ports and the development of towns and villages. Even in instances where the dolmens themselves were preserved, their setting in the landscape and context were often destroyed.

Figure 60: IAA archaeologist surveying a dolmen in the Tuba-Zangariyye field, with the village in the background (Photo taken by E. Mordohovich, 2019).

Fortunately, that was not the end of the story for the Tuba-Zangariyye dolmen field. In 2019, the development plan was expanded, and consequently, an additional archaeological survey was conducted in the expanded area (Fig.60). During this time, the IAA became more aware of contemporary practices in archaeological resource management. This included a recognition of the policy presumption for the preservation of archaeological heritage in situ, which is enshrined as one of the principles in the Valletta Convention, as well as the need for an integrated approach to the conservation of archaeological heritage. This awareness was further complemented by recognizing the importance of a holistic approach to the cultural landscape and incorporating the concept of value-based management. The renewed survey thus presented an opportunity to clarify the significance of the dolmens and the importance of the megalithic cultural landscape. It also allowed for the establishment of new guidelines to integrate the remains into the development plan.

The legal system

The Israeli Antiquities Law of 1978 designates the IAA to oversee and manage the country's archaeological sites and artifacts. According to the law, "antiquity" is defined as "Any object, whether detached or fixed, which was made by man before the year 1700 of the general era and includes anything subsequently added thereto which forms an integral part thereof". An "antiquity site" indicates an area that contains antiquities.

Under the law, the IAA is responsible for conducting archaeological surveys and registering antiquity sites. It is also tasked with regulating any construction or development that may impact these sites. Any proposed development within the area of a registered antiquity site must receive approval from the IAA. When a development plan is submitted for approval, the IAA will either conduct a survey or trial trenches and/or excavation to identify potential remains. Based on the results, it will decide whether to approve the plan with no further conditions, reject the plan, or require salvage excavations before permitting development activities. The IAA may also mandate mitigation measures to protect archaeological sites during construction.

More than 30,000 antiquity sites are currently registered under the Antiquities Law. However, while the law effectively regulates the discovery, excavation,

and ownership of antiquities, it lacks robust tools for designating sites for preservation. As a matter of fact, archaeological sites that merit preservation must be statutorily protected under the 1965 Planning and Building Law.

The evaluation system

In Israel, the authorities do not implement a formal evaluation system for designating archaeological sites for preservation. The following text adopts a significance assessment information model (Alef, 2021) and guidelines for cultural significance assessment developed by the author. These guidelines are intended for the training of Archaeological Resource Management (ARM) practitioners in academia and the Israel Antiquities Authority (IAA). They are based on a Context-Based Significance Assessment (CBSA) approach, which aims to place the site within broader historical processes, enabling the perception of broad patterns and how individual resources fit within these patterns. This approach also helps to explain spatial and cultural interconnections (Briuer and Mathers, 1997; Carman, 2015; Hardesty and Little, 2009; Mathers et al, 2005).

CBSA evaluates a site within its historical themes and geographical contexts. Common criteria for evaluating archaeological sites include the period; quality of the remains (in terms of integrity and preservation); rarity; representativeness; vulnerability; documentation; aesthetics; and research potential. However, it should be noted that in addition to the changing nature of significance in relation to cultural agendas, academic and professional literature does not specify precisely what needs to be done to assess these qualities. Generally, these qualities refer to academic and scientific value, changes over time, local and community values, and wider public benefits (Carman, 2015).

The CBSA model suggests complementing the site description with the following steps:

1. Identify the cultural elements and context components, including (a) typological, structural, and geographical context; (b) historical information referring to figures, events, and processes related to the site or its context; (c) cultural themes related to stories and figures, artistic themes depicted in artifacts, traditions, and practices.

2. Articulate the cultural significance, explaining why these elements are significant.
3. Contextualize the cultural significance in relation to the themes, demonstrating how the broader context amplifies this significance.
4. Compare the site to other similar sites to highlight its uniqueness or representativeness, including the integrity of the remains. Consider factors such as rarity, workmanship, and artistic quality.
5. Write a concise summary integrating all the previous points into a cohesive narrative. Where relevant in the description or cultural significance assessment, refer to the quality of information, such as available sources, the richness of data, as well as uncertainties or different explanations for phenomena.

Description of the site

The Tuba-Zangariyye dolmen field is situated on a hill in the basalt Korazim Plateau, which stretches in the Jordan Rift Valley, between the Sea of Galilee in the

south and the Hula Valley in the north (Fig.61). This field is part of the larger Korazim dolmen field which is the western extension of the vast megalithic field of southern Syria and upper Jordan.

Throughout history, the plateau was home to semi-nomadic cattle herders and pastoralists who lived in temporary dwellings, leaving behind stone animal pens as a common feature in the area. However, the most significant archaeological elements on the plateau are approximately 500 dolmens and a few hundred more tumuli that dominate the landscape. These are dated to the Intermediate Bronze Age, around the end of the 3rd to the early 2nd millennia BCE (4,500-4,000 years ago) and represent the latest in a series of megalithic monuments of the Jordan Valley and the Golan Heights (Stepansky, 2005).

In 1877, Herbert Kitchener, who later commanded the British Empire Army during World War One, reported that while surveying the area of the Zangariyye tribes for the Palestine Exploration Fund, they discovered the first perfect dolmen he had seen in the country, which was called Hajr ed Dum, or “the stone of blood”

Figure 61: Survey map of the Tuba-Zangariyye dolmen field on the Korazim Plateau showing its dense concentration of dolmens. (GIS map prepared by Y. Alef, 2024)

Figure 62: An historic photo of dolmen in the Tuba-Zangariyye vicinity, possibly the Hajar ed Dumm dolmen mentioned by Kitchner in 1877. (B. Rothenberg, 1955, Meitar Collection, The Pritzker Family National Photography Collection, The National Library of Israel)

(Kitchener, 1877). This dolmen was part of a large field of dolmens on the Korazim Plateau, identified by Karge in 1917. The field was later included in a report on Prehistoric Galilee by Francis Turville-Petre in the 1920s, who also excavated 24 dolmens in the area. Following Moshe Stekelis in the 1960s and Claire Epstein in the 1970s, research continued into the 1990s with the IAA survey of Israel by Yosef Stepansky, who documented 578 dolmens on the Korazim Plateau. A few dolmens were also excavated as part of local salvage excavations (Berger and Sharon, 2018).

The dolmens located in Tuba-Zangariyye form part of the ancient landscape that was already familiar during Biblical times. It is possible that they are related to references in the Bible about giants who inhabited the eastern Transjordan. As stated in Deuteronomy 2:21, "That also was accounted a land of giants: giants dwelt therein in old time...". Among them was Og, the giant king of the Bashan. Additionally, there are references to dolmen in the Korazim area, which may be the "tombs" described in the miracle of the pigs where Jesus casts out demons from the body of a madman. Mark 5:2-3 states, "When Jesus got out of the boat, a man with an

impure spirit came from the tombs to meet him. This man lived in the tombs..." (Stepansky, 2005)

The Tuba-Zangariyye field includes more than 65 dolmens and more than 20 tumuli over an area of about 0.5km². It consists of several types of dolmens, most of which are small with 1.5 - 3m long closed chambers and 1-2 covering stones. The size of the covering stones varies, with an average of 0.5 x 1.5 x 3m, but some single stones may weigh as much as 15 tons. Some of the dolmens stand out conspicuously and can be seen from afar due to a large capstone that covers the dolmen chamber or its tumulus (see Fig.62).

Another type of dolmen is covered by tumuli, consisting of various-sized fieldstones. In many instances, one can discern within them or around their circumference remains of walls, adding an even more commanding and monumental appearance. The average sizes of tumuli are 5 to 10m in diameter and 1-2m in height, but some reach sizes of 15-20m x 3m. Those dolmens without a tumulus are usually enclosed by a stone circle or by scattered stones placed evenly or without order around the structure (Stepansky, 2005).

Significance assessment

The striking spectacle of hundreds of dolmens and tumuli, forming the characteristic cultural landscape, is the most prominent and conspicuous archaeological element of the Korazim Plateau. The Korazim dolmen field is the largest of its kind west of the Jordan River and one of the densest megalithic burial fields in the world. Within it, the unique and well-preserved Tuba dolmen field stands out (Fig.63).

Each dolmen is a product of an engineering construction effort that attests to a developed social organization, a sophisticated culture, and high technological knowledge and abilities, sometimes exaggeratedly compared to those of the pyramid builders in Egypt. The first basalt dolmen discovered in Israel was found in this field, documented as early as 1877. This discovery sparked ongoing research into this culture. These burial structures they left behind provide us with the most information about this culture. The enigmatic relics are all that remain of a civilization that sanctified its dead with monumental structures unknown in the area at any other historical period.

Since the discovery of dolmens in the Levant, there has been debate about their dating, and much remains unknown about the people who invested so much of their limited resources into the construction of megalithic tombs, especially compared with their assumed modest way of life. Future research may provide insights into this enigmatic phenomenon, enhancing our understanding of one of the most interesting phenomena in the archaeology of the Levant.

Figure 63: Aerial view of a dolmen from the Tuba-Zangariyye field and its surrounding (Photo taken by A. Kleiner, 2019)

The monumental remains stand almost as they were built about 4,400 years ago, creating a unique landscape known since biblical times, until recent times when the Bedouin Zangariyye tribes grazed their flocks in the area. Sadly, over the past 150 years, dozens of dolmens in the area have been damaged and destroyed due to development activities. Today, after extensive destruction, this dolmen field is a rare and almost the last remnant of this cultural landscape.

Results/ outcomes

The findings of the survey and evaluation were presented to the planners of the Ministry of Housing during a field visit. The result was a compromise in which the IAA was asked to redefine the areas for preservation and development in a manner that preserves the greatest number of dolmens and enables the development of the rest of the area. Based on the significance assessment, conservation principles have been at the forefront of planning efforts for the Tuba-Zangariyye dolmen field. These principles include preserving the dolmens as part of the megalithic landscape in an open and connected area; minimizing the impact of infrastructure and roads on the concentration of dolmens; preserving prominent individual dolmens; and incorporating dolmens into the planning of public buildings and tourism land use. Efforts have also been made to ensure that development works do not damage or cover the remaining dolmens. These principles were integrated in recent planning versions, and it remains to be seen how they will be implemented in the final plan and in subsequent detailed planning stages.

The case study illustrates a gradual shift in the IAA's practice from relying primarily on the Antiquities Law, which has proven insufficient for the effective protection and preservation of archaeological heritage, to integrating the site into the development plan. Other current ARM principles that emphasize community participation are another challenge for the future.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank Jon Seligman for his thoughtful comments on the case study.

7.13 'Leithon', The Netherlands

Bjørn Smit

Location and surroundings

In the village of Leiderdorp (near The Hague and Leiden) in the western part of the Netherlands the remains of an early medieval settlement (Merovingian and Carolingian) is scheduled as national archaeological monument (Fig.64). The region between the villages of Katwijk (in the west) and Koudekerk (in the east) is known for the presence of numerous archaeological remains from Roman and early medieval period located at the former river course/ estuary of the Oude Rijn river, part of the Rhine delta. This region is one of the most densely populated area of the Netherlands, so over the past decades numerous archaeological excavations have been

executed. In general the impetus for this research was spatial developments (construction of infrastructure, building of houses, etc.). Until the beginning of the twentieth century the site was located in the outskirts of Leiderdorp. Since 1937 the terrain on which the site is located was in use as tennis courts. The research history of the early medieval site 'Leithon' and its surroundings in Leiderdorp already started in the 1950s when an excavation was done by the curator of the National Museum of Antiquities in Leiden. During that excavation the remains of an early medieval settlement were discovered but also wooden and stone constructions along the residual river channels near the settlement. In the 1980s, human remains were found as well as animal bones (settlement consumption waste and butchering refuse) in a former channel.

Figure 64: Location of the listed archaeological monument in Leiderdorp (Courtesy Cultural Heritage Agency of the Netherlands)

Reasons for assessment

At the beginning of this century it was decided that the (open) area of the tennis courts which was surrounded by houses was to be developed as residential area with numerous new houses. The archaeological remains are situated in the subsurface only about 40cm below the present surface and in fact directly below the tennis courts. As a result the question arose: what to do with the important archaeological site of 'Leithon', preserve or excavate?

The majority of archaeological remains in the Netherlands, are invisible because they are situated below the surface. However, the characteristics of the subsurface of the Netherlands and then especially the Holocene parts of the Netherlands (western and northern Netherlands and riverine areas in the central and southern Netherlands) leads to good to excellent preservation of (organic) archaeological remains. So for large parts of the Netherlands archaeological remains and objects are very well preserved²⁴. If one would visit these Roman monuments in the Netherlands the majority of these sites are below your feet underground and their location and significance is marked through signs, information panels, 'reconstructions' and visualizations of what these remains exemplify.

The site of 'Leithon' is thus located in the area with generally good preservation if remains are not yet destroyed by later activities. The presence of well-preserved bone, wood and other organic remains related to the Early Medieval settlement shows the good conservation conditions on the site. For decades it was known that underneath the tennis courts and its surroundings significant archaeological remains are present. Because of the fact that in this – nowadays highly urbanized – part of the Netherlands these valuable early medieval archaeological remains are still present below the surface, the area of Leiderdorp gained the attention of both archaeologists and heritage resource managers (national and local). The settlement of Leithon might be regarded as relic or representation of the (former) dense clusters of archaeological remains from this period in the wider highly urbanized area.

Entirely conforming to the principles of the Valletta Convention, the initial premise was to leave these

archaeological remains 'in situ' and in this safeguard them from future developments and destruction.

Other motives and aspects also have to be dealt with in heritage management especially when spatial development (in this instance new houses) is necessary. Furthermore at a national level it was observed that Early Medieval settlements (with well preserved (organic) archaeological remains) had been discovered in the past decades in the area. However most sites were excavated and only a few scheduled as national monuments. Therefore the settlement in Leiderdorp was designated to become a scheduled archaeological monument to preserve remains of this type.

Firstly, this decision needed to be coordinated with local authorities and plans for the site, because originally, the plan had entailed the complete destruction of the archaeological site. Fortunately the building plans were adapted and a new plan which entailed the combination of new housing and recreation was developed. The Cultural Heritage Agency of the Netherlands and the local government of Leiderdorp came to the following agreement or compromise: the area of the archaeological site which was to be built over was to be professionally excavated, and the area of the site where the tennis courts were was to become a scheduled archaeological monument where the archaeological remains were left unharmed and a recreational park was to be developed. One could regard this compromise as a loss for the archaeology because yet another part of the early medieval archive in this region was to be destroyed and only a part of the settlement was to be preserved in situ. However, this compromise produced a bonus because the partial excavation means it is now much clearer what exactly is preserved in situ.

Assessing significance- methods and outcomes

For the excavation, an extensive programme of requirements was written by the Cultural Heritage Agency, the municipality of Leiderdorp and researchers from the Amsterdam Archaeological Centre (University of Amsterdam). The researchers from Amsterdam conducted the excavation because it fitted within their framework of research.

²⁴This preservation state of the buried archaeological remains was for example one of the key arguments to list the Dutch part of the Lower German Limes as a UNESCO World Heritage Site.

Figure 65: Finds from one of the residual gullies (Courtesy University of Amsterdam)

During the excavation (2013) a total of almost 200,000 finds were recorded. For organic finds especially the fill of the residual river channels proved to be a treasure trove. The channels were lined with revetments made of timbers, wickerwork and re-used stone material (Fig.66).

It was possible to use the timbers from these revetments for dendrochronological research, providing very accurate construction dates in both Merovingian and Carolingian periods. An interesting inorganic finds category were the numerous stone fragments. The use of stone material is not that common in Dutch (pre)history, it turned out that the stone material in Leithon mainly was re-used building material which derived from the former Roman fort of Matilo situated about 800 m to the west. This re-used 'Roman' building material was combined with timber in the construction and re-enforcement of the shores of the residual gullies.

Finds from the channels consisted of large quantities of animal bones and pottery, metal objects and metal production refuse, numerous leather finds, bone and antler combs and a lot of rope (Fig.65). Based on the analyses of the finds it is clear that subsistence in the settlement was based on animal husbandry (cattle, sheep/goat, pig and horse) and growing of crops (barley, rye and emmer) with an addition of both salt and freshwater fishing. Possibly a part of the wheats were imported from southern regions.

Figure 66: The excavation of one of the residual gullies showing the remains of revetments (Courtesy University of Amsterdam)

Numerous personal objects and tools of both metal and organic material were found. A number of wool combs, loom weights and hackles indicate that the processing of wool and flax. Furthermore both objects from iron, bronze and lead were made in the settlement. The pottery assemblage shows resemblance to that from the famous Dorestad settlement with pottery coming from the German Rhineland and Eifel area. Whereas Dorestad in Carolingian times clearly can be identified as an international trading hub, Leithon cannot be qualified as such, because the residual channels were too small to facilitate large vessels. It is likely the former inhabitants of Leithon participated in the Frisian Trade network that connected the North Sea region with the Carolingian hinterland. Around 840 AD the settlement ceased to exist likely due to a massive storm surge dated to 838. Its features and finds remained hidden until the excavations in 2013.

Conclusion

To conclude, in Leiderdorp, on the banks of two residual channels in the Rhine estuary, the remains of an Early Medieval settlement is located. The settlement is characterized by the presence of revetments lining residual channels and thick pack of find-rich inorganic and organic material in the residual channels. In addition, some skeletons have been found indicating

the presence of at least one burial ground. Probably the settlement in Leiderdorp formed part of a network of early medieval settlements along the coast and in the Rhine estuary participating in the Frisian Trade network. Most of these settlements have completely disappeared and been disrupted due to urbanization in the Western Netherlands. In Leiderdorp part of the site remains in situ and are scheduled as archaeological monument (monument number 532469) (Fig.67). The remains are well-preserved and largely intact in the subsurface and therefore a valuable addition to the archive of listed sites in the Netherlands providing a possibility for research of future generations (Fig.68).

Acknowledgements

Many thanks to Jan van Doesburg and Liesbeth Theunissen (Cultural Heritage Agency of the Netherlands) for valuable comments on a draft version of this text and thanks to Menno Dijkstra (University of Amsterdam) for permission to use photos of the excavation and finds.

Figure 67: The demarcation of the listed archaeological monument on an aerial photo (Courtesy Cultural Heritage Agency of the Netherlands)

Figure 68: Part of the listed archaeological monument situated under the recreation area in the suburb of Leiderdorp, the archaeological presence is marked by an artwork depicting some of the pottery found during the excavation (Courtesy Cultural Heritage Agency of the Netherlands)

7.14 Prehistoric barrows as archive for future research, The Netherlands

Liesbeth Theunissen

Introduction

As in many other countries in north-western Europe, there are a lot of prehistoric barrows in the Netherlands: at a rough estimate, about 3,000 barrows are known. This number is still growing due to discovery of new elevations on Lidar images, which – after evaluating – are recognized as anciently thrown up mounds, very possibly new, unknown barrows (Fig.69).

Most of these mounds were erected from the Late Neolithic onwards up to the early phase of the Iron Age, from 2900-800 BC. They were built with sods cut in the vicinity of the grave monuments, for instance from heather land, and usually stacked upside down.

The majority of the barrows are situated on the sandy soils in the northern, eastern and southern parts of the country, especially in the provinces of Drenthe, Overijssel, Gelderland, Utrecht and Noord-Brabant. A few dozens of barrows have also been discovered in the Holocene parts of the Netherlands, especially in the West-Frisian region in the province of Noord-Holland. These Holocene ‘wetlands’ are characterised by favourable preservation conditions, where vulnerable remains such as wood or unburned bone are embedded in moist clay layers. The skeletal parts of the deceased in these parts of the Netherlands are often well preserved whereas the inhumation graves on the sandy soils are deteriorated to a point where only discolourations remain visible. The acidic soils let the unburnt bodies fade away to soil silhouettes at best.

Figure 69: Overview of the visible barrows in the Netherlands. Most barrow groups are situated on the sandy soils in the east and south of the country. (Courtesy CulturalHeritage Agency of the Netherlands)

Figure 70: Typical small-scale excavations of barrows. (left) , the ditch and bank barrow of Hoogeloon-Zwartenberg (RM 45713), in 1950. In remaining crossbalks the vertical structure of the stacked sods is noticeable. (right) one of the seven mounds (Zevenbergen) near Laren (province of North Holland), carried out in the early 1950s by a handful of workers. (Courtesy CulturalHeritage Agency of the Netherlands)

As regards the treatment of the body, relatives decided either to bury the corpse (inhumation) or to burn it on a pyre and then bury the remains (cremation). The custom of cremating the deceased grew during the Bronze Age, although inhumation was still practised.

More than a century of assessment

Thanks to their visibility, Bronze Age barrows in the Netherlands have always attracted a lot of interest, and they consequently have a long research history. JH Holwerda, curator of the National Museum of Antiquities, was the first scholar to carry out the scientific barrow excavations in 1906, by invitation of

Queen Wilhelmina. From 1947 onwards a lot of barrows were threatened by extensive heathland reclamation projects. The archaeological institute of the University of Groningen and the National Service for Archaeological Investigations in Amersfoort managed to excavate many of them (Fig.70). This emergency research carried out by these institutes was on a small scale, involving the investigation of the barrow and the peripheral structure over a couple of days. The work was done by hand. The biggest expense was the wages for the workers who moved the sand with shovels and wheelbarrows.

The so-called kwadrantenmethode (quadrant method) was first applied to excavation of barrows in 1916 (Fig.71). Digging up mounds in this way gave researchers a good insight into the distribution of traces and the vertical structure and layers of the mound. Viewed from above, a barrow is divided in quadrants, which are excavated in quadrants, one by one. The central cross remained in situ; these are the so-called profile dams, the crossbalks.

Figure 71: The kwadrantenmethode allows studying and recording the various features and layers in both horizontal planes and vertical profiles, all with great care (Glasbergen 1954).

Potential for future research

In post-war years the excavators were already aware of the barrows' potential for future research. They cared about the conservation of the excavated tumuli. The remaining parts of the crossbalks might allow renewed study of the sections, further analysis of the structure of both the mound and the old surface, and sampling. Palynological examinations of the old surfaces under barrows, for instance, can reveal the

Figure 72: A re-evaluation of a restored barrow in 2016, with the original features of the post circle still clearly visible. (Courtesy CulturalHeritage Agency of the Netherlands)

vegetation history. In the case of the barrow group at Toterfout-Halve Mijl near Veldhoven, the excavator W Glasbergen (1954) not only left the crossbalks intact, he also left most of the post circle features undisturbed. A lot of barrows were often carefully restored after excavation (Fig.72).

The undisturbed parts of the mounds were the main reason for placing many of the excavated barrows under the protection of the Monuments and Historic Buildings Act, which was introduced in 1961. The designation of scheduled monuments in this early period did not involve evaluation and selection. Visibility and expert judgement (by the provincial archaeologists) were the main criteria. Each designation was viewed and assessed in the field. Measurement of the dimensions was done by counting the number of steps, later with a measuring wheel was used.

The scheduled area included the dimension of the visible mound of the barrow with a 10m buffer. Barrow excavations showed that this strip of 10m contained important features, such as the peripheral structures, ditches with bank, ring ditches or post circles. An open area was also desired from an aesthetic point of view (Fig.74).

Figure 73: Many burial mounds are located in forest areas, such this barrow near Putten (scheduled archaeological monument 341245), in the Veluwe area. Most of them are managed by nature organisations. Shoots of young trees and shrubs are removed on a regular basis. (Courtesy CulturalHeritage Agency of the Netherlands)

Heritage management of burial landscapes

In the 1980s and 1990s, the focus shifted more to restoring the mounds, and sometimes - even more radically - reconstructing them. For this, local sand was often used, to replenish parts of the mound that had been eroded and also to raise it. Those extra layers formed a protection for the intact parts, so that they were more resistant to, for instance, motocross racers, dogs, badgers and wild boars. Only a few mounds were 'opened' in these years, mostly to retrieve information about their age. This growing focus on heritage conservation led to protocols for maintenance and management. Barrows still in fact account for the majority of scheduled monuments (c.1550) in the Netherlands.

Nowadays, most of the scheduled prehistoric burial mounds are situated in nature conservation areas, far away from the built environment (Fig.73). These burial landscapes are managed by a number of Dutch nature

organisations, for instance by the State Forest Service (Staatsbosbeheer), taking care of 260.000 ha and a considerable number of scheduled monuments. It's a world of balancing between protecting, managing and using the landscape.

In the developer-led archaeological projects sometimes the remains of (unknown) barrows are encountered, such as two barrows excavated within the framework of the road construction of the Westfrisiaweg in Noord-Holland. One of them was 'hidden' below a Late Medieval dwelling mound. Another, quite spectacular discovery is the ritual Bronze Age landscape of Tiel-Medel, investigated preceding the building of a new industrial estate. In the vicinity of an open-air sanctuary three barrows were found where the remains of 60 people were buried; men, women and many children. This research will reignite discussions about barrows and their buried communities and generate new research questions in the Netherlands.

Figure 74: The protected area of the barrow with bank and ditch of Hoogeloo (scheduled archaeological monument 45713) and a 10 metre strip of the direct vicinity (blue circle). (Courtesy CulturalHeritage Agency of the Netherlands)

7.15 The hillfort 'Zamczysko' ('The Burgstall'), Poland

Agnieszka Makowska

Location and surroundings

The hillfort called 'Zamczysko' ('The Burgstall') is located in the Kampinos National Park, which is key to preserving and protecting it. The Park was established in 1959, in order to protect the unique complex of inland dunes interspersed with marshes, its fauna and flora, as well as natural and cultural landscape. The variety of habitats, from very wet to very dry, ensures a great diversity of plants, fungi and lichens. Together with its buffer zone, the Park is also an important refuge for more than 5,000 animal species, 250 of which are protected.

Much of the Park (about 75%) is covered by forest. Strict protection areas have also been established within its

territory, and about 12% of the Park area is left entirely to nature, allowing ecological processes to take their course. The hillfort is located within the Zamczysko Strict Protection Area (Fig.75). In 2000, the Kampinos National Park was declared a UNESCO Biosphere Reserve, and in 2004 it became a part of the 'Puszcza Kampinoska' Natura 2000 site. Kampinos is the second largest national park in the country (385 km²). Its location close to Warsaw, Poland's growing capital, poses many threats to nature and cultural heritage. Risks include construction investments within the buffer zone, lowering of the groundwater table, as well as increased waste and fire hazard. The proximity of the major city also means excessive wilderness penetration by people and their pets, as Kampinos is a very popular walking destination for Varsovians. Hiking and biking trails are available near the hillfort, and the site area is open to visitors.

Figure 75: The hillfort called 'Zamczysko' within the Zamczysko Strict Protection Area in the Kampinos National Park, view from the walking trail, condition as at November 2022. (National Institute of Cultural Heritage, Agnieszka Makowska)

Reasons for assessment

The hillfort was entered to the register of monuments in 1965 (registry number: C-54). Since the 1985 it also has been listed in the National Inventory of Archaeological Sites (AZP 55-62/11). For its protection, however, its location within the Zamczysko Strict Protection Area is most beneficial. This is a passive form of natural world conservation, where a designated area is left entirely to nature, allowing ecological processes to take their course (Fig.76). This area of the Park is managed by the Director of the Kampinos National Park, appointed by the minister responsible for the environment. He acts under the provisions of the Act of 16 April 2004 on Nature Conservation. In areas listed in the register of monuments, any planned change requires the Voivodship Monuments Preservation Officer (VMPO) approval.

At the end of 2009, the hillfort was under evaluation as part of the project for the verification of all registered archaeological sites in Poland, conducted by National Institute of Cultural Heritage (NICH). A further assessment took place in 2015 when the VMPO requested the NICH's opinion on the design of the new visitor infrastructure on the hillfort.

Description of the site

The hillfort is situated on the southern edge of the wooded dune embankment, with extensive marshes at its foot. An old-growth forest with rare tree species grows on the archaeological site and around. Zamczysko in the Kampinos is an example of a well-preserved medieval hillfort. The double ring

of ramparts and two moats are still clearly visible. The earthwork is egg-shape and closed, it is a so-called ringfort. The natural landform was used in the construction. The marshes acted as a natural defence. It measures c.102 x 78 m. The inner rampart is about 5 m high, the outer one is much lower. A relatively small part of the hillfort has been excavated. Our knowledge of the site is therefore incomplete, but it is enough for us to understand that we are dealing with relics that are definitely worth protecting and preserving in situ for future generations. Archaeologists have been interested in the site since at least 1923, when Zofia Podkowińska carried out a surface survey of the area. In order to verify the hypothesised function and dating of the site, a trial excavation was carried out in 1980 by Jerzy Pyrgała. It covered a small fragment of the inner part of the hillfort, and slope of the rampart towards the northern moat. Traces of burnt layer, charcoal, lumps of worked clay with wood print were found. Research has revealed remains of a domical kiln built of clay around a wooden framework, and wooden fortifications of the ringfort. These include burnt beams and laths, arranged horizontally, forming a 5-metre-wide strip. Remnants of the crossed logs construction were also discovered during an archaeological rescue excavation in 2017, conducted by Mariusz Samborski. This research was carried out when constructing a platform, footbridges and stairs for visitors (Fig.76). Researchers have also found medieval knives, iron bow and fragments of Gothic bricks, possibly from the brick tower existing on the castle. The place inspires the imagination – folk tales say Queen Bona Sforza, wife of King Sigismund I the Old, hid gold and valuables in the tower.

Figure 76: The hillfort called 'Zamczysko', view of the ramparts and the moats, with fallen trees not removed as it is within the Nature Strict Protection Area, and view of the inner part from the platform for visitors as at November 2022. (National Institute of Cultural Heritage, Agnieszka Makowska)

Figure 77: The hillfort called 'Zamczysko', with marshes visible in the background, as at November 2022. (National Institute of Cultural Heritage, Agnieszka Makowska)

Archaeological research, however, suggests that the castle was in use and was destroyed at a much earlier date. Dates given by archaeologists indicate the 12th to 14th century. There is no consensus among researchers as to whether the castle served as a refuge or was part of a larger fortification system. The more recent history of the site is linked to the period of World War Two. The area of the hillfort was one of the partisan bases. There was an unmarked grave on the rampart. In 2018, archaeologists from the Institute of National Remembrance carried out an archaeological investigation and exhumation of the young man buried there. The research only covered the tomb and did not provide any new information about the hillfort itself.

The current mode of a land use of the site is the result of a model collaboration between the Kampinos Park administration and Voivodship Monuments Preservation Officer, with expert support from the National Institute of Cultural Heritage. Due consideration was given to the need to protect both the archaeological and natural heritage. The single platform is accessed by a staircase located on the western side of the hillfort. Made of composite planks, it has minimal impact on the existing cultural landscape, and does not require frequent repairs. The needs of tourism have also been taken into account. It makes it possible to enjoy the natural and archaeological heritage.

Figure 78: 'Zamczysko' - Digital Terrain Model, with a double ring of ramparts and two moats visible. (National Institute of Cultural Heritage, <https://mapy.zabytek.gov.pl/nid/>)

Assessing significance – methods and results

Based on the Polish monument protection law and criteria enumerated in the legal definition of an archaeological monument, we can articulate historical and scientific significance of the hillfort 'Zamczysko'. We are certainly dealing with the underground remains of the human activity, composed of cultural layers and works or traces contained in these layers. And, it was the state of preservation – the original strata and structures, largely preserved in situ – that had the greatest influence on the assessment of the monument's significance. They have considerable scientific potential. They are a time capsule, an almost complete record of how the site functioned in the past for future generations. This is what makes the place special. The same applies to the cultural landscape – all its components have been protected for centuries, including the preserved terrain form and the exposure of the monument and its surroundings. The hillfort is in close proximity to hiking and biking trails, and is a popular destination for trips from Warsaw. It is also of great educational significance. Using various criteria to assess the significance of the monument concerned, it is impossible to ignore the aesthetic and natural values considered important by the public perception. It is a beautiful green space for rest and reflection. This is a reflection on the difficult contemporary history and the events of World War Two, which also gives the place a symbolic value.

7.16 The Church of St Nicholas and the Romanesque Cellar, Gdańsk, Poland

Agnieszka Makowska

Location and surroundings

The relics of the oldest monumental architecture in Gdańsk are located in the heart of the city's historic centre. The masonry Romanesque St Nicholas Church are exhibited in situ inside the historic Market Hall which is owned by a private company. The Romanesque Cellar, part of the 13th-century monastery, is presented nearby, beneath Dominikański Square, between the gothic church of St Nicholas (Fig.80) and the Market Hall. This is the area of the so-called Dominican Hillock (Kępa Dominikańska), a slight land elevation in the north-western part of historic Main Town (Fig.79).

Gdańsk is one of Poland's oldest cities of great historical importance. The first mention of Gdańsk dates back to 997 AD and comes from the life of St Adalbert. In the 13th century Gdańsk was granted a city charter modelled on Lübeck law. The next stage in its history was the period of occupation by the Teutonic

Order. This resulted in the granting of a new privilege for the Main Town under the Chełmno law. In 1361 Gdańsk, a port city of growing importance, became a member of the Hanseatic League, which allowed it to engage in maritime trade on favourable terms. After the victorious war with the Teutonic Knights, it was incorporated into Poland in 1454. This was a golden period in Gdańsk's history, both economically – as a major trading port, prospering from the export of grain, salt and timber floated down the Vistula from all over the Commonwealth – and culturally – as a city open to foreigners, attracting artists and craftsmen from other European centres, who found wealthy patrons among Gdańsk's burghers. Late Gothic brick churches, townhouses, military buildings and modern structures by prominent Northern European architects, who gave the city its distinctive image, account for its exceptional artistic qualities. Only a few cities in northern Europe have retained so much of their pre-18th century urban structure. Thus, Gdańsk today is a showcase of late and post-medieval urban heritage. It is also one of the most valuable architectural and urban ensembles in Poland. An estimated 3 million tourists visit Gdańsk every year.

Figure 79: Fragment of the plan of the city of Gdansk from 1615, with the St Nicholas Church and Dominican monastery in the centre. (Source: electronic collection of the National Archives of Sweden (Riksarkivet) - riksarkivet.se, Reference code: SE/KrA/0406/25/044/013)

Figure 80: St Nicholas Church, as it stands today. (National Institute of Cultural Heritage, Agnieszka Makowska)

Reasons for assessment

The need to assess the significance of the relics came with their discovery. They were discovered during rescue excavations conducted by the Archaeological Museum in Gdańsk. The first archaeological works carried out in the area were related to the renovation of the Market Hall and the lowering of its basement to create additional retail space. The research began in 2001. The biggest, most sensational discovery was the foundations of the nave and the choir, with an apse of St Nicholas Church (Fig.80). An investment was underway, so an assessment of the value of the artefacts uncovered was needed to make decisions about the future of the site. The same goes for the remains of the first Dominican cloister. The excavations that led to the discovery of the Romanesque Cellar initially were carried out as part of the renovation of Dominican Square, which is now an area of an open-air market. Significance assessment was an essential part of the decision-making process for the relics found.

Description of the site

The construction of the masonry Romanesque Church began, most probably, at the end of the 12th century. Physical and chemical tests showed that the first church was erected around the year 1190. As a result of excavations, the plan of the oldest church was defined. It had a single nave made of stone, two towers made of brick from the west and the apse from the east. According to the researchers from the Archaeological Museum in Gdańsk, the entrance was between the towers. The church was 34.5 m long. It was founded on the site of a cemetery, which was still in use at the time the church was built.

Archaeologists found that some parts of the building had collapsed in a fire at the beginning of the 13th century. At the end of January 1227, the Duke of Gdańsk, Świętopętk, handed over St Nicolas' church to the Dominicans, who had just arrived in the city. They have been part of the city's history ever since, often at the centre of events. The Dominicans rebuilt the church according to the Latin cross plan using salvaged materials. The buildings of their monastery from this period were erected to the south of the church, on the border of the town housing.

Figure 81: Inside the historic Market Hall, with relics of the Romanesque church on the ground floor. (National Institute of Cultural Heritage, Agnieszka Makowska)

In 1308 Gdańsk was attacked by the Teutonic Knights. The town was in flames. That was also when the monastery and once again the church burned down. The church was then rebuilt a short distance away to the south, where it stands today. On the ruins of the destroyed monastery as well as in place of the former church, a new Gothic monastery was founded. There were more and more monks living within the walls, and intellectual life and preaching flourished. The monastery survived almost unchanged until the Napoleonic army entered Gdańsk in 1807. It was then converted into a large field hospital, and continued to be used this way until its destruction by the Russian army in 1813. In 1896, a Market Hall was built on the site of the destroyed monastery. Registered as a monument, the Market Hall still performs its original function.

The church's stone foundations, partly open to the public after conservation work, are now to be found under the Market Hall (Figs.82 & 83). These are displayed on the lowest floor of the hall. The exhibition, in the form of an underground archaeological museum which includes the remnants of the church's chancel and parts of the nave, can also

be seen from the level of the two upper floors of the building, the ground floor and the mezzanine level, as a free space has been designed above the relics. It is surrounded by a glass fence. There are food stalls all around it, frequented by local people who can come into contact with the heritage as they go about their daily shopping. The excavation, conservation and exhibition were fully funded by the owner of the Market Hall, the Dominican Merchant Company. The hall is currently being renovated by its new owner. It is being converted into a three-level food hall, meeting place and concert venue. Relics from the church will still be on exhibit.

The Romanesque Cellar is the only surviving late Romanesque brick building in Gdańsk (Fig.83). It is the remains of a hall from the 13th century with a vaulted ceiling supported by a single pillar. It is well preserved, at 60 per cent, including important parts of the unique vault. According to the researchers, its floor was originally about 1.2 metres below the level of the ground at that time. The room served as a refectory of the first Dominican monastery. A kitchen with a brick oven attached to the refectory, the staircase leading to the refectory floor and an entrance from the south

Figure 82: Dominican Square, now an open-air market, directly above the Romanesque Cellar. The Market Hall in the background, on the left. (Narodowy Instytut Dziedzictwa, Agnieszka Makowska)

with a brick vestibule have also been discovered as remains of the first monastic complex. In 2009 it was decided to open the cellar to the public. To make it possible, a concrete structure was built above the cellar. The underground archaeological open-air museum, a branch of the Archaeological Museum in Gdańsk, was open to the public in 2015 (Figs.82 & 83). Visitors are led through a light and sound show. There is also a film about the history of the cellars, full of visual reconstructions of the church and monastery through the ages.

Assessing significance – methods and results

The discovery of relics under the Market Hall and bazaar in Dominican Square was sensational, but required difficult decisions to be made, with a huge amount of time and money behind them. The renovation of the Market Hall, which began in 2001, was planned to take 15 months. As a result of the archaeological discoveries relating to the Church of St Nicholas, the Voivodship Monuments Preservation Officer had altered recommendations for the restorative of the Hall. Changes were made to the interior renovation project to expose the discovered foundations. In the end, the renewal work took 5 years.

The Romanesque Cellar was discovered in 2006. Initially, it was decided that after the research, the cellar would be filled in. This decision was met with protests from the archaeological, art history and conservation communities. It was argued that the parts

Figure 83: The Romanesque Cellar, part of the 13th-century monastery, now the branch of the Archaeological Museum in Gdańsk. (Narodowy Instytut Dziedzictwa, Agnieszka Makowska)

of the vaults that had survived would most likely be destroyed when they were filled in again. The criteria for assessing significance of the relics were outlined in a letter to the General Monument Preservation Officer. It was emphasised that it is the only surviving brick late-Romanesque building in Gdańsk. The criteria used were local uniqueness and relevance to the local community. It is also valuable for its historical and symbolic value, as the only monument of its kind from pre-Teutonic Gdańsk and as an object associated with the Dominican Order, whose history is closely interwoven with that of the city. The cellar and the remains of the first church exposed in the market hall form an architectural complex. As stated in the letter, both should be made available to visitors for their educational and aesthetic value. The good state of preservation is a starting point in confirming the importance of the discovery. In the end, the General Monument Preservation Officer intervened, and it was decided to open the cellar to the public. It took several years to prepare the monument for its role as a museum, including the reconstruction of damaged parts of the walls and ceiling, conservation and groundwater protection. The costs of the project were shared by the City of Gdańsk, the local government of the Pomeranian Voivodship, the Archaeological Museum in Gdańsk and the Minister of Culture and National Heritage.

Conclusions

The present and the future constantly meet the past in the centres of historic cities. In such places, it is the past that forms the identity of the city. Wise dialogue with the space of historic cities can further their branding or visual identity. Its past gives the town a unique character that could be very attractive to tourists. It strengthens the bonds between residents and unites the community.

Survey on the knowledge and awareness of Poles about the archaeological heritage, carried out in 2020, shows that, according to the vast majority of respondents (98%-99%), archaeological heritage is a testimony to our history and an important source of knowledge for future generations. This heritage allows the inhabitants to feel proud of where they live (95%), which they consider to be unique (96%). As many as 83% of respondents were of the opinion that archaeological sites in their area could be of economic or tourist value. This should be an important voice when assessing the significance of the archaeological relics. It's worth knowing that respondents would most often like to take part in guided tours and archaeology-related displays, which fits in well with the solution proposed for the Romanesque Cellar.

It is essential to survey and record archaeological features in advance, using non-intrusive methods. This includes the analysis of archival maps, photographs and

documents, especially in historic towns. This will allow time and money to be secured for detailed research, thorough documentation and conservation, as well as significance assessment and making decision. This requires a multi-disciplinary approach, involving not only archaeologists and heritage managers, but also local authorities, town planners, architects, engineers and hydrologists (to predict the impact of the decision on the surrounding area, for example on neighbouring buildings or changes in water levels).

When deciding whether or not to protect an archaeological monument, the utmost care needs to be taken. The destruction of the archaeological relics is irreversible, and excavation research is an experiment that cannot be repeated. And it is a decision on behalf of future generations, not just today's needs. The social benefits of an archaeological site are an important consideration before a decision is made. The example of Gdańsk shows that it is well worth the effort.

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank Maciej Szyszka, who led the archaeological research under the Market Hall and on Dominikański Square, and is also the head of the Romanesque Cellar – branch of the Archaeological Museum in Gdańsk, for all the valuable information and insights into the relics described.

7.17 Dumbarton Rock, Scotland UK

Alex Hale

This case study describes a recent project that aimed to explore the significance of Dumbarton Rock, as a site of rock-climbing heritage, in terms of heritage and enabling community participation in the cultural heritage management system in Scotland. Dumbarton Rock comprises a number of heritage management legal designations, including one [Scheduled Ancient Monument](#), a number of [Listed Buildings](#), a geological Site of Special Scientific Interest and it is a significant location in the heritage of Scottish rock-climbing. This case study focusses on the 'living heritage' of an archaeological site, and how, as archaeological managers we can enable engaged communities to contribute to the management of these sites and so ensure that their heritage is taken into account as part of the conservation management of the place. This case study illustrates how Intangible Cultural Heritage can be place-based and why archaeological heritage management projects can enable community engagement, especially when it facilitates a better understanding of alternative and diverse heritages.

Context

[Dumbarton Rock](#) comprises a volcanic outcrop that stands on the north edge of the Firth of Clyde, 24km north-west of Glasgow city centre. The rock stands up to 73m tall but appears greater in height given the flat topography of the surrounding estuary (Fig.84). The following describes the context of the Rock and its early History:

'The twin peaks of Dumbarton Rock (a volcanic plug similar in origin to Edinburgh and Stirling Castle Hills) rise dramatically from the north shore of the Clyde at its confluence with the River Leven to form a site of great natural strength, which is reputed to have the longest recorded history of any fortification in Britain. From at least the 5th century AD it served as the principal stronghold of the Britons of Strathclyde, thereafter it was a royal castle, and during the postmedieval period the castle was used as an artillery fortress guarding the approaches to Glasgow.' (Stevenson 1985).

Figure 84: Dumbarton Rock in the Firth of Clyde. (Historic Environment Scotland)

As described above, the location and imposing geological form of the rock have been utilized by people over thousands of years and surviving archaeological remains cover the surface of the rock. These remains range in age from late Iron Age artefacts to the most recent military uses, which continued until 1909 when the responsibility for the rock was transferred from the War Office, to the Office of Works. The rock was used in World War Two, with four anti-aircraft guns positioned on the top. On the night of the 5th of May 1941, the rock was hit by four bombs. Since the war, the rock has functioned as an ex-military base, with occasional military events and in more recent years has become a major tourist attraction, managed by Historic Environment Scotland ([HES](#)).

‘Statement of Significance’ and cultural heritage management at HES sites in care

HES manages 336 properties, these range from castles, stone circles, industrial mills to archaeological landscapes, churches and Cold War installations, on behalf of Scottish Ministers and the people of Scotland. Each site is protected by legal designations, administered through specific place-based management plans and described in detail in a document known as a ‘Statement of Significance’. As can be seen in the accompanying [Statement of Significance for Dumbarton Castle](#), the format of the document for Dumbarton Castle follows acknowledged cultural heritage management protocols and is divided into the following sections:

- Synopsis
- Character of the Monument: comprising an historical timeline
- Archaeological Overview: details of excavations
- Architectural/Artistic Overview: historical details
- Social Overview: evidence of the significance of the site in the recent past, including ‘the importance of the site for the climbing and bouldering community’
- Spiritual Overview: religious associations
- Aesthetic Overview: natural and topographical associations and connotations
- Assessment of Significance

The final section, ‘Assessment of Significance’, comprises a section of key points, which highlights what are considered to be the major characteristics that make the site of regional, national and international significance. It also includes ‘Associated Properties’, such as other sites in Scotland that are of similar age and significance, demonstrating a landscape networked with significant sites. The final part of the Dumbarton Castle Statement of Significance includes an appendix entitled ‘Dumby: A contribution provided by Dumbarton Rock Climbers’.

The reasons why this case study can be of interest to heritage management practice more widely, are threefold:

- To develop new methodological, practice-based approaches to understanding significance
- To expand our conceptualisation of what archaeology can be and how archaeology is practiced at sites of ‘alternative’ heritages
- With a view to critiquing assumptions around expertise and knowledge sharing through engagement approaches

Figure 85: Graffiti and climbers chalk on the surface of the rock. (Historic Environment Scotland)

The Significance of Rock-Climbing at Dumbly

Recently the climbing heritage at Dumbarton Rock, or 'Dumbly' as it is known to the community of climbers, was one of ten sites across Scotland that were the focus of a research, partnership project called ACCORD (Archaeology Community Co-production of Research Data). The project aimed to enable communities to record heritage sites of their choice, using digital recording methods (Jeffrey et al, 2020). Most groups chose traditional archaeological sites and monuments, from a Bronze Age standing stone and an Iron Age roundhouse to World War Two memorials. Clearly, the site of Dumbarton Rock with its massive boulders and huge vertical wall of volcanic rock stand out from this group as 'untraditional' heritage. But as discovered during the project, the practice of climbing and bouldering has a long tradition, across Scotland and beyond. During the project it became clear that the site was significant because the climbers, present and past, had formed close physical and psychological connections with the materiality of the rock (Fig.85). Through the acts of climbing (and falling!), coming into close, sustained contact with the climbs, the holds, the problems and the physical presence of the rock, a sense of significance was established and that increased through further engagement with the place.

Dumbly presents climbers with a concentration of boulders around the foot of the volcanic rock and an extensive vertical and in places over-hanging main crag, on the shoreline of the Firth of Clyde (see photo in the Canmore archive). The climbing route known as Rhapsody (E11 7a) on the main crag, was first ascended by Dave MacLeod in 2006 (Ryan, 2006). It is still considered one of the hardest traditional climbing routes in Scotland, and the first route in Britain with such a high level of difficulty (E11). This climb is one of the many reasons why the significance of climbing heritage at Dumbarton Rock provides an important case study for heritage management practice.

By collaborating with the climbing community, we were able to learn about a new form of heritage, apply archaeological recording methods (RTI survey and terrestrial laser scanning), with the climbers to record the boulders and topography of boulders and the climbing routes (Fig.86). In this way the project developed a knowledge sharing practice, recorded a new form of 'living' heritage, expanded the types of subjects that archaeology can engage

with, to understand how people engage with the materiality of a part of Scotland. As a final part of the project, we worked with the climbers to enable them to incorporate their interpretation of the social significance of the site into the official Statement of Significance. This was the first time that community participants had been enabled to contribute to a Statement of Significance. In addition, the Statement is complimented by an academic paper that the project partners wrote collaboratively with the climbers. The paper outlines the methods applied and discusses the outputs, outcomes and the impacts that this form of co-production approach can have on significance and values, when alternative heritages are engaged with by archaeologists (Hale et al, 2017).

Figure 86: The project field team. (Historic Environment Scotland)

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